

MRV4SOC PROJECT

Report on the Factors Hindering/Enabling Stakeholders' and Farmers' Adoption of C Farming – D4.1

WP4, T4.1 Mapping of Factors Hindering/Enabling Stakeholders and Farmers Adopting C Farming in each Region

Authors: Andrea Declich and Claudia Colonnello (K&I)

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Table of contents

Table of contents.....	3
List of Tables	4
Acknowledgements	5
Executive Summary.....	6
Section A – Introduction	7
1. Background information on the MRV4SOC project	7
2. Theoretical and methodological frameworks	8
2.1. What is the map and to whom is it addressed?	8
2.2. The map creation process	9
Section B – Towards the “final” map.....	18
1. How the “final” Map was built	18
1.1. Processing data and information collected through the Consultation of the reviewers	18
1.2. Processing the information collected during the workshops	20
1.3. Presentation of the factors and the comments.	20
Section C – Conclusions	67
1. Some final considerations	67
2. Policy suggestions emerged from the validation process	71
A. CF and VCM mechanisms that are implementable	72
B. Work on how CF and VCMs produce beneficial effects	72
C. The promotion of CF and VCM is a complex process	73
D. Promoting research	74
E. Provision of continuing assistance to the actors involved in CF and VCM	74
3. Gender issues	75
4. Further research	76
References	77
Annexes	78
Annex 1 Forms of the 134 individual factors and sources of the documentary analysis.....	79
Annex 2 Questions for the workshops	160

List of Tables

Table 1 – Type of categories, Categories and Subcategories.....	10
Table 2 – Example of the forms presenting each factor and its main characteristics.....	13
Table 3 – Main characteristics of the experts consulted	14
Table 4 – Overview of the five multi-actor dialogue workshops	17
Table 5 – Matrix for the corroboration of the CF-related factors	19
Table 6 – Forms on CF-related factors	21
Table 7 – Forms on non-CF-related-factors.....	21
Table 8 – The Final map	67
Table 9 – List of Policy suggestions.....	71

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- **Francisco José Blanco Velázquez**, Project Manager of projects on soil protection at EVENOR-Tech, Tech S.L.U. - Soluciones para el uso y protección del suelo (*Sevilla, Spain*)
- **Julie Ingram**, PhD, Professor of Innovation for Sustainable Agriculture CCRI- Countryside and Community Research Institute, University of Gloucestershire (*Gloucestershire, UK*)
- **Zöhre Kurt**, Associate Professor, METU-Middle East Technical University (*Ankara, Turkey*)
- **Thomas B. Long**, Associate Professor of Entrepreneurship at EDHEC Business School, Faculty of Strategy, Entrepreneurship & Operations, expert in entrepreneurship and strategy for a regenerative economy, (*Nice, France*)
- Dr **Jane Mills**, Associate Professor in Agri-Environmental Behaviours, CCRI-Countryside and Community Research Institute, University of Gloucestershire (*Gloucestershire, UK*)
- **Stefano Monaco**, PhD, CREA - IT, Research Centre for Engineering and Agro-food processing, Turin, Research Centre of the CREA-Consiglio per la ricerca in agricoltura e l'analisi dell'economia agraria (*Turin, Italy*)
- **Marc Rosiers**, Senior Advisor, European Policy Group, ELO-European Landowners Organisation (*Bruxelles, Belgium*)
- **Benjamin Sanchez Gimeno**, Department Environment and Agronomy of the Instituto Nacional de Investigación y Tecnología Agraria y Alimentaria INIA, Research Centre integrated within the CSIC-Consejo Superior de Investigaciones Científicas (*Madrid, Spain*)
- **Alberto Sanz Cobeña**, Research Centre for the Management of Agricultural and Environmental Risks (CEIGRAM), Universidad Politécnica de Madrid (UPM), (*Madrid, Spain*)
- **Thalisa Slier**, MSc, Researcher on sustainable soil use, Wageningen Environmental Research, WUR-Wageningen University (*Wageningen, The Netherlands*)
- **Goedele Van den Broeck**, Assistant professor in agricultural economics, Earth and Life Institute at the UCLouvain-University of Louvain (*Louvain, Belgium*)
- **Bas van Wesemael**, Full Professor in Physical Geography at the Université catholique de Louvain (*Louvain, Belgium*)

It is worth noticing that the other reviewers who expressed a positive orientation in being involved in the consultation, but who were unable to contribute because of concurrent commitments during the planned timeline of the project, will be considered for possible future participatory activities promoted in the framework of WP4 and for the establishing MRV4SOC's Community of Practice.

Finally, with reference to the territorial experts engaged in the territorial workshops, detailed information will be provided within a devoted MRV4SOC's deliverable (D4.4), aimed at reporting the participatory activities promoted in the framework of WP4 and to give credit to the system of actors involved in it.

Executive Summary

The Deliverable 4.1 (D4.1) titled “Report on the Factors Hindering/Enabling Stakeholders’ and Farmers’ Adoption of C Farming” contains the results of the activities of Work Package 4 (WP4) of the MRV4SOC project, a Horizon Europe Research Project on Monitoring, Reporting and Verification (MRV) of Carbon Farming,

According to the DoA this Deliverable contains the main outcome of Task 4.1, namely the final version of the “Map” of factors hindering/enabling stakeholders and farmers to adopt C Farming in each Region. To this end, the main objective of the report is to present the final Map and the process through which the Map was built, which included a literature review, a consultation of experts, and the implementation of five territorial multi-actor workshops in four European countries. These activities have been carried out under the responsibility of K&I and with the participation of several MRV4SOC partners.

This Report is composed of three sections. The first one contains a presentation of the institutional framework and a description of the structure of the Report, a brief presentation of the theoretical and methodological approaches of the mapping process, and a description of the activities carried out. The second section of the Report is devoted to the presentation of the main results achieved from the implementation of T4.1, including the features and the structure of the final Map of hindering and enabling (H/E) factors after its validation process. The third and final section of the report is devoted to some conclusions, with general considerations on the results obtained, to some preliminary policy suggestions, and to some indications for further research. Finally, two annexes are attached: a. Forms of the individual factors as they are after the validation; and b. Short presentation of the questions/issues proposed for discussion in the five workshops.

Section A – Introduction

1. Background information on the MRV4SOC project

This document presents the main outcome of Task 4.1 “Mapping of factors hindering/enabling stakeholders and farmers adopting C farming in each region”, of the European RIA project titled “Monitoring, Reporting and Verification of Soil Organic Carbon and Greenhouse Gas Balance – MRV4SOC”. The core of this report is devoted to the presentation of the final version of the “Map of the Factors Hindering/Enabling Stakeholders' and Farmers' Adoption of Carbon Farming”, as result of an articulated mapping process during which documentary and live sources were analysed and consulted for its building and “validation”.

MRV4SOC is a Horizon Europe Research Project on Monitoring, Reporting and Verification (MRV) of Carbon farming, aimed at ensuring robust, transparent, and cost-effective results. MRV4SOC aims to account for changes in as many Carbon pools as possible, estimate Green House Gases (GHG) and full Carbon budgets, couple Carbon and Nitrogen cycles, quantify Soil Organic Carbon (SOC) accumulation, and assess the results of traditional management practices and carbon farming. By tackling the issues of soil organic carbon monitoring, reporting and verification, the project aims therefore to contribute to the general goal of climate neutrality.

In particular, MRV4SOC aims to target **six specific objectives**:

- i) To measure long-term Soil Organic Carbon (SOC) accumulation in nine EU representative Land Use, Land Cover (LULC) classes
- ii) To assess how carbon farming practices drive carbon flux dynamics in the nine LULC classes
- iii) To assess the impact of climate change on SOC accumulation
- iv) To develop a robust, transparent, standard, and cost-effective MRV to facilitate results-based payments associated with carbon farming practices
- v) To seek out revenue opportunities to unlock results-based payments
- vi) To increase stakeholders' faith in Voluntary Carbon Market.

Within this framework, Work Package 4 “Carbon Farming Credits toward Sustainable Carbon Markets and Socio-Economic Impact Assessment”, led by the University of Louvain, is aimed at the achievement of the three main objectives, through the activities planned under three corresponding tasks:

- a. Understand which factors shape stakeholders' and farmers' adoption of carbon farming practices (CFPs) (T.4.1)
- b. Evaluate the cost-effectiveness of C Farming practices and the MRV tools at the farm level (T4.2)
- c. Assess the socio-economic impacts of CF at the landscape level (T4.3).

The present deliverable falls below Task 4.1, led by Knowledge and Innovation, aimed at identifying the pros and cons of adopting CFPs, building a Map of different kinds of hindering and enabling factors shaping the farmers and stakeholder adoption of CF management practices, and their level of trust toward Carbon Markets, with particular reference to Voluntary Carbon Markets (VCM). To this end, the main results from T4.1 and the Map built on those results are connected mainly to the last three abovementioned objectives of the MRV4SOC project, and the sixth in particular.

The Map is the result of a collaborative research effort promoted by K&I. as Task leader, under T4.1, in which several partners of the Consortium and Demo Site leaders were actively involved¹, providing support to the planned activities and sharing relevant suggestions and insights considered for the setup of the final version of the Map. The Map benefited significantly from the relevant knowledge gained through the consultation of a Panel of experts (hereinafter, also called the reviewers) and through the implementation of five territorial multi-actor dialogue workshops on the challenges and opportunities of CF (see methodological framework). To this end, see the list of the organisations supporting the arrangement of the five territorial workshops and the list of reviewers/experts engaged in the consultation to whom credit is given within the box “Acknowledgments” at the end of this point.

This Report is composed of three sections. This first section contains a presentation of the institutional framework and the description of the structure of the Report, a brief presentation of the theoretical and methodological approaches of the mapping process, and a description of the activities carried out. The second section of the Report is devoted to the presentation of the main results achieved from the implementation of T4.1, namely the features and the structure of the final Map of hindering and enabling (H/E) factors after its validation process. The third and final section of the report is devoted to some conclusions, with general considerations on the results obtained, to some preliminary policy suggestions, and to some indications for further research. Finally, two annexes are attached: a. Forms of the individual factors as they are after the validation; and b. Short presentation of the questions of the five workshops.

It is worth noticing that, while the scientific results achieved through the consultation of reviewers and the implementation of five multi-actor workshops are described in this Report, the detailed description of the participatory activities promoted within T4.1 will be contained in a dedicated deliverable foreseen at the end of the project (D4.4 “Workshops/Events Report”).

2. Theoretical and methodological frameworks

2.1. What is the map and to whom is it addressed?

The core of this document is the Map of the factors that facilitate or hinder the adoption of agricultural practices for Carbon Farming (CF). The term factor refers to a specific event or element that facilitates or hinders the adoption of new practices, particularly those related to CF and carbon markets (CM) and may be connected to a certain agricultural production system, its institutions, norms, habits or the orientations and attitudes of relevant actors.

A theoretical approach based on the sociology of knowledge and science and technology studies (STS) was adopted for the mapping exercise. This approach focuses on the idea that, in addition to the scientific research process, the understanding of reality also comes from the experiential knowledge that the different stakeholders have about the reality in which they operate. Stakeholder knowledge can be used as an element of the research process and thus as a tool to increase scientific knowledge.

Based on this background, the mapping process was of a qualitative type. A meaningful number of documentary and live sources were analysed; the process was aimed at a final corroboration of the factors singled out in the literature based on the comments obtained during the validation process, i.e., aimed at finding more support, thanks to different points of view of stakeholders and experts.

¹ UCL, Université catholique de Louvain; SC, Soil Capital; ULIEGE, University of Liege; CSIC, Consejo Superior de Investigaciones Científicas; INIA-CSIC, Instituto Nacional de Investigación y Tecnología Agraria y Alimentaria; CREA, Consiglio per la Ricerca in Agricoltura e l'Analisi dell'Economia Agraria; CREA - Centro di ricerca Foreste e Legno; ERSAF Lombardia Region, Ente regionale per i servizi all'agricoltura e alle foreste; CZU, Czech University of Life Sciences Prague; ICONS Foundation; EVENOR-Tech; University of Vigo, and GMV.

In fact, Task 4.1. was aimed at acquiring new knowledge on factors shaping the adoption or the rejection of CF and VCM by farmers and stakeholders, building a provisional version of the Map based on the results of a desk research. Then, the final version of the Map was finetuned using new knowledge achieved through the consultation of two different live sources, namely a panel of experts (internal and external to the MRV4SOC Consortium, also called the “reviewers”), and key persons (experts, farmers and other practitioners, policy makers, societal actors representing different perspectives) engaged in focused discussion on CF in five territorial multi actors dialogue workshops.

The analysis presented in the provisional and in the final version of the Map was carried out by a team of K&I. The final Map reported in this deliverable represents a step-forward in terms of knowledge acquisition on the complex typology of factors to be considered for supporting the process of transition toward more effective and sustainable Carbon Farming Practices (CFPs) and policies.

CF policies are designed to mitigate greenhouse gas emissions, but policy success depends on the participation of farmers and land managers and on their adoption of alternative land management practices. In this framework, the provision of this map might contribute to a better understanding of factors of any nature (social, cultural, economic, communicative, legal/regulatory/administrative, environmental, and technological) that might hinder or enable the adoption of new CF management practices or affect the degree of trust toward the access to VCM by farmers and other relevant stakeholders.

Different possible ways of exploitation of the Map may be considered, based on the experience done so far, within the project. To this end, it might be used for different purposes.

- First of all, it is meant as a useful basis for the arrangement of future occasions of interdisciplinary scientific discussions and multidisciplinary dialogue within and outside the MRV4SOC project.
- The Map might also be used for fostering a further dialogue and self-reflection exercise. For example: for keeping alive the engagement of the key players of the different territorial ecosystems connected to the MRV4SOC Demo sites engaged so far and enlarging the process to new ones; for going ahead in the discussion about challenges and opportunities of CF, and in particular for exchanging best practices and solutions useful to overcome existing problems, challenges and barriers.
- It can also be exploited for the design of future participatory activities or research tools foreseen under the other tasks of WP4 (e.g., designing of farmers' survey).
- Finally, the analysis of the H/E factors and the insights and suggestions gathered in the consultation process might represent a starting point for the provision of possible recommendations for policy improvement at the local, national, and European levels and for the identification of effective support measures to put in place in other activities of the project. To this end, the experience gained through the promotion of multi-actor space for dialogue and discussion around the main challenges and benefits of CF can be considered a positive starting point for the design of an effective policy dialogue to be promoted during the following stages of the project.

2.2. The map creation process

The mapping process was conducted by adopting a co-creation approach (in line with the theoretical and methodological approach briefly presented above). It was articulated in three working phases:

- a. Set up of a provisional Map of H/E factors
- b. Validation/development of the Final Map of Factors
- c. Final studies and draft of the Report.

The final version of the Map presented in this deliverable is grounded on the following different activities.

- Documentary analysis (based on desk research of K&I and relevant contributions from the Consortium partners, as internal acknowledged experts and representatives of relevant EU projects focused on Soil and CF).
- Consultation of a panel of reviewers and relevant key stakeholders (internal and external to the MRV4SOC Consortium).
- Planning, co-designing and tailor-made implementation, in collaboration with T4.1 contributing partners and concerned Demo site leaders, of a series of five multi-actor workshops involving farmers and other key territorial stakeholders in five Demo sites from four different European countries (Spain, Belgium, Italy, and Czech Republic), covering different regions/sub-landscapes and focusing on three main land use landscapes (cropland, grassland/pasture and agroforestry)².
- Final studies, aimed at corroborating the final version of the Map of factors, and drafting and review of the present deliverable.

Here below, the main steps of the validation process, with reference to the three working phases mentioned above, are described.

2.2.1. The set up of a preliminary version of the Map: Documentary analysis

As mentioned above, the mapping process started with the identification of H/E factors to CF through a preliminary documentary analysis.

A provisional version of the map was thus set-up, starting from a literature review (with a mainly scoping³ character). It was based on desk research conducted by K&I, through search engines, snowballing, and networking with the Consortium partners and other experts, considered as an acknowledged source for the identification of further relevant scientific literature and documentation.

The literature review included not just scientific, but also the so-called “grey literature”, including policy documents, relevant EU projects’ deliverables, and other relevant documentation produced by the “community of practitioners” (e.g., Reports from National or European Associations of Farmers and Landowners). It dealt with CF and VCMs as well as environmental innovation in agriculture in general.

After a preliminary selection of the sources identified, we reviewed more than 100 texts, read in depth 67 texts (see Sources in Annex 1) and extracted the factors out of 41 texts. When reading, we registered 391 elements that could be of interest. Based on the description contained in the text we were able to understand if these elements could facilitate or hamper the adoption of CF practices or the participation in CM. Successively, we proceeded to look at those that were similar and registered them as the same factor. At the end of this exercise, we had 134 factors, that were grouped into 12 categories and sub-categories (see table 1).

Table 1 – Type of categories, Categories and Subcategories

#	Category	Sub-categories
1 – Ec	Costs and benefits of Carbon Farming practices	a. Costs connected to the practice/innovation b. Policy on subsidies and incentives c. Effects on profitability and yields d. Farming systems interactions

² The workshops were arranged in collaboration with the WP6 and T6.2 concerned partners as responsible of the more general MRV4SOC’s strategy of engagement of stakeholders aimed at the building of a Community of Practice in MRV4SOC in each country present in the project. To this end; the T4.1 workshops were included within a general event; part of which devoted to the first round of “multiplier events” (see T6.2). A detailed description of these participatory events will be reported within another deliverable foreseen under WP4; namely D4.4. “Workshops/Events Report”; due at the end of the project.

³ About the scoping review see: Arksey and O'Malley, 2005; Munn et al, 2018.

#	Category	Sub-categories
		e. Market and sector dynamics (demand and supply sides) f. Access to resources (human and social capital)
2 – Ec	VCM and innovative practices	a. Farming system interaction with VCM b. VCM uncertainty c. VCM implementation costs
3 – S/C	Orientation towards the environment and drive for change	a. Social pressure (from peers, local communities, etc.) b. Pro-environment sentiment c. Information/knowledge d. Orientation/ability to change e. Utilitarian vs Non-utilitarian orientation
4 – Te	Technological and operational complexity of innovation	a. Time required for change b. Complexity of the technologies and the control system c. Role of actors in the implementation
5 – Po	Role of advisory, information and training services, soil illiteracy	a. Advisory needs for CF technologies and VCM procedures b. Advisory agencies' skills and capacities c. General weaknesses of advisory agencies
6 – Po	Policies and regulation	a. Rules impeding CF adoption b. Effective regulation c. Diverse contexts and conditions of policies' implementation
7 – Te	Differences in impacts across biophysical environment (geographical, temporal) and evaluation of farmers	a. Proximity to agricultural services b. Agricultural practices are affected by the characteristics of location and the farming systems
8 – S/C	Time and risk preferences	a. Land Tenure and succession b. Risks and uncertainty
9 – Po	Externalities and spillovers	
10 – S/C	Habits (including consumers' ones)/ Resilience of existing organisational arrangements	
11 – Te	Access/Lack of basic infrastructures and technologies	
12 – S/C	Gendered different behaviour	

The cells' background colour indicates the type of category, as indicated in the Legend below. Anyhow, next to the number of the category is reported also an acronym indicating its type.

Ec	Economic	S/C	Social/cultural	Te	Technical	Po	Policy
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In the Map, the factors are grouped starting from how they were described in the texts, according to their similarities and connections and not according to disciplinary criteria (e.g., through categories labelled as economic, social, legal)⁴.

The reason for this choice is that the identified factors were very diverse. Often, they were labelled according to idiosyncratic approaches. Therefore, it would have been difficult to label them as e.g., purely economic while they consisted of phenomena that were somehow mixed and could be also

⁴ We found analogous descriptive approaches in some analyses of barriers to CFP; i.e. those Sykes; et al 2020. and Raina et al. 2024.

defined according to, for example, socio-economic or legal perspectives⁵. Efforts were made to prevent any predetermined viewpoint from influencing the way the problem of promoting CF has to be handled.

The same categories could be, anyhow, recognized as belonging to certain disciplinary areas. For example, the category concerning the “costs and benefits of Carbon Farming practices” or that on “VCM and innovative practices” are clearly economic in nature, while the category on “Habits (including consumers' ones)/Resilience of existing organisational arrangements” is of a socio-cultural type. A post-hoc classification of these types into each category was performed, without affecting the approach of clustering factors according to their commonalities.

This further aggregation is somehow useful because it lets us understand some aspects of the problems that are being faced when trying to promote CF and VCMs. First of all, the effort should be interdisciplinary, putting together experts, actors, and stakeholders with very diverse backgrounds. This is confirmed by the fact that one of the types of categories – Policy – is characterised by the centrality of diverse actors, their interactions, and orientations concerning the promotion of agriculture and sustainability – those who make and implement policies. Such actors have to co-operate by managing interactions that have “hybrid” nature, i.e., jointly technical, economic and social, whose rationale must consider such complexity and include a holistic approach.

The four types of categories are: **economic**, i.e., connected with the costs and benefits of practicing CF and participating in the VCMs; **social/cultural**, i.e., connected with the characteristics of the role of actors involved in implementing or promoting CF and VCMs; **Technical**, i.e., the operational aspects connected to the technologies CF consists of; **Policy**, i.e., connected to the initiatives undertaken by actors for promoting and implementing CF and VCMs.

This choice about how to organise the description of the Map made it more user-friendly to better help stakeholders to adapt interventions and policies to what occurs in the process of innovation they try to foster.

Our literature review also included texts that in turn reported on other literature reviews. This adds up to a greater outreach to this map since it considers somehow the already accumulated knowledge on the matter. A further characteristic of this map is that it is based on diverse sources covering various disciplinary domains (also sociology, political sciences, economics and not just the more technical and specialised fields connected to agriculture).

In the literature review search criteria were included for considering not just factors directly connected to CF or VCMs, but also those connected to the so-called Climate Smart Agriculture (CSA), conservative agriculture, and other environment-friendly practices. This choice was made for two reasons. On the one hand, some of these practices – e.g., no-tillage practice or agroforestry – imply CF, although not aimed at creating carbon credits; on the other hand, such practices are promoted for the same purpose of CF, i.e., achieving environmental sustainability. Factors affecting the adoption of these practices could be strongly analogous to those affecting CF practices and the reactions that could be met when practicing CF could be similar to those that could emerge when practicing other environmental innovations. This “inclusive” approach seemed desirable and useful since promoting CF and establishing VCMs are examples of relatively recent European agricultural policies aimed at introducing production and management innovation. Figuring out what obstacles and facilitating factors could be met and addressed to pursue them should depart from similar experiences.

⁵ As it is clear from the table above; there is anyhow some disciplinary prevalence; as some categories are mainly economic (e.g. the first two); while others are more focused on mainly technical issues (the 4th and 12th); or on social and organisational issues (the 3rd and the 5th). The point is that the factors were taken from a wide array of sources and the authors belonged to very different research or professional (in the case of gray literature) fields. They tend to use descriptive approaches that could change significantly and harmonizing such different approaches would not avoid the risk of overlapping definitions.

This inclusive approach implied that some factors initially listed in the Map could be related to CF or play a role in the CFP promotion process, even if not explicitly discussed in the consulted sources⁶. As a result, the initial map categorized factors as 'CF-related' or 'non-CF-related'. This distinction was necessary since the risk was doing an incomplete Map and missing the possibility of using the valuable existing knowledge about innovation in agriculture. Anyhow, this distinction – made in the first version of the Map – was not relevant anymore after the validation (see below).

In Annex 1, all 134 factors of the preliminary Map are presented with their form (see table 2 below)⁷ illustrating all the descriptors used, as well as the information provided by the reviewers.

Table 2 – Example of the forms presenting each factor and its main characteristics

#3	Financial constraints (due also to equipment costs of establishment)	
Description	Carbon Sequestration practices often imply upfront adoption costs, and investments in equipment. This may create financial constraints.	
Explicitly mentioned in the literature as relevant for Carbon Farming	Yes	
Factor type: Hindering/facilitating	Hindering	
Type of CFP for which is relevant (according to the source)	Water and tillage management; agroforestry, cover cropping, catch cropping and residue return	
Concerned actors	Farmers	
Gender perspective is considered in the analysis of the factor	No	
Sources:	23; 30; 41; 43; 44; 58; 63; 64; 67	

References are given in the section “Sources” of Annex 1, with a number for each text considered. Each factor’s form indicates the relative numbers under the heading ‘source’.

2.2.2. The process of “validation” of the preliminary Map: Consultation of Panel of experts

The provisional Map was used as the basis of the validation process, therefore as a tool to guide a reflection on these factors based on what emerges from the process of accumulation of knowledge currently ongoing in various relevant research fields⁸. More in particular, the process was conceived as a way for gathering new knowledge and passing from a preliminary (or “ideal”) map of factors (based on consolidated knowledge) to a final (or “real”) map of factors, in which the relevance, the diffusion and other aspects were corroborated through the consultation of other live sources of scientific and experiential knowledge.

Thus, the preliminary map was used for conducting the consultation of experts, as a part of a co-creation exercise in which they were asked to contribute to identifying these factors by providing their comments and suggestions based on their field expertise.

In this framework, the reviewers were asked to fill in a small questionnaire at the end of the description of each factor. We asked them to look at all the categories of factors, but we gave them the possibility to provide their feedback on some categories only, those for which they felt to have more expertise and knowledge.

⁶ If a certain factor emerged both from the sources that did mention CF and others that did not; we assumed that it could be connected to CF.

⁷ The forms in Annex 1 contain also other relevant information emerged from the review process.

⁸ For an interesting presentation of the issue of knowledge accumulation process, see Towne and Shavelson, 2002.

The questions asked concerned:

- The very existence of the factor about which the reviewer should say how much, according to them, the factor is known
- The relevance of the factor (the literature and documents we consulted, according to the readers, could have overemphasised a factor or underestimated it)
- The CFP for which the factor is particularly relevant
- The geographical distribution of the factor
- The type of land use (i.e., landscape, such as croplands, pastures, forestry, peatlands, etc.) in which the factor is particularly relevant (the reader is requested to provide a point of view about these issues)
- The (possible) connection between the factor with gender, or with other social categorisations such as religion, race, class, etc. (if yes, the readers should briefly describe such connection).

Those listed above were the questions concerning the **CF-related factors**. There were fewer questions for the **non-CF-related-factors**, and concerned:

- The knowledge of the reviewers of the factor
- Their opinion about the relevance of the factor to CFP adoption
- The (optional) explanation about this relevance.

Here below are briefly recalled the different steps implemented with a short description of the features of the composition of the Panel of reviewers engaged and some comments shared from the experience done.

The process of involving experts in the consultation was, as always in these cases, complex and took a long time. Various sources were used to identify the experts to be consulted, including the documents analysed, the project partners and around 50 key organisations in the sector at national and international level. An initial list of more than 40 experts was drawn up and their availability to participate in the consultation was requested. Of these, 25 indicated their availability and some also indicated other experts (snowball method).

The map (and the guidelines for its compilation) was then sent to the available experts and an agreement was reached on the date for its return. In the end, a total of 18 experts participated in the consultation. Of the 18-feedback forms sent by the experts, 16 concerned an analytical validation of the factors (although not all in all categories), while 2 experts sent only general feedback, which were nevertheless taken into account in the definition of the map and in the conclusions.

Among these experts (see Table 3 below), there is a good gender balance (10 men and 8 women), the presence of different types of perspectives on CF and VCM (academia or other relevant agricultural research organisations, but also consultants from private organisations, intermediary farmers' organisations, international organisations of the UN system, as well as representatives of other EU projects) and a good territorial distribution among the member countries.

Table 3 – Main characteristics of the experts consulted

	Gender	Type of organisation	Country
1	M	University	Spain
2	F	University	UK
3	M	University	Belgium
4	M	Federation of landowners, land managers and rural entrepreneurs' national associations	Belgium
5	F	Environmental Company	Spain
6	F	University	Turkey
7	F	University	The Netherlands
8	M	Research Public Institution	Germany
9	F	University	UK

	Gender	Type of organisation	Country
10	F	International Organisation	International
11	M	University	France
12	M	University	UK
13	F	Research Public Institution	Italy
14	M	Research Public Institution	Spain
15	M	Research Public Institution	Italy
16	M	University	Belgium
17	M	Private technology-based company	Spain
18	F	University	Belgium

2.2.3. The process of “validation” of the preliminary Map in local context: the 5 multi-actors territorial dialogue workshops

The workshops were part, as said before, of general “multiplier events”⁹, aimed at presenting the MRV4SOC aims and activities in the local context and at engaging an initial core group of actors concerned with CF and the related agricultural policies. This choice helped to minimise the workload for territorial partners and, above all, the so-called “stakeholder fatigue” (i.e., overloading stakeholders with project-related invitations and activities).

The process of organising and implementing the workshops was relatively long and complex. It implied discussions and exchanges with the contributing partners and the Demo site leaders to achieve an agreement on the locations, on the date (for farmers and other types of invitees, meetings could hamper seasonal production activities), on the possible types of actors to engage, and on the themes to be discussed, including the land uses to focus such discussions on.

In the process, various preparatory materials circulated among the involved partners concerning the agendas of the workshops and the multiplier events, guidelines for their design, issues for the workshops’ discussions, translation, etc. Most of these exchanges took place in relation to each workshop through bilateral meetings. Such a “bilateral” approach, and the active involvement of the Demo site leaders, helped to create a positive climate for discussion and interest among the participants.

Each workshop was held based on a set of three thematic areas of discussion relevant to the validation of the map. These areas were discussed, in the various workshops, in three discussion rounds and were focused on: existing challenges, barriers and hindering factors to the adoption of CFPs and the access to VCM; possible benefits, opportunities and solutions for overcoming the identified barriers; suggestions and recommendations for policy improvement (at local and European level) and identification of other supporting measures for addressing existing gaps, expectations and needs.

The questions were formulated – or anyhow raised during the workshops – in such a way that the participants, also those with no specific experience of CFPs and/or VCMs, were encouraged, based on their experience in agriculture and knowledge about technical, juridical and commercial issues, to figure out what the obstacles or facilitating factors could be. The three areas were adapted, in each workshop, to the local needs and workshops’ characteristics (e.g., in Madrid were discussed two types of land uses). For a description of how the workshops contributed to the validation process, see the following section.

It should be stressed that a higher number of participants than expected, representing different perspectives, were engaged in the workshops. Thanks to the active contribution and support from the local partners and the Demo site leaders, the planned number of around 50 participants (up to 10 for

⁹ Within the MRV4SOC Project, two rounds of “multiplier” events are foreseen, in the framework of Task 6.2, aimed at building a MRV4SOC Community of Practice in each country.

each workshop) was exceeded, with the achievement of overall 87 participants, of which 52 men and 37 women. The main information about participation in the workshops is reported in Table 4.

The participants in the workshops represented a multi-actor composition, even though with differences in numbers and type of actors among the five workshops. The different types of actors were farmers and land managers; consultancy organisations/experts on CF and CM/VCM; local/regional/national policymakers and public administration officers; ONG/CSOs/ Environmental foundations; researchers/soil scientists, MRV experts; industry representatives, private company and other business actors.

2.2.4. Final studies and drafting of the final version of the Map

The map, after the validation process, is presented in the following section B. It comprises **127 factors** (i.e., 134 "ideal" factors minus 7 factors not corroborated during validation) grouped into the same 12 categories (and related sub-categories). Such categories have been presented above and did not change after the validation process. Each category and the sub-categories belonging to it are presented in the introduction of the section dedicated to each category. The final list of 127 factors is reported below, in Table 8 at the beginning of Section C. The information collected during the validation process have been processed (see below, paragraphs 1.1 and 1.2 of Section B) and presented accordingly. Section C is dedicated to some conclusions focused on what emerged from the entire mapping exercise. In Annex 1 all the factors are reported (both those corroborated and those that are not) using the form reported in Table 2 and complemented with other relevant information emerged from the review process.

Table 4 – Overview of the five multi-actor dialogue workshops

BELGIUM	SPAIN	ITALY – 1	CZECH REPUBLIC	ITALY – 2
DS6: Dorinne (Namur, Wallonia Region) – <i>Grassland & Pasture</i>	DS7: Extremadura Dehesas (Extremadura) <i>Agroforestry</i> DS2: Alcalà (Madrid) <i>Semi-arid Mediterranean rainfed cropland</i>	DS8: Casale Monferrato , (Alessandria, Piemonte Region) <i>Agroforestry</i>	DS4: Amàlie (Bohemia) <i>Agriculture Croplands</i>	DS3: Giussago (Pavia, Lombardia Region) <i>Agriculture Croplands</i>
When: March 26 th , 2024 Where: Dorinne (Namur Province, Wallonia)	When: April 23 rd , 2024 Where: Madrid, INIA Premise (PdH I)	When: May 15 th , 2024 Where: CREA Foreste e Legno Venue, in Casale Monferrato (Alessandria Province)	When: May 25 th , 2024 Where: CZU – Czech University of Life Science, Prague (in the same area of DS4)	When: June 6 th , 2024 Where: Demo site area in Vellezzo Bellini (Pavia Province)
Organising team: (beside K&I as T4.1 leader): <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ULIEGE, University of Liege • UCL, University Catholique of Louvain • SC, Soil Capital 	Organising team: (beside K&I as T4.1 leader): <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • INIA-CSIC, Instituto Nacional de Investigación y Tecnología Agraria y Alimentaria of the Consejo Superior de Investigaciones Científicas 	Organising team: (beside K&I as T4.1 Leader): <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • CREA-FL Forests and Wood • CREA-IT, Consiglio per la ricerca in agricoltura e l'analisi dell'economia 	Organising team: (beside K&I as T4.1 leader): <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • CZU, Czech University of Life Sciences (Faculty of Agrobiology; Faculty of Environment engaged with DS4) 	Organising team: (beside K&I as T4.1 Leader): <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • CREA-IT, Consiglio per la ricerca in agricoltura e l'analisi economica • ERSAF Lombardia, Ente regionale per i servizi all'agricoltura e alle foreste
Field visit to the Demo site placed in Dorinne	Other MRV4SOC partners attending and contributing: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • GMV (Coordinator) • Evenor-Tech (T6.2 leader) • UVIGO, Universidad de Vigo 	Field visits to: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cascina Nuova (in Valenza) • Fondazione Cappellino (in San Salvatore) 	Field visit to the Demo site placed within the University area (DS4)	Other MRV4SOC partners attending and contributing: ICONS Foundation (WP6 Leader)
TOT Participants: 13 Male: 12 – Female: 1	TOT Participants: 35 Male: 19 – Female: 16	TOT Participants: 16 Male: 7 – Female: 9	TOT Participants: 8 Male: 4 – Female: 4	TOT Participants: 17 Male: 10 – Female: 7

A more analytical description of the participatory activities promoted in the framework of T4.1 with a focused analysis of the actor's composition of the 5 workshops will be reported in the planned D4.4 (due at the end of the project), based on the 5 territorial reports elaborated by the organising teams and K&I.

Section B – Towards the “final” map

1. How the “final” Map was built

As previously emphasized, the 127 factors of the final Map are the outcome of the validation process, which involved a thorough review. The process consisted of two different consultations through which various stakeholders (researchers, farmers, professionals, public officers, etc.) were consulted about facilitating and hindering factors impacting the adoption of CFPs and the entry into VCMs. Firstly, a group of stakeholders reviewed the first version of the Map and its factors answering a brief questionnaire concerning each factor. The reviewers who answered these questions analytically were 16. Secondly, five workshops were held in different locations, connected to some of the Demo sites involved in MRV4SOC.

The following sections will detail the **data processing procedures applied to the information collected** from a) the map reviewers, particularly concerning their 'corroboration,' b) the workshops, and c) the integration of these two sources to provide additional insights into the highlighted factors.

1.1. Processing data and information collected through the Consultation of the reviewers

As a general rule, all the factors initially included in the Map, because they were singled out in the literature, should be considered as existent. Nevertheless, thanks to the review and the discussion held in workshops, we now have a better idea about their actual relevance. Furthermore, it was feasible to ascertain if the so-called “non-CF-related” factors are indeed relevant also for the promotion of CF. As for the **CF-related factor**, we considered as **corroborated** those factors that responded to two criteria:

1. were known by the respondents, and
2. considered relevant for bringing about the adoption of CFPs.

The first criterion was to gauge that a certain factor is known beyond the boundaries of specific scientific or professional communities. The second criterion was aimed at indicating that a certain factor is not notional but actual, i.e., important in bringing about CFPs adoption. Using these criteria, we were able to know that our panel of reviewers did know a certain factor and that they considered it relevant. It was a form of **corroboration**, in the sense that we gave more support, thanks to different points of view, to what we took from the documentary review.

Each factor was considered “known” based on the ratio of reviewers who declared to know it to the set of reviewers who provided feedback on the factor’s reference category. A value between 0 and 1 was thus obtained, which provided a rough indication of the degree of knowledge (Well known, Known and Little known) of each factor according to the following thresholds:

- $\geq 0,67$ → The factor was defined as “well-known”
- $\geq 0,34$ and $< 0,67$ → the factor was defined as “Known”
- > 0 and $< 0,34$ → the factor was defined as “Little known”
- 0 → the factor was defined as “Not known”.

Regarding relevance, a similar approach was taken. The responses to the question 'In your opinion, how relevant is this factor for the adoption of CFPs in general?' were analysed. The proportion of those who rated the factor as 'relevant' or 'very relevant' was calculated among those who had answered 'Yes' to the previously discussed question.

If the score was:

- $\geq 0,67$ → the factor was defined “Very relevant”
- $\geq 0,34$ and $< 0,67$ → the factor was defined “Relevant”
- > 0 and $< 0,34$ → the factor was defined “Little relevant”
- 0 → the factor was defined “Not relevant”.

Following these criteria, factors were considered 'corroborated' as defined in the Table 5 matrix.

Table 5 – Matrix for the corroboration of the CF-related factors

		Knowledge			
		Well-Known	Known	Little known	Not known
Relevance	Very relevant	C	C	C	NC
	Relevant	C	C	NC	NC
	Little relevant	NC	NC	NC	NC
	Not relevant	NC	NC	NC	NC

Legend: C – Corroborated; NC – Not corroborated

Given that the preliminary version of the Map was drafted including factors already reported in the scientific literature or policy documentation, therefore already considered as “existent” (see above, the so-called “general rule”), the validation exercise was aimed at assessing the actual degree of knowledge and of relevance assigned by the reviewers for each factor, adopting an inclusive criteria, namely excluding only those factors judged as little known or little relevant (with just one exception: when factors were deemed highly relevant despite limited familiarity among the panel¹⁰, it was determined that the specialized knowledge of a few individuals should be considered based on their assessment of strong relevance). To this aim, consistent thresholds were defined assigning the above-mentioned values, and assessing as little known or little relevant those factors known or deemed important in just 1/3 or less valid reviewers’ feedback.

The criterion for arriving at corroboration was to look at the convergence within the panel, which was composed of people from different disciplinary and/or professional and/or geographical backgrounds. Generally, it was determined that a convergence of opinion existed if more than one-third of the respondents expressed views that warranted the inclusion of a factor in the map. This was also on the basis that the list of factors was not the product of theoretical speculation but the result of preceding work concerning the knowledge accumulated within different epistemic communities (disciplinary and/or professional) specialized in the issues covered by the map (i.e., an application of the aforementioned “general rule”). Convergence, for this reason, was defined with a rather inclusive criterion (in such cases, to decide about convergence of opinions, it is more natural to use the majority principle and not the 1/3 threshold, as we found it is useful to do).

As for the **non-CF-related factors**, the procedure was very similar. Initially, it was assessed whether the reviewers were familiar with the factors and measured them in the same manner as the CF-related factors, as indicated by the identical question in the questionnaire. Subsequently, the responses to the relevance question 'In your opinion, could this factor be relevant for the adoption of CFP in general?' were analysed. The answers were scored in the same way, and it was possible to assess the corroboration of these factors using the same matrix used for the factors related to CF. In this way, we were able to decide if including these factors in the Map.

¹⁰ i.e.the cell little known/very relevant-

1.2. Processing the information collected during the workshops

The validation process – as explained above – foresaw five workshops dedicated to discussing with farmers and stakeholders of the local ecosystem the main challenges and opportunities of CF and identifying barriers and enablers to adopting CFPs. The discussions in the workshops were held based on a set of questions that were posed to discussion groups (in each workshop, there could be more than one of these groups) in successive rounds.

The participants discussed and wrote on sticky cards their comments concerning the issues posed in each round. The cards had different colours according to the type of participants. There were four types: 1. farmers, 2. researchers, 3. public officers, and 4. representatives of local associations, NGOs, professionals, and other actors operating in the agricultural sector who could be involved in the promotion of CF and VCMs. After the workshops, the cards posted in each round and concerning each question were grouped according to their similarity; their meaning was summarised by the rapporteur of each workshop (i.e., two or more cards could have the same meaning).

The questions that were at the basis of each workshop and discussion round were almost similar, but there were some differences based on the context in which they were implemented (see above): the workshops were carried out together with “multiplier events” dedicated to presenting MRV4SOC; in the Italian workshops these MRV4SOC related activities – the multiplier event and the workshop – were, in their turn, part of meetings of local networks. In Spain, the workshop was part of a wide national initiative dedicated to CF (See the list of questions for each workshop in Annex 2).

The “complex” context in which the workshops took place, far from being an obstacle to an in-depth discussion of the chosen themes, helped the participants to be more attuned to the overall stake of the discussion being held, which could emerge not only through the questions raised in each table but also through the discussion of wider issues connected to the implementation agricultural policies at the local level.

The results were summarised through Excel sheets in which the various answers to the rounds were listed. In one case, the reporting was done differently, even if not substantially. Apart from the differences in the format through which the results were presented, the reports all consisted of lists of factors and issues related to the broad questions raised during the workshop (for the workshop reported differently, there was indeed a detailed list of factors in a matrix format, complemented by detailed comments). The discussion was not always directed to very specific factors as those listed on the Map, because it was almost impossible to arrive at such a detailed level in open discussions among many people. In general, the emerged issues were more general in character, but they provided, in many cases, a useful idea, and lively indications of how people on the field figure out facilitating and hindering factors, opportunities, and suggestions concerning CF.

The workshop results represented a significant integration of the free comments provided by the reviewers beyond the answers they gave to the closed questions of the questionnaires. This was true for both the “CF-related factors” and “non-CF-related factors”. Also for the latter, the reviewers were asked to provide some general comments, which were very useful¹¹.

1.3. Presentation of the factors and the comments.

In the rest of the main text, each factor is presented by reporting its title and the brief explanation that was contained in the map. The information that led us to the assessment of corroboration was reported too in a small form (about knowledge and relevance, see below). Factors that were not corroborated at the end of the consultation and analysis process were highlighted in red.

¹¹ in general, the questionnaires for “non-CF-related factors” were shorter than those for “CF-related factors”.

One of the descriptors we used concerns the potential effects of factors (after the heading “Factor”). Factors could be, as a general rule, either facilitating or hindering. The majority of them fall into these two categories. However, in some instances, it was noted that there is not a clear distinction, and “It depends” on the context. This is not an indeterminacy that undermines the importance of such a factor. It just means that its possible effect depends on how it is acted upon by relevant actors (farmers, supporting bodies, etc.) and on the general context it appears. This is typical of certain types of costs; for example, introducing CFPs – as often happens with the adoption of new production practices – implies opportunity costs; in this framework, it is important to consider them appropriately in order to make them bring about more revenues than older practices. In some cases, it cannot be said that certain factors are clearly facilitating or hindering CFPs because of the inherently complex characteristics they have (actions and decisions of varied actors are often implied). Policies, for example, are essential elements of agricultural sector dynamics; this is a factor to consider, but it can’t be said in absolute terms in which direction they push (i.e., in favour or against CF). In general, about these factors we can say that it is important to consider them properly, in their right context, to make them favourable to CFPs.

The factors are presented in the following 12 sub-sections, each dedicated to the categories and sub-categories (each subsection is numbered sequentially from B.1. to B.12.; thus, there is correspondence between the numbering and the sequential number of each category). At the beginning of each sub-section, there is a **brief presentation of the category and of the types of factors** that belong to it. Each factor is presented by using the small forms reported in the following tables. The difference between the two forms is that those dedicated to non-CF-related factors are indicated with a green background.

Table 6 – Forms on CF-related factors

#	Name of the CF-Related-factor		
#1	Financial constraints (due also to equipment costs) Carbon Sequestration practices often imply upfront adoption costs, and investments in equipment. This may create financial constraints.	Factor effects	Hindering
		Knowledge	Well known
		Relevance	Very relevant
		Corroborated	Yes

Table 7 – Forms on non-CF-related-factors

#	Name of non-CF-related factors (initially)		
#4	Maintenance costs of new practices could impact adoption Maintaining certain technologies costs more than buying them.	Factor effects	It depends
		Knowledge	Known
		Relevance to CF	Relevant
		Corroborated	Yes

After this rather “formal” presentation, each factor is briefly commented on using what was reported by the reviewers and the results of the workshop.

The review of the Map and the workshop provided a lot of indications beyond the facilitating and hindering factors to CFPs.

B.1. Costs and benefits of Carbon Farming practices

This category is dedicated to factors that have a predominant economic character. It covers factors that have impacts connected to the costs and benefits/rewards of certain practices of CF or of CSA (therefore considering the practice in itself, no matter if connected to VCM or not). Such factors could facilitate the adoption of certain practices or hamper them. Their common characteristic is that they produce changes in the economic balance, either directly or indirectly, of the adopters.

It should be noted that almost all the factors of this category were known by the reviewers, including those that were not initially connected explicitly to CF. Furthermore, most of the comments that emerged on facilitating factors and barriers were general, but, anyhow, some of them were more focused on **specific land uses**. In the following, when relevant, this connection will be stressed. The factors have been distributed among six sub-categories (see above). We will use this partition to provide the more interesting results of the review, and the discussion held during the workshops.

a. Costs connected to the practice/innovation

The **first category** refers to the possible positive or, on the contrary, negative effects on the costs connected to the practice of innovation.

Forms of factors in subcategory 1.a

#	Name of the CF-Related-factor		
#1	Financial constraints (due also to equipment costs) Carbon Sequestration practices often imply upfront adoption costs, and investments in equipment. This may create financial constraints.	Factor effects	Hindering
		Knowledge	Well known
		Relevance	Very relevant
		Corroborated	Yes
#2	Opportunity costs of soil carbon sequestration practices Soil Carbon Sequestration measures can also imply opportunity costs, i.e., their implementation could require farmers to forgo revenue from other sources.	Factor effects	It depends
		Knowledge	Well known
		Relevance	Very relevant
		Corroborated	Yes
#3	Learning costs Carbon farming requires new knowledge and skills that should be acquired at a cost, e.g., training, support, outreach, and practical examples (and potentially up-front payments).	Factor effects	Hindering
		Knowledge	Well known
		Relevance	Very relevant
		Corroborated	Yes
#5	Reduction of operational cost is an important aspect of the new practices Some Carbon Farming practices reduce operational costs, especially because require less input (fuel, fertiliser, etc.).	Factor effects	Facilitating
		Knowledge	Well known
		Relevance	Very relevant
		Corroborated	Yes
#	Name of non-CF-related factors (initially)		
#4	Maintenance costs of new practices could impact adoption Maintaining certain technologies costs more than buying them.	Factor effects	It depends
		Knowledge	Known
		Relevance to CF	Relevant
		Corroborated	Yes
#6	Agro-forestry is labour-intensive Agro-forestry requires an extra effort for tending new trees.	Factor effects	Hindering
		Knowledge	Known

		Relevance to CF	Relevant
		Corroborated	Yes

The factors explicitly connected to CF were well-known by the reviewers and there was a very strong convergence about their relevance and spread is present only for the first one. The factors listed here (#1, #3 and #5) outline the existence of contrasting factors to the practice of CF – pros and cons –, since financial constraints and other costs could be balanced by possible advantages (see Factor #5), and the overall balance among them is not certain. This is reasonable: in general, the introduction of new technologies implies costs but – especially in the case of technologies that are not widely practiced yet – the actual scope and impact of diverse types of cost (see Factor #5) is not known with certainty. It should be stressed that there was not a strong convergence of opinion among the reviewers about the factors initially not explicitly related to CF but, in general, they can be considered relevant also for CF. During the workshops, many concerns were raised about the **higher costs** implied by CFPs, especially if connected to mechanisation (in line with factor #1).

The high cost of investment in new production tools and machinery was, indeed, indicated as relevant in three workshops, especially those focusing on croplands. Anyhow, the issue of cost increase connected to CF was raised also in the workshop in which the issue of mechanisation was not explicitly raised. Emphasis on mechanisation was particularly relevant for croplands (and emerged in Italy and Spain).

One of the barriers highlighted in a workshop (Dorinne) is that practicing CF implies a **strong engagement of the farmers**, and this turns out to impact costs. CFPs imply time for training, advice, for re-design farms' management plans and estimations. This implies also taking risks, not just those connected to the effects of the new practices adopted, but also those connected to the adaptation of those practices to the specific farm's context. This particular barrier could be defined as a specific new one (relative to the original map), that could be termed **hidden (or quasi-hidden) costs**, whose relevance is potentially high. It is, at least implicitly, at the basis of another important category of barriers, the 5th one, related to training and advisory¹². In general, such a barrier depends on the level of complexity of CFPs (see the 4th category).

Some reviewers said that a type of cost – maintenance (see factor #4) – could be relevant, particularly because maintaining Soil Carbon sequestration implies continuous expenses (one reviewer stressed those connected to monitoring through specific technologies – see costs of MRV, below) that could be underestimated. The issue of costs of new technologies adoption is, of course, very idiosyncratic and is connected to the particular land use (see factor #6) through which CF is practiced. It was stressed by one reviewer that agro-forestry requests extra work and specific skills, while another said that there are diverse opinions.

b. Policy on subsidies and financial incentives

A **second sub-category** is dedicated to some relevant aspects of policies¹³ for fostering CFPs, i.e., those concerning both financial incentives and subsidies that impact deeply on rewards for the adoption of innovation. Both factors were recognised by the reviewers and considered as very relevant factors impacting on CF. Some reviewers said that financial incentives are very relevant for undertaking the investments needed for initiating CFP. One reviewer suggested that incentives may not be as relevant for poorer farmers, while another suggested that small farmers combine their efforts to access them in order to maximize their positive effects.

¹² Training and advice are necessary for overcoming this kind of barriers.

¹³ This includes both public direct interventions and the definition of policy and legal frameworks that promote and are primarily based on the action of private actors (typically; private financing schemes).

Forms of factors in subcategory 1.b

#	Name of the CF-Related-factor		
#7	Government subsidies Government subsidies (in the form of credit or loans or direct payment) favour the adoption.	Factor effects	Facilitating
		Knowledge	Well known
		Relevance	Very relevant
		Corroborated	Yes
#8	Financial incentives Financial incentives favour the adoption; poorer farmers tend to be more sensitive.	Factor effects	Facilitating
		Knowledge	Well known
		Relevance	Very relevant
		Corroborated	Yes

From the workshops too, emerged the issue of financial incentives (and subsidies; see factors #7 and #8): CFPs could be promoted thanks to policy interventions whose rationale is, somehow, proposing a buffer for adverse effects of new practices and, in general, promising participation to the risks being taken up by farmers in the future. The reason for doing so – supporting farmers – is the potential of CF to provide valuable ecosystem services and externalities (it emerged clearly in Milan). An issue that emerged in various workshops (e.g., in Dorinne and Milan) is connected to the different storage capacities/potential of different soils. The issue will be dealt with when discussing other categories (i.e., when dealing with Policies and regulations).

Policy interventions of this type must **cope with the complexity of the process** of promoting CF, i.e., changing how the entire socio-economic system of agriculture works. For example, in the Madrid workshop, it was stressed that planning incentives was more important to facilitate the costly transition to CF than for other phases of the process of adoption of CFPs. Of course, the issue of simplification of procedures for obtaining subsidies was also raised in other workshops (e.g., in Amalie-Prague). In this framework, how various **actors interact** is a very relevant issue. In Milan was stressed that the possible incentives to CF should go together with training for farmers and other relevant actors (to respond to the technological challenges implied by CF). Furthermore, policies should not limit themselves to providing benefits to individual farmers, but also promote – among both farmers and other stakeholders – generalised favourable expectations concerning the positive outcomes of CFPs (this is the issue of promoting branding, products identity based on quality and other sector level policies; see category 6).

c. Effects on profitability and yields

The third sub-category concerns the effects of new practices on yields and profitability.

Forms of factors in subcategory 1.c

#	Name of the CF-Related-factor		
#9	Profitability of new practices Increased profits brought about by new practices favour adoption. New practices must be perceived as bringing positive effects on profits for being adopted.	Factor effects	Facilitating
		Knowledge	Well known
		Relevance	Very relevant
		Corroborated	Yes
#10	Certain carbon sequestration practices diminish yields Certain carbon sequestration practices ¹⁴ diminish yields in the short run. Possible positive effects occur over longer time.	Factor effects	Hindering
		Knowledge	Well known
		Relevance	Very relevant

¹⁴ See the detailed form in Annex 1.

#	Name of the CF-Related-factor		
		Corroborated	Yes
#11	Some practices increase yields in the long term Practices of C sequestration such as crop rotation, cover cropping and other bring about reduction of fertiliser, pesticide and herbicide needs, and possible crop yield and soil quality improvements in the long term, added to the low investment and operational costs to implement the practice, may encourage farmers to establish crop rotation.	Factor effects	Facilitating
		Knowledge	Well known
		Relevance	Very relevant
		Corroborated	Yes

Profitability of new practices (#9) was well known by the reviewers and was considered as a very relevant facilitating factor. During the workshops (particularly in Milan, Madrid, and Amalie), once the focus on costs was raised, the issue of the **reduction of profitability** of carbon farming activities emerged too. The issue was also posed in terms of lower expected returns, uncertainty of results of CF (for example in Amalie; also referred to in factor #10), and reduced competitiveness of production (in Amalie workshop). It is worth mentioning that for one reviewer CF is being practiced not just based on considerations about profitability but also on the time horizon of the expected effects of CFP (in the short vs long term).

The issue of **time horizon** is important: Factors #10 and #11 concern the impact of CF on yields. They would seem in contradiction to one another, if not that factor #11 states that gains in profitability could emerge in the longer run. The issue is controversial in itself. Among the reviewers these factors were well known and considered very relevant in bringing about CFP adoption. In general, the impact on yields is important but emerges from reviewers' comments that it depends a lot on the individual CFPs and, therefore, on different land uses and the related specific conditions and situations: agroforestry, zero/reduced-tillage systems, reduction of fertilisers, use of organic fertilisers, crop residues, and other practices have in the short term immediate negative results on productivity. It was stressed that CFPs have to be adapted to local conditions and time is needed for learning and mastering the new practices. During the workshops, the practice of CF was not seen just as a path with barriers (that hamper profitability). In line with the analysis of the literature and the comments of the reviewers, there was a wide recognition that CF could promote **productivity and also profitability** for farms (in line with factor #11).

d. Farming systems interactions

The fourth subcategory is focused on farming systems, since individual practices are never adopted in a vacuum but in the context of a wider set of production activities, therefore it is important to consider how a certain practice could interact with others. Most of the reviewers knew these factors and there was a general agreement that they are very relevant for the adoption of CFPs. Furthermore, the factors that were not singled out in the literature as connected to CF (#16 and #17), according to most of the reviewers, are indeed actually relevant to it.

Forms of factors in subcategory 1.d

#	Name of the CF-Related-factor		
#12	Combination of multiple practices Combining multiple practices may improve ecosystem services.	Factor effects	Facilitating
		Knowledge	Well known
		Relevance	Very relevant
		Corroborated	Yes
#13	Co-benefits of Carbon farming affect the adoption Co-benefits of Carbon farming affect adoption because it has positive impacts on soil quality and indirectly on yields.	Factor effects	Facilitating
		Knowledge	Well known
		Relevance	Very relevant

#	Name of the CF-Related-factor		
		Corroborated	Yes
#14	Uncertainty about the results of introducing Soil Carbon Management Practices Farmers, particularly those who are risk adverse, are looking for more assurances about the income potential of these Soil Carbon Management and other conservation practices.	Factor effects	Hindering
		Knowledge	Well known
		Relevance	Very relevant
		Corroborated	Yes
#15	Improving fertilisation efficiency indirectly reduces emissions of CO2 Improving fertilisation efficiency may induce savings in other input costs but implies also some investment costs.	Factor effects	It depends
		Knowledge	Well known
		Relevance	Very relevant
		Corroborated	Yes
#	Name of non-CF-related factors (initially)		
#16	Farmers face competing pressures Farmers are business managers and as such must deal holistically with a range of financial and time requirements.	Factor effects	Hindering
		Knowledge	Well known
		Relevance to CF	Very relevant
		Corroborated	Yes
#17	Unequal distribution of costs/benefits across supply chains The unequal distribution of costs and benefits across actors in agri-food supply chains reduces the motivation of farmers to adopt CSA technologies.	Factor effects	Hindering
		Knowledge	Known
		Relevance to CF	Very relevant
		Corroborated	Yes

During the workshops, some of these factors were confirmed as **facilitating** CFPs adoption especially because they bring about, or contribute to, the production of various **co-benefits for individual farms**, such as soil health and fertility, reduction of soil erosion, increase of water retention and, through diversification, an increased resilience of farming activities (all this in line with factor #13). In the workshop focused on grassland (Dorinne) was emphasised that the practice of CF on grassland and agroforestry fosters animal health and landscape continuity and can optimise production systems.

In general, it emerged as an enabler of CFPs benefits, hence of CFPs adoption (in line with #12 and #13), the practice of farm management based on the promotion of **synergies with the various production activities and cultural practices**. In this framework, it should be stressed that from the workshops emerged that the beneficial net effects of CF depend on varied practices within the farms and that there is a significant level of uncertainty on the final results and worry about their financial sustainability (see factor #14). The latter is a factor of particular concern since, as some reviewers observed (see factor #16), producers face different sources of instability and, in general, try to keep technological changes in line with the existing practices to maintain overall profitability. Comments provided by the reviewers on Factor #14 are interesting: the introduction of each CFP as such could diminish certain input but the entire set of input used within a farm as a whole could change and a positive effect on the overall balance is not sure. It is suggested that specific studies in different situations could help.

Synergies among various components of diverse farming systems in order to make possible the practice of CF are important (see above) and very idiosyncratic. **It depends on the type of land use**, as well as on very diverse pedoclimatic characteristics, the prevalent farming systems, etc. In the workshop on grassland, optimisation of production systems was explicitly mentioned but emerged also in other contexts.

From the review and the workshops emerged clearly that both costs and benefits of specific CFPs have to be understood in a wider context, be it a specific farming system or the wider supply chain, as long as the farmers feel that there is an **unequal distribution of costs along the value chain** (#17, therefore, could be considered as confirmed even if in the consulted literature it was not connected to CF). Market and sector dynamics are, anyhow, the object of the next category.

e. Market and sector dynamics (demand and supply sides)

The fifth sub-category concerns those interactions of farms with market and market forces that may favour or hamper the adoption of practices that – in the context of the individual production unit – could be profitable. These two factors have been singled out in the literature without a specific connection to CF but, interestingly, some of the reviewers considered them as relevant also for the adoption of CFPs.

Forms of factors in subcategory 1.e

#	Name of non-CF-related factors (initially)		
#18	Consumers' willingness to pay for sustainable products is not certain Consumers' willingness to pay for sustainable products sometimes is assumed as relevant by farmers, but sometimes it turns out that it is not the case.	Factor effects	It depends
		Knowledge	Well known
		Relevance to CF	Very relevant
		Corroborated	Yes
#19	The organisation of industrial sectors and value chain affects adoption of climate-friendly measures The existing contracts within the value chains may induce farmers to not practice climate friendly measures (e.g., the related costs cannot be sustained).	Factor effects	It depends
		Knowledge	Little known
		Relevance to CF	Very relevant
		Corroborated	Yes

In general, what happens in the context in which farms operate emerged from the review and the workshops as relevant for the adoption of CFPs. Adoption depends also on contractual arrangements among actors in the **value chains** that should be considered (#19). It was a common opinion among the reviewers that this is a very relevant issue and a potential barrier to the adoption of CF: costs and risks connected to the possible **production of ecosystem services** are not, and in any case are not perceived, as equally distributed along the value chain (see also #17, above). Consumer willingness to pay (#18) is an aspect of this distribution (this issue is the object of other categories).

f. Access to resources (human and social capital)

The last sub-category concerns the connection between the adoption of new farming practices and resources, including human and social capital. Factor #20 was well-known by most of the reviewers but not many considered it relevant.

Forms of factors in subcategory 1.f

#	Name of the CF-Related-factor		
#20	Farmers' wealth/firm size and property impact adoption Literacy level, wealth, and firm income favour the uptake of practices. In general, these aspects increase availability to those resources that favour the uptake of new technologies.	Factor effects	Facilitating
		Knowledge	Well known
		Relevance	Relevant
		Corroborated	Yes

#	Name of non-CF-related factors (initially)		
#21	<p style="text-align: center;">Access to labour</p> <p>The possibility to access labour improve possibility to practice. Family size is relevant for this reason.</p>	Factor effects	Facilitating
		Knowledge	Known
		Relevance to CF	Little relevant
		Corroborated	No

Factor #21 was known but considered as little relevant, therefore it is to be considered as not corroborated. The wider issue of farms' dimension, anyhow, cannot be considered irrelevant, as indicated in factor #20 and by some comments during the workshops (see below #80) as well as by some reviewers (see below, for example factor #77 and #113). They indicated that some CFPs are more likely to be adopted by those farms whose dimensions let them afford to take bigger economic risks. An issue that emerged clearly from many workshops is related to the need for training of people who should implement CFPs. This means that, in general, it has been recognised that the lack of labour, at least of workers with appropriate skills, is a problem that hampers CFPs adoption. The issue is dealt with under another category.

B.2. VCM and innovative practices

Participating in the Voluntary Carbon Market (VCM) depends on how it works and the specific set of administrative practices it implies. Furthermore, attributing rewards for soil carbon sequestration in agriculture through VCM implies a series of impacts that could promote carbon farming itself.

Following the review and workshops, the factors initially identified in the literature under this category are now better understood, particularly in terms of their actual significance. Indeed, they were recognised in general as existent by the reviewers, but some of them were better known and considered particularly relevant than others.

During the literature analysis, three subcategories of factors were identified, and the results of the review and workshops will be presented using the same classification.

a. Farming system interaction with VCM

The first sub-category of factors entails those stemming from the interaction of VCM-related practices with farming systems (such interaction impacts the decision to enter this type of market and to adopt the related carbon farming practices).

Forms of factors in subcategory 2.a

#	Name of the CF-Related-factor		
#22	Market leakage – Unintended effect Combining multiple practices may improve ecosystem services.	Factor effects	Hindering
		Knowledge	Known
		Relevance	Little relevant
		Corroborated	No
#23	Price structure impacts decision Changes in certain prices induced by policy choices can have effects on adoption. In general, carbon gains and profits depend on the overall market conditions.	Factor effects	It depends
		Knowledge	Known
		Relevance	Very relevant
		Corroborated	Yes
#24	Possible competition between farmers in higher and lower income countries The advantages of selling carbon credits could be greater for farmers in lower income countries, (if the carbon price is the same in all the countries).	Factor effects	Hindering
		Knowledge	Known
		Relevance	Relevant
		Corroborated	Yes

#	Name of non-CF-related factors (initially)		
#25	Averse attitude towards data publishing The need to publish data needed for the practice of carbon schemes can create adversity among farmers.	Factor effects	Hindering
		Knowledge	Well known
		Relevance to CF	Relevant
		Corroborated	Yes
#26	Off-farm income Off-farm income may also influence the adoption of SAP (Sustainable Agricultural Practices). An additional income, external to farmland, may provide additional resources for adoption or decrease the priority of agricultural work.	Factor effects	Facilitating
		Knowledge	Well known
		Relevance to CF	Very relevant
		Corroborated	Yes

#	Name of non-CF-related factors (initially)		
#27	Unintended effect of incentives (crowd out effect) Studies demonstrate that specific incentives could crowd out investment-related investments. It depends on the context.	Factor effects	It depends
		Knowledge	Little known
		Relevance to CF	Very relevant
		Corroborated	Yes

The possible **unintended effects** called **market leakages** (#22) connected to possible participation in VCMs were known by the reviewers but were considered little relevant. It was not corroborated, and it seems that the actual importance of this specific factor should be ascertained once CFPs becomes widespread.

The issue of **possible unintended effects of CFPs and VCMs** is not limited to possible “market leakages” and remains open: CFPs, especially if fostered through efficient VCMs, could impact how agricultural systems work, incentivising practices that could conflict with the attainment of other objectives of societal and environmental importance. For example, in Dorinne it was suggested that there could be an agronomic risk connected to implementing carbon storage practices that may not be suitable and to prioritising carbon over fertility and other environmental benefits (e.g., biodiversity) or sustainability considerations. Crowding out because incentive, the #27, was indicated in the literature as another possible unintended effect of incentives, even if it was not explicitly connected to CF (or VCM). Anyhow, some of the reviewers considered it relevant for the adoption of CF and, in general, some commented that incentives are always set to change farmers’ behaviour. Therefore, it is possible that – if not adequately fine-tuned – incentives could crowd out investments in an unintended way.

Factor #23, “**Price structure** impacts decision”, has been recognised by more than half of the reviewers and most of them considered it as very relevant for bringing about CF adoption. The possibility that the presence in VCM could impact price structures emerged anyhow during the workshops. In Dorinne was hypothesised that carbon prices could impact land tenure systems, the price of land, and rural leases, distorting somehow the incentives to CFPs and participating in VCMs. This phenomenon is connected to that discussed above (see sub-category 1.b on Policy on subsidies and financial incentives) connected to carbon storage potential. The issue is connected to that of prices of carbon credits, that – as suggested in Milan – should be set to guarantee a fair gain for farmers.

As for factor #24, “Possible **competition between farmers** in higher and lower income countries” it was known by most of the reviewers, even if not most of them considered it just relevant. The point to underline here is that, as it was for factor #23, the structure of price – and, particularly, how carbon price – is set, emerges as relevant.

One of the factors singled out in the literature concerns **farmers’ aversion to publish the data** needed for participating in VCM (#25). It was well-known by the reviewers and some among them considered it also relevant for explaining CFP adoption. Comments from the reviewers were interesting: such aversion is in line with the aversion to bureaucratic workload connected to CF, VCM and certification in general. Furthermore, farmers, as small entrepreneurs in general, tend to avoid disclosure about their production practices. There is a possibility that this factor could affect VCM participation.

Another facilitating factor (#26), not initially connected to CFP, is the possibility of adding new income sources to the farm. In general, since the practice of VCM – according to some comments of the reviewers – could turn out to be another of such sources, it can be said that this factor could be considered validated.

b. VCM uncertainty

The second type of factors connected to the functioning of VCM has been identified in the uncertainty connected to carbon market operations.

Forms of factors in subcategory 2.b

#	Name of the CF-Related-factor		
#28	<p style="text-align: center;">Risk of Double funding</p> <p>Double funding occurs when farmers are paid twice from different policies/schemes for the same action. It undermines market functioning and the objective of decarbonisation. This should be avoided by regulators but is difficult to achieve and requires complex controls.</p>	Factor effects	Hindering
		Knowledge	Well known
		Relevance	Relevant
		Corroborated	Yes
#29	<p style="text-align: center;">Potential lack of demand for Carbon credits</p> <p>It is not clear if the demand for credit will be sufficient to make the carbon credit market an opportunity for farmers.</p>	Factor effects	Hindering
		Knowledge	Known
		Relevance	Relevant
		Corroborated	Yes
#30	<p style="text-align: center;">Cyclicity of demand for agricultural credits disincentives CF practices</p> <p>Cyclicity of demand and multiyear process of production of agricultural credits disincentives continuous CF practices. Investments tend to be higher in the first period after the launching of policies and then diminishes. Overall, this phenomenon could jeopardise the correct functioning of carbon credit market.</p>	Factor effects	Hindering
		Knowledge	Known
		Relevance	Relevant
		Corroborated	Yes
#31	<p style="text-align: center;">Uncertainty about the price of carbon hinders the adoption of carbon farming practices (operational aspect)</p> <p>The price of carbon credits is not stable. This uncertainty represents a barrier: the prospect of financial gains is not seen as a benefit able to offset to costs of adopting the new farming practices required to trade the credits.</p>	Factor effects	Hindering
		Knowledge	Known
		Relevance	Very relevant
		Corroborated	Yes
#32	<p style="text-align: center;">Credibility of credit markets/Quality of carbon credits/Accountability of reporting</p> <p>The low level of credibility of credit markets (connected to issues such as permanence and non-additionality) is a barrier to participate in trading; Changing farm management to increase SOC-sequestration will only be eligible for offset payments if activities represent permanent abatement.</p>	Factor effects	Hindering
		Knowledge	Known
		Relevance	Very relevant
		Corroborated	Yes
#33	<p style="text-align: center;">Competition between providers of carbon credits not in agriculture</p> <p>Uncertainty in the conversion of agricultural practices into carbon credits, suppliers of agricultural carbon credits will face competition from other suppliers of carbon credits.</p>	Factor effects	Hindering
		Knowledge	Known
		Relevance	Relevant
		Corroborated	Yes
#34	<p style="text-align: center;">Carbon storage reversal/ Credit reversal are a liability</p> <p>This is a problem for carbon credit schemes, as participants may have incentives to reverse carbon storage or lack incentives to reduce this risk, which would undermine the integrity of these schemes and undo the carbon gains. No insurance is present for carbon credit reversal.</p>	Factor effects	Hindering
		Knowledge	Well known
		Relevance	Very relevant
		Corroborated	Yes

All the factors under this sub-category were hindering. Some of them were recognised by the reviewers as existent, i.e., factors such as **low credibility of credit markets** (#32) also because of the risk of carbon storage reversal (#34). The issue of **reversibility** of carbon storage as a source of lack of credibility of VCMs was indicated clearly in the workshop of Dorinne. A specific factor of low credibility of VCM is the “risk of double funding” (#28). The reviewers recognised it but did not consider it as “very relevant” but simply “relevant” (the comments stated that this problem can be addressed as in the case of other payments connected to CAP). The problem was, anyhow, raised during the workshops (i.e., in Dorinne). Factor #30 “Cyclicality of demand for agricultural credits” was known by the reviewers, and half of them considered it relevant for participation in VCM.

As for factor #33, “Competition between providers of carbon credits”, almost half of them knew it and it was considered relevant by most of them. Factor #31, “Uncertainty about the price of carbon”, is known by more than the half of the reviewers and most of them considered it very relevant. The comments left by some reviewers are interesting: one said that in some countries VCM schemes foresee a given price for the farmers, that are covered against price fluctuations. In Madrid, the issue of the lack of guarantees to compensate for potential losses was raised and the opportunity for making insurance companies participate in the market was formulated. Another reviewer said that, of course, carbon prices in the VCM are important but CF is practiced also for other possible co-benefits. Anyhow, the issue of the uncertainty of the Carbon credit markets, because of business volatility and because of its procedures and economic valuation, has been raised during the workshops (in Dorinne, Milan, Casale Monferrato and Madrid).

The main aspects of the uncertainty of VCM were confirmed also during the workshops. The functioning of VCM is questioned based on doubts about how the measurement of stored carbon is done. The issue of uncertainty about the quantification of soil carbon sequestration (similar to factor #32) emerged clearly in Dorinne and in Madrid. In Madrid, Dorinne, and Milan, in particular, the issue of the need for data for estimating correctly carbon storage was raised (e.g., the need of regional reference for estimating the baseline in local cropping systems). This issue is, anyhow, relevant regardless of whether the measurement is aimed at making VCM work or, more generally, at rewarding the practice of Carbon Farming (therefore, it is a crucial aspect of MRV).

The risk of double accounting of carbon storage (#28) was also raised in Dorinne, diminishing accountability of reporting that is the base of Carbon Markets. This situation, as it was also stressed in Dorinne, could take shape a form of conflict of interest between credit sellers and buyers (#32). In Dorinne was also raised the issue of the real value of a carbon credit (What is the precision of measurement? Does it represent a given quantity of carbon stored?). Similar issues have been raised in Milan, where was stressed the importance of transparency was stressed as well as simplicity of evaluation, calculation and certification methods.

All the issues emerged in the literature and during the validation process helped explain the problem of **lack of trust in VCM** (emerged in various workshops). In Madrid it was stressed that there is a lack of understanding of what the carbon market is and how it works. This has the effect that farmers do not have a big trust in obtaining fair benefits. In Madrid was also stressed that farmers are concerned about the consequences of possible carbon leakages induced by the pedoclimatic conditions of certain cropping systems. This is an issue of measurement that is fundamental for the correct functioning of the VCM. Among the issues raised concerning the functioning of the VCM, there is the lack of transparency regarding the rules for sales (Dorinne and Amalie), and that of regulations for certification, since uniform rules should be followed so that farmers can trust VCMs (Amalie).

c. VCM implementation costs

The third sub-category concerns factors connected to the costs to comply with the rules for participation in VCM.

Forms of factors in subcategory 2.c

#	Name of the CF-Related-factor		
#35	High costs for results-based schemes/MRV-Increased transaction Costs Participation in VCM implies higher costs, particularly the result-based schemes. Indeed, there are transaction costs of verification for carbon farming; High certification costs; need to define the pace of calculation. The application of the procedure implies also hidden costs.	Factor effects	Hindering
		Knowledge	Well known
		Relevance	Very relevant
		Corroborated	Yes
#36	Lack of transparency in the price discovery mechanism Some participants of marketplaces for credits see credit price information as sensitive, and do not want to make this public. This could be a problem for schemes, as generally, clear information on prices supports efficient operation of markets.	Factor effects	Hindering
		Knowledge	Known
		Relevance	Very relevant
		Corroborated	Yes

Factor #35 has to do with “High costs for results-based schemes”. It was well-know and considered relevant for explaining the participation in VCM (and, likely, the very practice of CF). The issue has been raised strongly in all the workshops and clearly emerges as one of the main problems for practicing VCM according to the voices from the field (i.e., the people who participated in the workshops). Sometimes it is labelled as a bureaucratic cost that should be lowered through transparency, simplification of calculation and certification methods and reduction of administrative burdens (Milan, Casale and Madrid). In Dorinne it was highlighted the risk of increasing administrative burden, workload, and organisational constraints could be addressed if the administrative costs are distributed on large, cultivated areas (i.e., large farms). In Madrid too it was suggested to promote the aggregation of exploitations in order to reduce the connected risks. In Dorinne, it was also stressed that these costs (not just for participating in VCM) are connected to the time needed, the accuracy of the estimation, the need for training and advice. There are many things that participants in these markets have to know about VCM functioning to foster their participation, as emerged in Madrid.

In general, as emerged from the literature and the workshops, participation in VCMs implies costs. In this context, it was highlighted (Madrid) the need to devise new business models that entail the participation of farms in VCM based on simple and agile soil carbon capture calculation methodologies for certification (the problem being to overcome the high cost of MRV). In Madrid was also suggested that VCMs should cover a fair share of benefits for the farmers, also including the environmental co-benefits produced by CFPs (this emerged also in Milan).

Just half of the reviewers knew factor #36 about the “Lack of transparency in the price discovery mechanism”. It is connected to a certain reluctance of participants in VCMs to disclose information about themselves. Such an issue emerged also previously (see above, factor #27).

B.3. Orientation towards the environment and drive for change

Another category of factors impacting the adoption of CFPs and, in case, the decision to enter VCMs, regards the orientation to change of those who should implement innovative practices. These factors are less economic in nature and concern personal beliefs, social pressure and other motivations for undertaking, or not, a particular technological or farming practice.

The subsequent chapter will present these findings using the five subcategories of factors employed in the literature analysis. A distinction was made between pressures on individuals stemming from social interactions, in the first subcategory, and those originating from individual attitudes and beliefs, albeit socially mediated, in the others. It should be stressed that, from the workshops, not many comments relevant to these factors have been formulated, compared to the preceding categories a. and b.

a. Social pressure (from peers, local communities, etc.)

The first sub-category has to do with those pressures on individuals, and their possible decisions, coming from social interactions (from peers, colleagues, local communities).

Forms of factors in subcategory 3.a

#	Name of the CF-Related-factor		
#37	Demonstration: Farmers evaluation of neighbour agricultural practices impacts on adoption Farmers make their opinions based on what they see in neighbouring properties. Demonstration occurs by observing what happens in neighbouring properties.	Factor effects	It depends
		Knowledge	Well known
		Relevance	Very relevant
		Corroborated	Yes
#38	Acceptance and support from neighbours/pressure from significant others Social capital is important for the adoption of new agricultural practices (there could be a role for social media in this).	Factor effects	It depends
		Knowledge	Well known
		Relevance	Relevant
		Corroborated	Yes

#	Name of non-CF-related factors (initially)		
#39	Knowledge brokers are crucial for promoting innovation The opinion of key stakeholders, advisors and other gatekeepers are crucial for the adoption of innovation.	Factor effects	Facilitating
		Knowledge	Well known
		Relevance to CF	Relevant
		Corroborated	Yes
#40	Importance of knowledge networks Social networks sometimes have specific knowledge on soils (it's a form of social capital). Users' network are effective tools for promoting innovation.	Factor effects	Facilitating
		Knowledge	Known
		Relevance to CF	Very relevant
		Corroborated	Yes

The four factors above are corroborated by the reviewers. They were known by most of the respondents with the only exception of factor #40 "Importance of knowledge networks" which was anyhow recognised by almost half of them. The reviewers considered them as relevant for CF and its adoption. These results are important since they confirm **the relevance, according to the reviewers, of social interactions among adopters in CF adoption process**. The reviewers stressed (see factor #39) the

importance of the circulation of knowledge through brokers – be they consultants or peers. Some reviewers, in line with this kind of thinking, stated that knowledge networks are also relevant (i.e., social networks that share knowledge on soil, such as users' networks – factor #40).

As anticipated, during the workshop there were not many explicit comments on this matter. Nevertheless, it can be said that there was an implicit recognition of the importance of these factors. In Madrid, for example, it was suggested to act upon the perception of VCM of the potential participants, to build business cases including the possible combination of incentives; it was also suggested to involve farmers' and cooperative associations in MRV activities. In both cases, the **importance of social pressure and the role of mobilisation of collective actors and/or networks** is recognised. In Milan, social appreciation was indicated as one possible factor facilitating CFP adoption. In Dorinne, in Milan and Casale, participants indicated the objective of improving the image of agriculture and livestock in society as a motive for practicing CF.

The recognition of the importance of social networks for promoting the increase of relevant knowledge for the CFPs was stressed also in the ice-break session in the workshop in Casale. It could be said that factors under this sub-category – horizontal interactions, particularly facilitated by social networks – are at the basis of the importance of factors considered in other categories (see category 5).

b. Pro-environment sentiment

This sub-category includes factors that – although socially mediated – are rooted in individual attitudes and beliefs, such as a pro-environmental orientation.

Forms of factors in subcategory 3.b

#	Name of the CF-Related-factor		
#41	Farmers' beliefs on climate change/environmental stewardship Attention to the environment, feeling responsible for it, is a relevant factor. If farmers feel they are doing enough, they are reluctant to further engaging. Beliefs on climate change influence positively the adoption of SAP (anyhow, the issue is sometimes contested since this is not sufficient).	Factor effects	Facilitating
		Knowledge	Well known
		Relevance	Very relevant
		Corroborated	Yes
#	Name of non-CF-related factors (initially)		
#42	Political views about the role of the state The states with a population more opposed to public environmental spending are more likely to have higher EQIP (Environmental Quality Incentive Program) application rates.	Factor effects	It depends
		Knowledge	Little known
		Relevance to CF	Very relevant
		Corroborated	Yes
#43	Increase in land aesthetic value Some farmers engage in agricultural practices that increase the aesthetic value of land (e.g., by maintaining certain landscapes).	Factor effects	Facilitating
		Knowledge	Known
		Relevance to CF	Relevant
		Corroborated	Yes

Factor #41, "Farmers' beliefs on climate change/environmental stewardship", is generally known by the reviewers, and the majority of them consider it relevant for the adoption of CF. Some of them commented interestingly on it. In one case, it was said that environmental orientation is one of the factors that motivate the adoption of CFPs. In another case, it was reported that farmers' sensitivity to environmental issues is not different compared to other sectors of the population; responsiveness

depends on the time frame of farmers, who decide based on a varied set of variables. In one workshop (Milan) it was suggested that the lack of orientation toward the environment could impact on adoption.

Regarding the other two factors identified in the literature as not directly related to CF but potentially relevant, factor #42 (which seems counterintuitive) is almost unknown. The impact of political views on the role of the state in CF promotion is difficult to assess, as there were no significant comments from the reviewers. The other factor, #43, is known by half of the respondents and only half of them consider it relevant to CF; furthermore, the comments provided by the reviewers were divergent and generic.

c. Information/knowledge

The third sub-category gathers factors connected to the availability of information/ knowledge about possible changes toward CFPs and their potential impacts.

Forms of factors in subcategory 3.c

#	Name of the CF-Related-factor		
#44	Lack of skill and knowledge among farmers Farmers felt that they lacked the necessary skills and knowledge to implement the practices and integrate them into their existing management systems and regulatory requirements. It could include several practices, for example peatland restoration.	Factor effects	Hindering
		Knowledge	Well known
		Relevance	Very relevant
		Corroborated	Yes
#45	Awareness of observable phenomena of climate change/Environmental consciousness Farmers who are aware of the connection between certain practices and the environment are more likely to adopt those practices.	Factor effects	Facilitating
		Knowledge	Well known
		Relevance	Relevant
		Corroborated	Yes
#46	Awareness and understanding of Carbon Farming related policy framework do not increase related practices Attitude to Carbon Farming is not only a matter of knowledge of the relevant practices. It depends on other assessments, connected to policies. Studies found that knowing that there is a policy for Carbon sequestration does not facilitate adoption.	Factor effects	Hindering
		Knowledge	Little known
		Relevance	Very relevant
		Corroborated	Yes
#47	Information about the benefits of Conservation practices impacts positively adoption Information is crucial for adopting Conservation practices (including Soil Carbon Sequestration). Nevertheless, relevant information is context specific (not all measures work in the same way in all the places).	Factor effects	It depends
		Knowledge	Well known
		Relevance to CF	Very relevant
		Corroborated	Yes

Factor #44 “Lack of skill and knowledge among farmers” was acknowledged by most of the reviewers as relevant. One reviewer stressed that knowledge is crucial, especially in the transition period toward the full adoption of certain practices. Another commented that knowledge and skills are not equally distributed among those who manage farms. These ideas were shared by the participants in the workshops. In Madrid it was stressed that there is a general lack of knowledge on CFPs as well as on how they must be implemented at the local level. Similarly, in Dorinne, and Casale, it was said that there is misinformation and the circulation of incorrect ideas, as well as a need to access knowledge.

Factor #45 was also known by the reviewers who considered it, in most of the cases, relevant to the adoption of CFPs. There were no particular comments on it, if not that it is considered by one reviewer as similar to #41 (see above, sub-category 1.b ¹⁵).

There are differences, anyhow, that should be stressed. Factor #47, “Information about the benefits of Conservation practices impacts positively adoption” was one of those singled out in the literature but without an explicit connection to CF. Its particularity is that it points out that, for fostering the adoption of certain practices, **context-specific information is needed**. Factor #41 was also focused on the fact that adopters could think of already doing the right thing to practice their attention to the environment. Therefore, there is an interaction to consider: farmers could consider themselves as already doing good and be reluctant to do more and continue to innovate.

This is an issue that needs to be paid attention to. One reviewer’s comment on factor #47 is interesting: content and communication mechanisms are crucial, and doing well in this field cannot be taken for granted. In this framework the comments provided in Milan and Madrid respectively are relevant: training is important and should be provided also in schools to make clear the overall process of CF and its importance; public campaigns would be useful to inform about the societal relevance of the agricultural products generated under certified VCM schemes. Such campaigns could help change the perception of farmers – it was stressed in the Madrid workshop – that their entry into VCM would increase the bureaucratic burden and, in general, help them to correctly assess the adequacy of their effort and engagement. In Casale the importance of product valorisation, and public sensibilisation was mentioned.

d. Orientation/ability to change

The fourth sub-category refers to the factors related to a general orientation to change of the relevant actors (mainly farmers), or the lack of, that impacts the possible adoption of CFPs and/or the entrance in the VCM. Such an orientation,

Forms of factors in subcategory 3.d

#	Name of the CF-Related-factor		
#48	Attitudes towards Carbon Farming change according to the type of farm Farmers can be divided in different groups that differ considerably in terms of their level of concern about climate change, environmental values, time orientation, place attachment, and efficacy beliefs associated with LEAP (low emission agricultural practices), indicating that different engagement strategies are needed for each group	Factor effects	It depends
		Knowledge	Known
		Relevance	Relevant
		Corroborated	Yes
#49	Relative advantage of sustainable practices in agriculture It means the degree to which an innovation is perceived as being better than the idea it supersedes” (e.g., economic profitability or social prestige). Favourable attitudes toward relative advantage might influence positively the adoption of sustainable practices in agriculture	Factor effects	Facilitating
		Knowledge	Known
		Relevance	Very Relevant
		Corroborated	Yes

¹⁵ Some similarities could be noticed also in relation to factor #47. The three factors, anyhow, are focused on different aspects: #41 on beliefs, #45 on awareness while #47 on information. We decided to keep them as different and avoid a form of conflation.

#	Name of non-CF-related factors (initially)		
#50	Farmers' resentment about land cost and conservation policy Resentment concerning policies on conservation is a predictor of engagement of farmers in conservation policies	Factor effects	Hindering
		Knowledge	Known
		Relevance to CF	Relevant
		Corroborated	Yes
#51	Prejudice about certain practices may hamper adoption Prejudice against certain practices is a relevant factor that explains adoption. It was observed in relation to biological fixation with clover	Factor effects	Hindering
		Knowledge	Known
		Relevance to CF	Relevant
		Corroborated	Yes
#52	Exposure to climate change impacts increases willingness to innovate for conservation Farmers who are exposed to climate change impacts tend to be more willing to undertake conservation practices	Factor effects	Facilitating
		Knowledge	Well-Known
		Relevance to CF	Relevant
		Corroborated	Yes
#53	Self-efficacy facilitates the adoption of LEAP (Low Emission Agricultural Practices) An individual's perceived ability to engage in a specific behaviour	Factor effects	Facilitating
		Knowledge	Little Known
		Relevance to CF	Very Relevant
		Corroborated	Yes
#54	Positive attitude towards specific practices Adoption is also based on the familiarity with certain practices and habits.	Factor effects	Facilitating
		Knowledge	Known
		Relevance to CF	Relevant
		Corroborated	Yes
#55	Temporal spillover Attitude to innovation tends to persist. Certain practices tend to favour the adoption of other practices later on.	Factor effects	Facilitating
		Knowledge	Known
		Relevance to CF	Relevant
		Corroborated	Yes
#56	Perception of market practices (and of the behaviour of other actors) How market practices are perceived is relevant for certain actors' behaviour (e.g., in a research, interviewees thought that supermarket specifications were connected to food losses).	Factor effects	Facilitating
		Knowledge	Little Known
		Relevance to CF	Very Relevant
		Corroborated	Yes

Factors #48 and #49 are both known and considered relevant by the reviewers who provided few but interesting comments. As for factor #48, one reviewer stressed that some farms are locked in certain practices and technologies, and this should be considered. Another reviewer stressed, somehow on the same line of thinking, that **farms are heterogeneous** and, consequently, different engagement strategies for promoting CFPs are needed for each group. The same reviewer also stressed that grouping by farm type is not useful. Farmers have different knowledge about how to innovate and diverse actors (e.g., advisors, technicians) can be mobilised, and actually are, to bridge the knowledge gap.

Regarding factor #49, two comments were received. On the one hand, it was stressed that, in general, CFPs seem not particularly profitable even if, on the other hand, at certain conditions and for certain types of farmers

(e.g., older farmers choosing agroforestry that is less labour intensive¹⁶), they could appear attractive. In general, it was also stressed that the stake is choosing between practices that are low-risk and guarantee more resilience in the longer term, but, in the short term, produce a decrease in profits.

From the review emerged that a set of factors could be included as relevant to CF – even if they were not initially considered as such (factors #50 to #56). First of all, most of the reviewers agreed that a factor impacting negatively the adoption of CFPs is represented by the bad past experiences of the potential adopters with agricultural policies (factor #50).

Factors #51 and #54 are very similar but based on opposite stances. On the one hand (#51), prejudice impacts adoption negatively. During the workshop in Casale, for example, it was stressed that adopting agroforestry practices is against **widespread views** of cropping farmers¹⁷. **Negative prejudices**, especially those based on worries about potential short-term profit losses, according to some, can be overcome through demonstration, co-design, and dialogue among peers about new practices. Indeed, as stressed by a reviewer, familiarity with certain practices and habits (factor #54) (see also below Category 10 on habits) could be the basis for the above strategies (e.g., resorting to the advice of trusted people). In all the workshops, the importance of these aspects of cooperation in learning (e.g., exchanges between farmers about experiences in adoption) was stressed (see below, category 5). It was also stressed by a reviewer that what matters is not just attitude. In the adoption process, **the opinion of farmers** about whether they will have to change their advisory support, markets, their machines, and their labour is important.

There was a convergence among the reviewers about #52, i.e., on the importance of **farmers' experience of climate change** damages for undertaking new practices. This emerged also in Milan, where the idea of contributing to resilience to climate change through CF could become a drive for adopting new practices (nevertheless, in Milan someone said that currently, climate changes produce damages that make it difficult to undertake the intended changes).

Factors #53 and #56 were scarcely known by the reviewers but considered very relevant. Factor #56 received little comments. As for factor #53, it emerged an agreement among the reviewers on the fact that positive experiences with certain practices bring about further practices. In general, the common trait it can be said that **farmers' (and actors') experience** with the process of change is a crucial aspect to be considered to promote CFP adoption, especially because it forges the perception actors have of them and of their implementation process.

e. Utilitarian vs Non-utilitarian orientation

The fifth sub-category entails those factors implying a utilitarian orientation of actors (or the relative lack thereof) as the main motivation for the adoption of CFPs.

Forms of factors in subcategory 3.e

#	Name of the CF-Related-factor		
#57	Non-monetary drivers are more important than monetary motivation to join programs Economic motivations are not the unique drivers of adoption of new technologies. Farmers decide also to optimise social and	Factor effects	Facilitating
		Knowledge	Well-Known
		Relevance	Relevant

¹⁶ This is at odds with factor #6 that stated that agro-forestry requires an extra effort for tending new trees. The issue could be analysed further: the extra work required could be concentrated in certain phases; but not in others.

¹⁷ One reviewer stressed that this would be relevant for adopting intercropping in olive orchards; where farmers tend to think that a clean area close to the olive trees is better (even in soil is exposed to erosion) to avoid competition for water resources. Another example would be green manure; as in Mediterranean areas farmers think it is best to burn crop residuals.

#	Name of the CF-Related-factor		
	intrinsic goals. Lifestyle farming is relevant for explaining adoption	Corroborated	Yes
#58	The opportunity to participate in carbon credit markets is not the only relevant driver of carbon farming practices Carbon farming practices could depend on incentives that are not necessarily economic.	Factor effects	Facilitating
		Knowledge	Known
		Relevance	Very relevant
		Corroborated	Yes

#	Name of non-CF-related factors (initially)		
#59	Irrational motivations behind the choice of innovating Studies from psychology and sociology found that individuals seemingly acted irrationally, for example: over discounting the future, suffering from overly positive illusions and enacting presumed associations	Factor effects	It depends
		Knowledge	Little known
		Relevance to CF	Very relevant
		Corroborated	Yes
#60	Perception of the effectiveness of the new practices New practices should be perceived as effective from a productive point of view. Perception is not necessarily correlated with actual impacts on yields	Factor effects	It depends
		Knowledge	Little known
		Relevance to CF	Very relevant
		Corroborated	Yes
#61	Emotional attachment to land could hamper relocation Emotional or cultural attachments to land or activity can act both as an enhancer and barrier to adaptation (including relocation).	Factor effects	It depends
		Knowledge	Known
		Relevance to CF	Very relevant
		Corroborated	Yes

As for Factor #57 on “non-monetary drivers” of adoption, there was agreement among the reviewers on its relevance and comments were interesting for better qualifying it: one reviewer suggested that various adopters’ motivations are always connected to, or compatible with, the economic/financial obligation of farmers. One reviewer said that the non-monetary drivers are important but not more important for farmers than the economic drivers.

There was a substantial agreement also on factor #58, since economic incentives are important, but not uniquely relevant for CFP. It was stressed by one reviewer that SOC has a saturation level, so carbon sequestration cannot be considered an absolute incentive.

The factors not initially connected to CF could be considered relevant to its adoption, according to the reviewers. As for factor #59 on the importance of “irrational motivations”, an interesting comment was that decisions on farming practices, including CF, should be based on compelling reasons (either “rational” or not). Another participant suggested that rational reasons could be not sufficient and long-term consequences (that could be considered “rational”) come after priorities such as preserving profit in the short term.

Some reviewers agreed on the importance of “Perception of the effectiveness of the new practices” (#60) but they stressed the connection of such perceptions to the actual yields. Another reviewer stressed that the ultimate impact of CF is not certain and is contextual; furthermore, the final balance is not absolute (i.e., you may reduce production, but the related production costs could decrease even more; lost production could impact differently in places where there is food scarcity compared to where this problem is absent). The “emotional attachment to land” (#61) has been considered very relevant by various reviewers. It is an important motivator for change but could work in the opposite direction. It was also commented that it can create prejudices.

B.4. Technological and operational complexity of innovation

The adoption of new technologies and CFP, or new arrangements needed to enter VCM, are endeavours that are complex in many respects.

Also in this case, we will present these results using three sub-categories, that will be presented in the following sub-paragraphs.

a. Time required for change

From the review emerged that the time dimension is a factor impacting adoption of CF. Therefore, the first sub-category has to do with those factors – all were hindering – connected to the time needed for implementing new practices and for letting them produce the desired impacts.

Forms of factors in subcategory 4.a

#	Name of the CF-Related-factor		
#62	Soil organic carbon content of Mediterranean soils changes relatively slowly The relative slowness of Soil organic carbon content of Mediterranean soils makes payments for sequestration less attractive.	Factor effects	Hindering
		Knowledge	Known
		Relevance	Very Relevant
		Corroborated	Yes
#63	Timing of payment (before or after sequestration) If payments are done before sequestration based on expected climate impacts, it increases uncertainty about actual impacts and decreases permanence incentives; if payments are done ex-post, this represents a risk for farmers.	Factor effects	Hindering
		Knowledge	Well-known
		Relevance	Very relevant
		Corroborated	Yes
#64	Slowness of technological innovation in agriculture Studies demonstrate that initial adoption rates of adoption of Climate Smart agricultural practices is slow.	Factor effects	Hindering
		Knowledge	Known
		Relevance to CF	Relevant
		Corroborated	Yes

These three factors were corroborated during the review process. Factor #62 is specific to particular geographical areas (Mediterranean soils) where the attractiveness of CFPs (reviewers mostly said “all” CFPs) could diminish significantly.

Timing of payments for Carbon sequestration (#63) is also considered relevant. Basing payment on expected impacts could increase uncertainty if impacts turn out to be lower. Ex-post payments increase risks for farmer. Anyhow, it was suggested that pre-payment for CF could be made attractive and could consider this risk.

A phenomenon that was considered for agricultural innovation in general – its slowness (#64) – was considered relevant also for CF. In this framework, it is interesting that two reviewers said that the slowness of innovation processes could also be due to the relatively old age of farmers, who are relatively less oriented to change than the younger ones. This observation was done also during the workshops.

b. Complexity of the technologies and the control system

The second sub-category is connected to the complexity of technologies – typically those aimed at sequestering carbon into soil – and/or of the control system for acting in the market.

Forms of factors in subcategory 4.b

#	Name of the CF-Related-factor		
#65	Difficulty in integrating GHG impacts into national GHG inventories Difficulty in integrating GHG impacts into national GHG inventories. This fact can undermine the integrity of schemes, including demands for credits.	Factor effects	Hindering
		Knowledge	Known
		Relevance	Very relevant
		Corroborated	Yes
#66	Control systems are not effective Absence of a system of control for the fulfilment of legal regulation.	Factor effects	Hindering
		Knowledge	Known
		Relevance	Very relevant
		Corroborated	Yes
#67	Permanent grassland has physical constraints There are physical-environmental constraints in practicing permanent grassland, since after a certain time lapse the quality of grass begins to diminish.	Factor effects	Hindering
		Knowledge	Known
		Relevance	Relevant
		Corroborated	Yes
#68	Some practices diffuse contaminants The use of slurry may increase the accumulation of metals in the soil. Biochar or municipal compost have similar risks.	Factor effects	Hindering
		Knowledge	Well-known
		Relevance	Very relevant
		Corroborated	Yes
#69	R&D can reduce the uncertainty of MRV that hampers the adoption of carbon farming practices R&D can reduce uncertainty of MRV that hampers the adoption of carbon farming practices. The current level of uncertainty hinders market-based carbon farming schemes. Investments in research are needed and should be complemented by continuing practical experience to identify further barriers and new solutions.	Factor effects	Facilitating
		Knowledge	Well-known
		Relevance	Very relevant
		Corroborated	Yes
#70	Carbon leakage could diminish sequestration The emissions reduced by one country through stricter environmental controls or greater voluntary adoption of mitigating measures by actors, are increased in another country with weaker environmental protection.	Factor effects	Hindering
		Knowledge	Well-known
		Relevance	Very relevant
		Corroborated	Yes
#71	Technological trade-offs could offset the positive impacts of new practices Certain practices could imply adverse effects that could offset other positive impacts. Examples are the risk of fire caused by crop residue in Mediterranean areas; or the need to increase herbicides. Effects are not necessarily negative.	Factor effects	It depends
		Knowledge	Well-known
		Relevance	Very Relevant
		Corroborated	Yes
#72	Technical uncertainties/Lack of verified impact of technologies	Factor effects	Hindering
		Knowledge	Well-known
		Relevance	Very relevant
		Corroborated	Yes

#	Name of the CF-Related-factor		
	Technical uncertainties concerning the implementation of certain practices (e.g., use of agricultural inputs), the results that will be produced, the interaction with other practices.		
#73	Leakage of emissions within farms undermines additionality This phenomenon can occur when certain schemes are implemented in one part of a farm. In the others, the positive effects could be offset. This undermines additionality.	Factor effects	Hindering
		Knowledge	Known
		Relevance	Very relevant
		Corroborated	Yes
#74	The complexity and uncertainty of Market-based schemes of carbon soil certification There are many requirements for farmers to interact with carbon markets and the related actors and this creates additional costs – transaction costs. Extra activities are required for validation of the credit claimed and validation of reporting. The farmers bear the costs of climate actions while being highly uncertain about the possible rewards of such actions. Such uncertainty depends also on the possible occurrence of events that are completely out of farmers' control (e.g., wildfires). Another source of uncertainty is the fluctuation of the carbon market price.	Factor effects	Hindering
		Knowledge	Known
		Relevance	Very relevant
		Corroborated	Yes
#75	Lack of institutional capacity at the national and regional level The ability of regulators (at the national and regional level) to establish effective carbon markets is scarce. Difficulties regard all the phases of the market process, including setting up, implementing, and monitoring schemes. This problem is exacerbated once multiple jurisdictions are considered.	Factor effects	Hindering
		Knowledge	Known
		Relevance	Very relevant
		Corroborated	Yes
#76	New agricultural practices imply more organisational complexity Crop rotation implies management constraints that are not present for monocultures. Furthermore, paperwork is relevant since participation in carbon market programs implies reading long contracts, apply additionality requirements and so on.	Factor effects	Hindering
		Knowledge	Known
		Relevance	Relevant
		Corroborated	Yes
#	Name of non-CF-related factors (initially)		
#77	New technologies are complex Complexity refers to the degree to which an innovation is perceived as difficult to understand. Greater complexity of SAP should be negatively related to adoption.	Factor effects	Hindering
		Knowledge	Well-known
		Relevance	Very relevant
		Corroborated	Yes
#78	Availability and readiness of animal manure Ready availability of animal manure could be a problem for those farmers who do not practice both crop cultivation and livestock farming or do not have neighbours who do this.	Factor effects	Hindering
		Knowledge	Well-known
		Relevance to CF	Relevant
		Corroborated	Yes

Factors #65 “Difficulty in integrating GHG impacts into national GHG inventories” and #66 “Control systems are not effective” did not receive comments from the reviewers who know them. About the issue covered by factor #66, in Madrid workshop was commented that, at least for what concerns

Mediterranean semiarid rainfed cereal cropping systems, there is a lack of **transparency and complexity of MRV systems** (producing uncertainties in the estimation of carbon stocking). In the same workshop, this was confirmed with the consideration that MRV methodologies should be designed as simply as possible, without compromising their robustness and reliability. A problem was found in that MRV does not consider environmental trade-offs (including nutrient leaching and Greenhouse Gas Emissions).

Factors #67 “Permanent grassland has physical constraints” did not receive many comments from the reviewers, apart from the consideration that, with good management of grassland, the problem could be overcome. Factor #68 “Some practices diffuse contaminants” was not commented although it was well-known and considered very relevant by the reviewers (therefore, corroborated).

According to some reviewers, the issue of **costs of MRV** is acknowledged as important and R&D could contribute to this (Factor #69). Attention to R&D was paid not just by the reviewers but also during the workshops, for example in Dorinne, where the issue of the controversial effectiveness of CFPs was raised. In particular, it was stressed that the lack of **scientific consensus undermines the robustness of MRV methodology**. The need of R&D was also raised in Casale; in Milan, someone said that the focus should be also on the economic sustainability of CF, and, similarly, a proper risk assessment was suggested in Madrid.

Factor #72, i.e., “**Technical uncertainties**/Lack of verified impact of technologies” was recognised as a barrier by the reviewers. One reviewer stressed that CFPs are well known but their adaptation to specific local conditions is not well developed, which means plenty of risks for farmers who have reasons to be concerned about their adoption. In Dorinne, the issue of the complexity of verifying the carbon credits was raised and in the Casale workshop, someone stressed the need of precision soil mapping and baseline definition. The former issue was stressed also in Madrid: baselines are necessary to control the problem of additionality and for the issue of the comparative disadvantage of those farmers who have already implemented CFPs are closer to saturation limits.

The need for an MRV system that is effective to promote positive impacts on carbon markets has emerged strongly in the Madrid workshop. It is connected – and provides further corroboration to both factors #69 and #72. Particularly for what concerns agroforestry system of “dehesa”¹⁸, barriers were indicated in the **lack of harmonised robust data** and validated methodologies and in the absence of historical information and long-term studies for evaluating the effect of agroforestry practices. Specific advances in MRV technologies were seen as enablers, particularly remote sensing for mixed systems (tree-pasture). This would be seen as an opportunity for its use in harmonised modelling and cost reduction.

In Madrid, it was also stressed the opportunity to leverage existing data from long-term monitoring networks and to harmonise and standardise methodologies, improve databases, and develop validation methods. These, of course, are opportunities to overcome the uncertainties (#72) connected to technical problems that could be taken up through R&D (#69). Research could help to deal with uncertainties of their actual impact on carbon stocking and clarify the unknown beneficial and trade-offs effects of CFPs in the economic, social, and environmental domains, which was stressed in Madrid in relation CFPs in Mediterranean semiarid rainfed cereal cropping systems. There is a need to address these issues also through fundamental research and long-term experiments, especially for how to adapt CFPs to local conditions and assess their environmental and economic impacts at different time frames.

Factor #70 “Carbon leakage could diminish sequestration” was not commented, although it was well known by the reviewers that considered it very relevant for the adoption of CFPs. Factor #71

¹⁸ Dehesas are traditional agrosilvopastoral ecosystems in the Iberian Peninsula; originating from clearings of dense forests to combine tree exploitation; agriculture; and grassland. The result is an open arboreal ecosystem with a savanna-like structure; mainly dominated by Mediterranean holm oaks (*Quercus ilex* L.) and cork oaks (*Q. suber* L.).

“Technological trade-offs could offset the positive impacts of new practices” was commented on by one reviewer who said that trade-offs are common problems and change according to local conditions.

Factor #73 “Leakage of emissions within farms undermines additionality” was commented on by two reviewers who focused on the problem of implementing MRV in heterogenic terrains (Mediterranean region in which costs could increase) or in mixed farms.

The problem of uncertainty indicated by factor #74, “The complexity and uncertainty of Market-based schemes of carbon soil certification”, was also commented on by one reviewer who said that well-thought schemes could factor in risks, especially in the case of CF schemes implemented on large scale. The problem, said another reviewer, is that the gains from participation in the carbon market could be not as relevant as the other CAP subsidies. In Madrid (in relation to Mediterranean semiarid rainfed cereal cropping systems) was stressed that the chosen MRV methodologies can influence the estimation of carbon stocks (and this could increase the overall uncertainty about carbon market functioning). In Madrid, it was said that the practice of CF could be enabled through a discussion with experts and local actors about the final MRV methodologies under the EU Carbon Farming Removal Certification Framework (CRCF). In this way, it could be also addressed the need for a common understanding of crucial terms such as carbon sequestration, carbon stocking and mitigation of carbon losses.

The “Lack of institutional capacity at the national and regional level” (factor #75) was recognised as a barrier by the reviewers that – according to one of them – could be anyhow overcome.

One of the factors, “**New agricultural practices imply more organisational complexity**” (#76), was recognised also during the workshops (for example in Milan). Interesting is the comment of one reviewer, who said that the issue of rotation should be understood in the framework of the participation of farms in value chains: the resulting complexity must be understood and dealt with on this basis and is not an issue under the responsibility of individual players.

Two further factors were considered by the reviewers as relevant also for carbon farming. First of all, there is the complexity of new technologies (#77, a barrier). One reviewer suggested that this problem could be compounded by the size of agricultural exploitations in Europe, which are small in general (and less able to implement complex innovations), and by the fact that farms are generally run by aged farmers (who are less likely to innovate). Understanding new technologies is therefore a relevant aspect of innovation and represents the rationale of promoting training (see category 5, below).

The problem of the “Availability and readiness of animal manure” (Factor #78) was commented on by one reviewer as an issue that should be dealt with pragmatically, depending on the characteristics of the local agricultural systems.

c. Role of actors in the implementation

The third sub-category is about the role of actors in the implementation of new practices.

Forms of factors in subcategory 4.c

#	Name of the CF-Related-factor		
#79	Neglect of stakeholders in project design of sinking carbon Stakeholders needs and behaviours are not included in the design process of project design of sinking carbon	Factor effects	Hindering
		Knowledge	Known
		Relevance	Relevant
		Corroborated	Yes

#	Name of non-CF-related factors (initially)		
#80	Technologies are not fit for local farmers' needs Technologies neglect many 'day-to-day' realities faced by farmers. They are carried out by professionals who don't know the actual problems of farmers and needs.	Factor effects	Hindering
		Knowledge	Known
		Relevance to CF	Very relevant
		Corroborated	Yes

Both factors were known by the reviewers and finally corroborated. No open comments were provided by the reviewers about factor #79, while comments were provided about the fitness of technologies to local farmers' needs (factor #80). It was stressed that the problem is evident for small farmers (as it is also in non-agricultural sectors) and can be overcome through specific policies (e.g., community of practice, networks); the need for technologies suited to farms of every size was raised in Milan. The problem, as a reviewer also stressed, is compounded when technologies are promoted by private firms that do not consider small farmers' needs. This risk was also stressed in Dorinne, where it was indicated the risk of industry and agri-food sectors imposing on farmers inappropriate standards (e.g., for dairy cattle).

B.5. Role of advisory, information and training services, and soil illiteracy

New agricultural practices are normally introduced thanks to the support given to the technology users by a range of diverse advisory services, particularly through the provision of information, training, etc.

The factors related to this category will be presented following a subdivision in sub-categories.

Even if the factors can be analysed in the framework of the sub-categories and presented one by one, it is important to anticipate that this overall category deals with the issue of transfer of knowledge that obtained a big interest during the consultation process. The issue is not new, particularly in agriculture. Anyhow, it results that it is topical for CF and the related issue of VCM in agriculture. This stems from the fact that the envisaged change (to CF) has such a scope that many actors are required to adopt new routines, modus operandi and farming practices. At the centre of this change process, therefore, there are not only the farmers and their practice, but the entire agricultural ecosystem of actors (individual and collective, including advisors, trainers, and researchers in the public and private sectors as well), that are called to act in a coordinate way so that this big innovation process can take place.

a. Advisory needs for CF technologies and VCM procedures

The first sub-category under this category concerns the need for advisory services, which in this case is particularly relevant, given the technological and bureaucratic complexity of MRV for CF and the VCM.

Forms of factors in subcategory 5.a

#	Name of the CF-Related-factor		
#81	Communication barriers toward consumers Difficulties to communicate to consumers the additional (social) value of output produced in carbon farming schemes.	Factor effects	Hindering
		Knowledge	Known
		Relevance	Very relevant
		Corroborated	Yes
#	Name of non-CF-related factors (initially)		
#82	Farmers are hard to reach and train Some potential users of the Climate Smart Agriculture (CSA) technological innovations (and technology providers) are based several supply chain stages away from the farm.	Factor effects	Hindering
		Knowledge	Little known
		Relevance to CF	Little relevant
		Corroborated	No
#83	Trial of new practices is not easy Uptake of new practices depends on the difficulties to make trials.	Factor effects	Hindering
		Knowledge	Known
		Relevance to CF	Relevant
		Corroborated	Yes
#84	Scarce observability of impacts Difficulty in proving value and demonstrating impact of Climate Smart Agriculture innovations.	Factor effects	Hindering
		Knowledge	Well known
		Relevance to CF	Very relevant
		Corroborated	Yes

#	Name of non-CF-related factors (initially)		
#85	Difficulties for technology providers in reaching customers Difficulties for technology providers are both identifying and reaching specific customer segments.	Factor effects	Hindering
		Knowledge	Known
		Relevance to CF	Relevant
		Corroborated	Yes

The reviewers recognised the importance of communication barriers with consumers (factor #81) about the social value of CF schemes. Comments pointed out that consumers' willingness to pay is limited and not necessarily focused on CF as such (but on organic practices in general). In the Madrid workshop it was stressed that there is an opportunity for doing communication on these issues (to stakeholders but, it can be assumed also in general, therefore including the public).

Most of the generic factors, i.e., not connected in the literature explicitly to CF, were recognised by reviewers as relevant also to CF. While factor #82 was not corroborated, the others were.

The need for trials in specific locations (factor #83), so to adapt CFP to local needs are highly needed according to one reviewer, while another said that – generally speaking – the organisational infrastructures for these practices are available in EU member states and should be activated. The importance of networks of technical assistance emerged also in the Milan workshop. This orientation was reported also in the Amalie workshop, in which the importance of real-life examples for demonstrating to farmers the new methods was stressed.

This is in line with what a specific difficulty– according to the reviewers – of CF, i.e., the **scarce observability of impacts** (factor #84): they are difficult to verify, emerge in the longer term, and are connected to wider ecosystems services. In this framework, trials and training are important. The issue of training emerged clearly from all the workshops as an outstanding necessity to be addressed. Clear guidelines about the implementation of CF could be useful, was suggested in Milan, and the presentation of the available production and cultivation models was suggested in Casale.

Generally, the reviewers also agreed about the difficulties of technology providers to reach customers (factor #85). One reviewer said that this is also because of the wide variety of farming systems, which need different technologies or their adaptation to specific needs. For this reason, cooperation between farmers, private and research sectors is needed, according to another. In Casale, some participants stressed the importance of comparison and discussion between stakeholders through workshops and other initiatives. In Madrid the opportunity to create manager associations and share information and training in a framework of public-private cooperation was indicated.

b. Advisory agencies' skills and capacities

The second sub-category of factors concerns the capacity of advisory agencies – or the lack thereof – to provide services of the quality required for dealing with soil health, soil carbon, and other related issues.

Forms of factors in subcategory 5.b

#	Name of the CF-Related-factor		
#86	Lack of knowledge of certain practices (CC, manure, etc.) Lack of knowledge of certain practices by the implementers. This concerns both basic aspects and arrangements to optimise the impacts of given technologies.	Factor effects	Hindering
		Knowledge	Well known
		Relevance	Relevant
		Corroborated	Yes

#	Name of the CF-Related-factor		
#87	Advisor services (and quality) help adoption Advisor services and their quality help adoption. There is a need for more cooperation among the various services, more attention to the actual needs and to the specific regional and local conditions (soil, climate, current practices, etc.). Attention to the needs could also include giving feedback to farmers). The capacity of using local social capital is relevant.	Factor effects	Facilitating
		Knowledge	Well known
		Relevance	Very relevant
		Corroborated	Yes
#	Name of non-CF-related factors (initially)		
#88	Lack of a widely agreed definition for soil health as a novel concept There is not an agreed definition of the nature of healthy soil and of indicators (and the related thresholds) relevant for each type of soils, land use and climate context.	Factor effects	Hindering
		Knowledge	Well known
		Relevance to CF	Relevant
		Corroborated	Yes
#89	Training needs for precision farming Precision farming: there is a need for training the farmers as complex software are installed in the machinery (PW).	Factor effects	It depends
		Knowledge	Known
		Relevance to CF	Relevant
		Corroborated	Yes
#90	Alliances of advisors Alliances of advisors could help in the promotion of the adoption of advanced practices for soil health.	Factor effects	It depends
		Knowledge	Known
		Relevance to CF	Relevant
		Corroborated	Yes
#91	Low awareness of Climate Smart Agriculture CSA/inaccessible language Climate change and sustainability initiatives (including CSA) were associated with 'jargon', which non-experts found hard to understand and off-putting.	Factor effects	Hindering
		Knowledge	Known
		Relevance to CF	Little relevant
		Corroborated	No
#92	Knowledge gap on soil health Knowledge gap concerns not just the final adopters of new practices, but is also widespread among advisors. It is due to various reasons including that knowledge is often specialised according to disciplinary boundaries or the lack of meaningful guidance for the advisors.	Factor effects	Hindering
		Knowledge	Well known
		Relevance to CF	Very relevant
		Corroborated	Yes

Factor #86 – **lack of knowledge of practices by the potential implementers** – was well-known and considered relevant by the reviewers; one commented that it is crucial to make the general understanding of CFPs practical for implementers (i.e., the right combination of various CFPs), while another one said that knowledge of CFPs is unevenly diffused, since it depends on the farm type, on the sector and on geographical area: “More intensive system farmers are less likely to know about these practices, while those practising regenerative agriculture will know”. As stressed above, during the workshops emerged clearly the issue of training and the need to access knowledge. In Milan and Casale, it was stressed the importance of supporting farmers in adopting new practices and the agricultural sector in the transition to sustainable agriculture also to overcome the lack of knowledge and technical support.

The **quality of advisory services** as a facilitating factor (when quality is high, factor #87) was also recognised as crucial by the reviewers. Particularly, the actual orientation of the advisors was

highlighted: one reviewer suggested that they should be open to CF innovations, while another one stressed the importance of independence of the providers of advisory services (i.e., separate from input distributors and input producers). The latter issue emerged clearly in Milan.

The lack of a widely agreed **definition of soil health** as a novel concept (factor #88) was corroborated and commented by the reviewers. In general, it was stressed that common definitions and, mostly, agreed-upon indicators could help in pursuing soil health policies and promoting CF. Interestingly, resulted that the reviewers agreed on the existence of a knowledge gap on soil health also among advisors (factor #92). One held that the problem of knowledge on soil health is that the very scientific community has not yet reached a consensus on various issues. Anyhow, it was stressed that training for trainers is important.

There is a certain agreement on the relevance of precision farming techniques (factor #89) among the reviewers and, in some cases, the importance of training farmers about such techniques was highlighted. Notwithstanding the centrality recognised to the issue of training and to making it more and more tailored to actual needs within the sector, the issue of creating alliances of advisors (factor #90) is not considered overwhelmingly important. One reviewer stressed that cooperatives sometimes fulfil this function, and another one held that this could be useful in a sector that in some countries is very fragmented. In the Milan workshop, some commented that the local system of assistance to farmers provides information on CF.

Finally, factor #91, concerning the inaccessibility of language, was not corroborated. This result deserves a brief comment: there was a divide among the reviewers who commented, as some considered it very relevant while others didn't. Probably, this factor would deserve further inquiry since it focuses on linguistic aspects of policies (the perception of technical language as experts' jargon, that could create scepticisms among potential adopters). It is very specific and, maybe, available knowledge concerning it is mostly anecdotal.

c. General weaknesses of advisory agencies

The last sub-category is the general capacity of advisory agencies to provide services, which is a crucial aspect of a successful innovation process whose presence cannot be taken for granted.

Forms of factors in subcategory 5.c

#	Name of the CF-Related-factor		
#93	Education and training favour the adoption Education and training favour adoption, and interpersonal relations are important.	Factor effects	Facilitating
		Knowledge	Well known
		Relevance	Very Relevant
		Corroborated	Yes
#94	Credibility of advisors Credibility of advisors is crucial since behavioural changes, albeit difficult, can be achieved if those who promote them are recognised as authority and trustful.	Factor effects	Facilitating
		Knowledge	Well known
		Relevance	Very relevant
		Corroborated	Yes
#	Name of non-CF-related factors (initially)		
#95	Organisational weaknesses of public Soil Health Management advice services	Factor effects	Hindering
		Knowledge	Known

#	Name of non-CF-related factors (initially)		
	Organisational weaknesses limit the delivery of services. Such weaknesses consist of lack of adequate investment in staff capacity, little continuity in the provision of funds, little staff retention, competition with private services.	Relevance to CF	Very relevant
		Corroborated	Yes
#96	No-segmentation of information provision services The approach to extension with farmers should be segmented and targeted. It should not just provide information but also be more helpful and appeal to people's values.	Factor effects	Hindering
		Knowledge	Known
		Relevance to CF	Very relevant
		Corroborated	Yes
#97	Fragmentation of Advisory services for Agriculture Various providers of advisory services compete for clients and project funding. This brings about that soil advice for farmers is characterised by duplication, conflicting deliveries and other malfunctioning.	Factor effects	Hindering
		Knowledge	Little known
		Relevance to CF	Very relevant
		Corroborated	Yes

The idea that **education and training** favour the adoption of CF (factor #93) was widely accepted by the reviewers, including that of the importance of personal relations. One reviewer suggested that the latter is an issue relatively neglected by researchers. In Madrid, it was stressed the importance of training and capacity building on VCMs. The importance of education and persuasion (therefore including also interpersonal aspects) was stressed in Amalie workshop. In Milan, it was indicated the need to promote, among farmers knowledge and life-long learning (that is known for being based also on the management of interpersonal dimension of learning).

Credibility of advisors is a factor (#94) that was corroborated by the reviewers. One interesting comment was that credibility is particularly relevant because it is a new concept and implies the involvement of new players, i.e., the VCM intermediaries who are not known and therefore not trusted.

Factor #95 on the “**Organisational weaknesses** of public Soil Health Management advice services” was considered relevant also for CF. Comments from the reviewers were convergent in saying that this aspect of the system is crucial, also considering the need to contextualise CFPs for different land uses and landscapes. In Casale, some participants stressed the importance of Training of technicians, while in Milan was stressed that training is crucial for farmers and consultancy services as well.

The absence of segmentation of information services for farmers (#96) was recognised by some reviewers as a factor impacting also on CFPs adoption. The idea is that not enough attention is paid to adapt services and information to the actual needs of the variety of possible users. In some workshops the issue of targeting better services emerged clearly: in Casale was stressed the importance of “Ad hoc training courses”; in Amalie, someone stressed that training is needed as well as “persuasion, argumentation, promotion, and motivation”. In Madrid, when talking of the specific needs of “agroforestry systems of dehesa” it was indicated as a barrier the lack of training for farmers and livestock breeders on carbon capture practices. Similarly, when talking of CFPs in “Mediterranean semiarid rainfed cereal cropping systems”, as a barrier was indicated the lack of training and information on how CFPs should be implemented at the local level in these cropping systems, as usually they require more knowledge and skills than conventional practices.

Fragmentation of Advisory services for Agriculture, i.e., factor #97, was considered as relevant for CF. It is interesting to note that it resonates with comments about factor #87, about the independence of consultants (from private firms). In this case, the problem is the market orientation of advisors who are demand-driven and not supply-driven. This could undermine the effort to lead innovation toward specific objectives. The issue of the possible divergence between public and private consultants has been raised in Milan.

B.6. Policies and regulation

A relevant category of factors impacting the adoption of new agriculture practices is policies and regulations. Agriculture, in general, is closely connected to policies that include several types of interventions (involving both public and private actors). In this framework, how the use of technology, or a market, is regulated is important to explain how they work and their performances. Furthermore, agricultural practices change according to location, and, in general, policies should address the different needs emerging from this diversity and should fit the local systems they aim to regulate and control.

Three subcategories of factors relevant to agricultural system management were identified. The factors will be presented below according to them, including relevant comments from the reviewers and from the workshops.

a. Rules impeding CF adoption

The first sub-category includes those factors connected to how rules could hamper or facilitate CFP adoption.

Forms of factors in subcategory 6.a

#	Name of the CF-Related-factor		
#98	Current rules sometimes prevent the adoption of innovation for Soil Carbon Management Practices Some Soil Carbon Management Practices cannot be practiced in specific national contexts because current legislations actually forbid them or hinder them.	Factor effects	Hindering
		Knowledge	Well-known
		Relevance	Relevant
		Corroborated	Yes
#99	Inconsistencies between different regulations Inconsistencies between different regulations concerning different aspect of certain practices could create legal restrictions. Different regulations pursue different objectives that could be conflicting (e.g., European, National, local, etc)	Factor effects	Hindering
		Knowledge	Known
		Relevance	Very relevant
		Corroborated	Yes
#100	Barriers to certification hamper markets from working well Carbon credit markets involve trading a credence good (those whose quality consumers cannot directly verify and for which experts' evaluation is needed), and any barriers to certification hinder their proper functioning.	Factor effects	Hindering
		Knowledge	Known
		Relevance	Relevant
		Corroborated	Yes

Factor #98, “Current rules sometimes prevent the adoption of innovation for Soil Carbon Management Practices”, has been corroborated by the reviewers. Their comments were interesting since they were pinpointed mainly on legislation about the management of manure. Other problems were related to agroforestry¹⁹ and peatland. The issue was commented also during the workshops: in Milan barriers the existing norms about fertilisers or agrochemicals were indicated; in Dorinne emerged the issue of the ambiguity of regulatory frameworks (that give inconsistent operational directions while, if well designed could lead to satisfy the expectations of the market).

¹⁹ Example was that tree species in agroforestry that are eligible for support payments; in some cases, this creates conflicts with maintaining permanent grasslands or protected biotopes/species in the context of rewetting organic soils.

Another problem with the legislation is indicated by factor #99, on the “**Inconsistencies between different regulations**”. There were not many comments of the reviewers, but the issue was commented in the workshops. In Dorinne it was stressed that the application of CF schemes is applied differently in the EU countries; in Milan was stressed the need for harmonised CF schemes and coherence between national and European policies (and the related regulations), while in Madrid was stressed the problem of correspondence with the CAP and the compatibility of incentives with the international certification systems (at least in the agroforestry system of dehesa). A related problem, emerged in Madrid, is the need for harmonising the existing MRV methodologies. Similarly, in Amalie was indicated need for the establishment of a fair and transparent carbon measurement system.

“**Barriers to certification** hamper markets from working well” (factor #100) were recognised as relevant but not many comments have been provided by the reviewers (one stressed that there is not a big regulation; another stressed that these barriers to Credit Market are relevant for the maintenance of CF more than for its adoption). Also from the workshop did not emerge particularly significant comments, apart from those stressing the high cost of implementing MRV methodologies (that are conditional to the participation in VCMs).

b. Effective regulation

The second sub-category concerns the effectiveness of different types of regulations.

Forms of factors in subcategory 6.b

#	Name of the CF-Related-factor		
#101	Effective standards promote the adoption/ Lack of a solid monitoring scheme The existence of effective standards promotes the adoption of new practices (notwithstanding costs of compliance). Due to uncertainties in the MRV of net SCS and concerns about double accounting, activities that enhance net SCS have not been eligible.	Factor effects	Hindering
		Knowledge	Well-known
		Relevance	Very relevant
		Corroborated	Yes
#102	Uniform Subsidies are not effective Due to different operational conditions uniform subsidies are not effective.	Factor effects	Hindering
		Knowledge	Known
		Relevance	Little relevant
		Corroborated	No
#103	Lack of data at the local level Data on current/past GHG emissions/sequestration data or sufficient data for accurate GHG estimation needed for regulating the market.	Factor effects	Hindering
		Knowledge	Well-known
		Relevance	Very relevant
		Corroborated	Yes
#104	Uncertainty over credit ownership for regulators/administrators The lack of reliable and robust registry of carbon credit can make the demand decrease.	Factor effects	Hindering
		Knowledge	Well-known
		Relevance	Relevant
		Corroborated	Yes
#105	Carbon Audit tools can be manipulated Farmers, in principle, can “play” with carbon credit tools, e.g., changing inputs to maximise expected reductions in unrealistic ways. This undermines the functioning of the Carbon market.	Factor effects	Hindering
		Knowledge	Known
		Relevance	Very relevant
		Corroborated	Yes

The importance of “effective standards to promote the adoption of CFPs” (factor #101) was recognised by the reviewers, without many comments. The issue emerged as relevant in some workshops, such as in Dorinne, where it was indicated that the growing diversity of carbon offset mechanisms and standards is a flaw of the certification schemes. In Madrid it was indicated the absence of specific standards from the administration and of a list of practices to be evaluated as barriers for the agroforestry system of dehesa; in Madrid concerns were raised concern about the compatibility of the future EU MRV approach with the existing ones.

Factor #102 was not confirmed by the reviewers, and the issue was not brought up during the workshops.

As for the “lack of data at the local level” (factor #103), it was well-known by the reviewers, who considered it very relevant too. One observed that the problem is not just about GHG emissions. The issue of lack of reliable data was raised also in Milan. It should be added that this could be seen as a more general obstacle, those of lack of knowledge, an issue that was raised in various workshops: in Dorinne was mentioned the lack of knowledge about the main obstacles of CF, and in Madrid the real impact of CFPs. In Amalie was stressed that regulation should be based on research.

Factor #104, concerning **uncertainty over credit ownership**, was considered important by the reviewers, but not many comments were provided. Not many comments came from the workshops on the issue too. In Madrid an enabler for VCM schemes was indicated in a common registry, aimed at ensuring the traceability of carbon exchanges and their impact on carbon inventories. Anyhow, the general questions of the certainty of results or the need for the creation of marks and certification for encouraging the uptake of CFPs were raised in Milan and Casale. Similarly to the idea of creating marks, in Madrid was suggested the idea of labelling for farmers and territories adopting CFPs.

The **possible manipulation** of Carbon Audit tools (factor #105) was recognised as a hindering factor by the reviewers. One of them stressed that it concerns the issue of trust in the certification system, which is a general one. In the workshop in Amalie, the need for a quality monitoring of soil properties was raised.

c. Diverse contexts and conditions of policies' implementation

The last sub-category collects the factors concerning how much policies are tuned to the various contexts and conditions of implementation.

Forms of factors in subcategory 6.c

#	Name of the CF-Related-factor		
#106	Multiple and contradictory policy goals/unintended effects of policies Multiple and contradictory policy goals may be a barrier to a successful increase of carbon avoided and sequestered.	Factor effects	Hindering
		Knowledge	Well-known
		Relevance	Very relevant
		Corroborated	Yes
#107	Policy mix Different actions within policies favour adoption (e.g., favouring combinations of different practices).	Factor effects	Facilitating
		Knowledge	Well-known
		Relevance	Very relevant
		Corroborated	Yes
#108	Policies should consider geographical variability Biophysical environment diversity changes the conditions in which carbon farming is most effective. Policies should be	Factor effects	It depends
		Knowledge	Well-known
		Relevance	Very relevant

#	Name of the CF-Related-factor		
	based on this assumption and defining different payment schemes.	Corroborated	Yes

#	Name of non-CF-related factors (initially)		
#109	Policies are crucial for agriculture Policies are already dominant factors in agricultural management. Oftentimes farmers are already compliant with policies related provisions.	Factor effects	It depends
		Knowledge	Well-known
		Relevance to CF	Very relevant
		Corroborated	Yes

When talking about this sub-category it is important to stress that factor #109, focused on the **centrality of policies for agriculture**, initially not connected to CF, was recognised as very relevant by most of the reviewers. Reviewers' comments mostly agreed that policies are already dominant in agriculture. This factor helps to highlight the context of the transition toward a more environmentally sustainable agriculture, able to include CFPs.

Recognising the centrality of factor #109 helps to understand the saliency of the other three factors of this sub-category, which were all corroborated.

Factor #106 is focused on the existence of multiple and contradictory policy goals, that could create diverse unintended consequences. It was recognised by almost all the reviewers as very relevant. From the workshops, emerged a lot of comments confirming how policy goals could contradict each other, creating unintended consequences. In Dorinne, many participants indicated the **risk of greenwashing**: the reduction CO2 emission produced by farmers could be claimed by other actors bringing about the continuation of pollution. In practice it could turn out that private interests are served by CF policies more than the production of environmental benefits. "Perverse effects" were also quoted in Madrid as possible consequences due to the lack of VCMs credibility, particularly the risk of land abandonment, their conversion to grassland or forest or the intensification of agricultural practices due to speculative trade²⁰.

Another risk, indicated in Dorinne, was that of simplification of agricultural systems and intensification (e.g., dairy cattle and reduction of emissions). In that occasion, it was also stressed the risk that industry and agrifood sectors impose on farmers inappropriate standards (e.g., for dairy cattle). Another risk, also indicated in the Dorinne workshop, is that of rewarding with higher income farmers who make less effort than others but store more due to better soil quality (in relation to carbon storage). Policies could end up providing the wrong incentives, failing to cope with the challenge of complexity (as stressed above, for sub-category 1.b). For all these reasons, in Madrid was also suggested that public policies should be aimed at tackling this kind of risk through public supervision of certification entities and auditors with the aim of avoiding, for example, possible speculative trade, greenwashing, or double accounting.

The context of policies is clearly characterised by complexity. The importance of factor #107, focused on the issue of policy mix (favouring CFP adoption by means of a combination of practices), was widely recognised by the reviewers, who did not provide further comments. In the workshops, the issue emerged in several ways. In Dorinne, when talking of possible European or regional frameworks/schemes for CF, various policies objectives were indicated, such as finding a way to reward farmers for the ecosystem services they provide (and legitimise agriculture) or initiating farmers towards a transition to sustainable/regenerative agriculture. Such schemes, as it was also said in Dorinne, implying the clarification of the working environment of farmers promoting their access, would

²⁰ In Madrid this was connected to Mediterranean semiarid rainfed cereal cropping systems; but it could be considered a general risk.

help to legitimise CF and the connected creation of new markets, the involvement of private sector funding in agriculture. Policies considering the complexity of the sectors were also suggested in Casale through supply chain creation and support (also through product valorisation and public sensitisation). In Amalie was stressed that effective support should be both financial (for the adopters of CFPs) and legislative. It is worth recalling here that, in this workshop, emphasis was put on the creation of consensus about policies (that should be based on education).

It was recognised by the reviewers also the importance of factor #108, which stresses that **policies should consider geographical variability**. One reviewer stressed that there is a need for flexibility that allows local conditions to be taken into account. Another one said that this is relevant for all land use and landscapes, but especially those having a low carbon sequestration potential (such as Mediterranean rainfed cropping systems). In various workshops the issue of variability of pedoclimatic conditions emerged and has been commented on elsewhere in the text. Anyhow, in Madrid was stressed that the variability increases costs of MRV.

B.7. Differences in impacts across biophysical environment (geographical, temporal) and evaluation of farmers

The adoption of certain CFPs depends on the availability of services as well as on the specificity of the places and landscapes, farms and farming systems, and the aptitudes developed by farmers in those places.

The factors under this category have been distributed under two subcategories.

a. Proximity to agricultural services

The distance of farms from services is a factor that, in general, impacts negatively on the adoption of new agricultural technologies and – as it was recognised by the reviewers – also on CFPs. It should be noted that some reviewers stressed that this factor's impact concerns remote areas that, in Europe, are not the rules.

Forms of factors in subcategory 7.a

#	Name of non-CF-related factors (initially)		
#110	Distance of the farm from services Accessibility of extension services impacts on the adoption of new farming practices It is an aspect of geographical dimension of diffusion of technology.	Factor effects	Hindering
		Knowledge	Known
		Relevance to CF	Very relevant
		Corroborated	Yes

b. Agricultural practices are affected by the characteristics of location and the farming systems

The geographical variability of soils and the conditions for farming are crucial aspects of the promotion of CFPs. Such variability is particularly important also from a strictly technical point of view (as commented above, see factors #108) In this sub-category, we focus the attention mostly on the relation between how farming activities are implemented and the geographical location of businesses.

Forms of factors in subcategory 7.b

#	Name of the CF-Related-factor		
#111	Temporal variability of reducing nitrogen application The effectiveness of the reduction of the application of nitrogen changes according to the climate condition of each year.	Factor effects	Hindering
		Knowledge	Known
		Relevance	Very relevant
		Corroborated	Yes
#112	Certain practices are most fit for certain geographical sites Certain practices are more suited to specific geographical sites (e.g., some very fertile land could be removed from production ²¹ ; sandy lands are not fit for certain practices). Certain practices are valuable only with certain temperatures. The systems of incentives and the promotion should change accordingly.	Factor effects	It depends
		Knowledge	Well-known
		Relevance	Very relevant
		Corroborated	Yes

²¹ Some CFPs imply the reduction of land used, as in the case of rotation

#	Name of non-CF-related factors (initially)		
#113	Certain farm types are more suited to certain practices Farm types are relevant for favouring certain conservation activities (e.g., livestock practicing farm vs cropping)	Factor effects	It depends
		Knowledge	Well-known
		Relevance to CF	Very relevant
		Corroborated	Yes
#114	Attitudes change according to agro-systems being practiced In different locations and with different agricultural practices and mixes of practices, the orientation to adopting conservation practices change	Factor effects	It depends
		Knowledge	Known
		Relevance to CF	Relevant
		Corroborated	Yes

Factor #111 on “Temporal variability of reducing nitrogen application” was corroborated by most of the reviewers. There were few comments: one stressed that some member states are working on new rules on the matter and another one observed that there is a problem – especially in the Mediterranean regions – due to the dramatic meteorological changes. The issue was not commented on in the workshops.

Factor #112 reads that “Certain practices are most fit for certain geographical sites”. There was a general agreement among the reviewers on this factor. Several considerations done during the workshops are relevant. In Dorinne, for example, it was stressed that the heterogeneity of agricultural ecosystems makes certain practices beneficial in certain areas and detrimental in others. Similarly, in Madrid emerged that there are difficulties in the complete implementation of CFPs in Mediterranean semi-arid rainfed cereal cropping systems. In Amalie, it emerged the need to develop plans with methodology and strategies that are appropriate to individual areas (which have different needs and characteristics). In Dorinne was indicated, as a barrier, the fact that policies and models must consider the unpredictability of climate change and variability of local ecosystems.

In Dorinne, one comment was that local conditions are not flexible, and this represents a problem for CFPs promotion also because, as was stressed on various occasions, the potential for sequestration changes in different geographical and soil contexts. In Madrid, for example, was stressed that there is soil variability for what concerns SOC and this creates difficulties in estimating short-term changes or that Mediterranean cropping systems sequester carbon slowly (VCM project promoters would focus on northern regions).

The general statement that “Certain farm types are more suited to certain practices” (factor #113) was considered relevant to CF by the reviewers. Some of their comments on the matter were focused on the idea that measures targeted to different type of farming systems could be more effective. Beyond the direct connection between individual farming systems with specific practices, it was suggested that what is important for the transition to CF is appropriate territorial management and the size of farms. A real impact can be achieved only based on a territorial vision (this was also stressed in the Madrid workshop).

The general principle implied by factor #114 “Attitudes changes according to agro-systems being practiced” was considered relevant also for the implementation of CF. Not many comments were provided by the reviewers, but one said that “local conditions must be considered because it will suggest the best practice to implement”.

B.8. Time and risk preferences

A relevant aspect of the adoption of new technologies and new practices in agriculture is the time orientation of the relevant actors because, in general, innovations imply an orientation to the future and some form of planning, including those connected to carbon farming. Among the factors covered by this category, we found two sub-categories. The factors will be presented according to them.

a. Land Tenure and succession

The first sub-category concerns land tenure and succession, which affect the time horizon of land property and, consequently, the willingness of actors to invest in the light of a future reward.

Forms of factors in subcategory 8.a

#	Name of the CF-Related-factor		
#115	Tenure security is connected to land tenure Tenure security is considered a factor facilitating Tech Change. Farmers having security for a long term in their land are more willing to invest in practices that have long lifetime such as planting tree, peatland restoration.	Factor effects	Facilitating
		Knowledge	Well-known
		Relevance	Very relevant
		Corroborated	Yes
#	Name of non-CF-related factors (initially)		
#116	Succession and farm structure are relevant for decisions concerning new technologies Succession and farm structure impact land tenure, including fragmentation of properties, dimension of farms, time-horizon of property. They are factors that impact on decisions concerning the introduction of new practices.	Factor effects	It depends
		Knowledge	Known
		Relevance to CF	Very relevant
		Corroborated	Yes
#117	Principal agent issues Principal-agent issues such as landowners refusing efficient technologies for tenant farmers can also be identified.	Factor effects	Hindering
		Knowledge	Known
		Relevance to CF	Relevant
		Corroborated	Yes

Factor #115 on **tenure security** was corroborated by the reviewers. One commented that, notwithstanding its importance, what is more relevant for taking the risk of adopting CFPs and maintaining them in time is the prospective increase in the value of the product. The issue of time is confirmed crucial by two other reviewers: they stressed that land tenure security is particularly relevant for those types of land use that imply longer cycles of investment and exploitation, such as those that foresee rewetting and restoring of peatlands and wetlands, or reforestation to increase biodiversity. In Madrid, for example, the issue was raised about the uncertainty regarding the permanence of CFPs in the “agroforestry system of dehesa”.

Factor #116 on “**Succession and farm structure** are relevant for decisions concerning new technologies” was recognised as impacting also on decisions concerning CF. One reviewer commented that the decisions of older farmers to invest in CF depend on the willingness of heirs to take over. Other reviewers stressed the importance of a long-time frame for investment, which includes security of tenure. One reviewer connected this factor to farm size (the greater it is, the more likely are investments) and this orientation was raised in Milan (i.e., the fragmented structure of property of land). In Madrid was stressed that all the dehesas are privately owned and problems emerge for investment

in new practices and an issue is the lack of commitment to maintaining the (new) practice. In Dorinne it was commented that a factor impacting the structure of farms is the pressure on the land tenure system connected to the increase in land prices.

Factor #117, on “Principal agent issues” was corroborated by the reviewers. One comment was that it is especially relevant for CFP based on significant changes in land use, such as agroforestry or paludiculture. Another reviewer was more sceptical, considering that landowners in general would refuse new technologies except if it would devalue their land (but CF farming practices basically add value).

b. Risks and uncertainty

The second sub-category includes factors such as the willingness to take risks, or the specific orientation to the future of the actors. It entails also access to credit (i.e., the typical way in which future-oriented actions are managed in any economic systems) and the certainty of policies (i.e., how much policies are adequate to the need of actors in agriculture to operate in a stable context).

Forms of factors in subcategory 8.b

#	Name of the CF-Related-factor		
#118	Access to credit favours adoption The adoption of climate-friendly measures that imply investments depends on the availability of credit and, in general, of cash.	Factor effects	Facilitating
		Knowledge	Well-known
		Relevance	Very relevant
		Corroborated	Yes
#119	Policy Uncertainty reduces adoption The risk that policy toward Carbon Sequestration changes reduces adoption. This risk is relevant for non-market schemes, that are based on rewards for farming but could be generalised to any regulatory scheme related to carbon farming.	Factor effects	Hindering
		Knowledge	Well-known
		Relevance	Relevant
		Corroborated	Yes
#	Name of non-CF-related factors (initially)		
#120	Willingness to take risks favours adoption Willingness to take on the risks associated with the investment in new agricultural practices is a crucial factor (vs risk aversion).	Factor effects	Facilitating
		Knowledge	Well-known
		Relevance to CF	Very relevant
		Corroborated	Yes
#121	Time preference (vs short-termism) Farmers (and investors in general) are not positive toward waiting for the results of the new practices.	Factor effects	Hindering
		Knowledge	Well-known
		Relevance to CF	Very relevant
		Corroborated	Yes

The two factors #118 and #119 were both corroborated by the reviewers and could be considered very “standard” when talking of innovation. Among the comments, some referred to credit, which is all the more important the larger the investment. As for factor #119, on policy uncertainty, one reviewer stressed the need for policy coherence also aimed at ensuring strong support across the political spectrum. In this framework, was also stressed that the actors of the agrifood sectors are crucial for the adoption of CFPs or Sustainable Practices.

Also factors #120 and #121 could be considered as “standard” when talking of innovation although they were not found explicitly related to CFPs. The reviewers corroborated them. The willingness to take risk (#120) was considered at the origin of innovation and – although it was considered a peculiar actors' attitude, could be fostered through specific policies aimed at mitigating the perceived risks (e.g., promoting the increase of farm size or farm aggregations, supporting the value of products, keeping policy coherence and stability, and promoting access to credit). As for factor #121, about time preference, notwithstanding that farmers are somehow used to the long-time frame of investments (e.g., in agroforestry), their concerns about short-term productivity, which should not be affected, should be taken into account also because – as stressed in Madrid – exploitations are planned in shorter times compared to the 5-10 implied by CF.

B.9. Externalities and spillovers

New agricultural practices, including those connected to carbon farming, produce effects also on people not adopting them. Such impacts could foster or hamper, somehow, their further adoption by new actors. So far, we found only two factors but, of course, there could be more.

Forms of the factors of the category 9

#	Name of the CF-Related-factor		
#122	Negative externalities of climate action If carbon farming schemes and climate actions are compartmentalised and other impacts are not considered, negative externalities could emerge (e.g., loss of biodiversity of loss of jobs at the local level) bringing about an overall decrease of social benefits and even impacts on climate.	Factor effects	Hindering
		Knowledge	Well-known
		Relevance	Very relevant
		Corroborated	Yes
#	Name of non-CF-related factors (initially)		
#123	Spatial spillover Positive impacts of practices extend beyond the individual plot to neighbouring ones.	Factor effects	Facilitating
		Knowledge	Well-known
		Relevance to CF	Relevant
		Corroborated	Yes

Factor #122 deals with the issue of negative externalities. The reviewers considered it very important. Their few comments were, on the other hand, focused on the “opposite” side: farmers’ gains from CF will come from the co-benefits it produces and consequently – another reviewer said – social, economic, and environmental aspects related to the implementation of CFPs must be assessed holistically. The importance of externalities for CF was raised in various workshops, for example indicating positive social benefits concerning the mitigation of extreme climate events, support of biodiversity, diversity within landscapes (Amalie, Casale, Milan). The need to improve the monitoring of these externalities (both positive and negative) was raised in Dorinne.

Spatial spillover is a facilitating factor (#123) that was considered by the reviewers relevant also for CF. Their comments were focused on the social context in which innovation activities aimed at practicing CF: it was stressed, for example, that farmers learn from each other; that positive and negative effects of innovation do not affect just individual businesses but also those of neighbours, and so on. It was suggested that CFP should be implemented at the territorial level. In the Madrid workshop, in relation to the “dehesa system”, was singled out the opportunity to create efficient owner associations.

B.10. Habits (including consumers' ones) / Resilience of existing organisational arrangements

The actors that could adopt new CFP and/or enter the VCM have their own habits, and they could be reluctant to change them. Such factors are very diverse, and no sub-typology has been proposed. In general, their common trait is that how things are being done by the actors in agriculture (e.g., certain practices, certain expectations) does not change easily. In general, this tends to be connected to “mentality” and factors of this kind are mostly cognitive.

Forms of the factors of the category 10

#	Name of the CF-Related-factor		
#124	<p style="text-align: center;">Compatibility of Sustainable Agriculture Practice/Attachment to old practices</p> <p>The degree to which an innovation is perceived as consistent with the existing values, past experiences, and needs of the potential adopters. Favourable attitudes toward compatibility might influence positively the adoption of SAP.</p>	Factor effects	Hindering
		Knowledge	Well-known
		Relevance	Relevant
		Corroborated	Yes
#125	<p style="text-align: center;">Age of farmers affects attitude to change</p> <p>Age of farmers could affect the level of information about new technologies and implies planning horizon and different working experience. All these aspects of age could impact differently the orientation to change. There is no unambiguous evidence on the matter.</p>	Factor effects	Hindering
		Knowledge	Well-known
		Relevance	Relevant
		Corroborated	Yes
#126	<p style="text-align: center;">Difficulties in cooperation</p> <p>Cooperation between farmers is difficult to achieve, even if it helps in implementing the investments needed to promote adoption.</p>	Factor effects	Hindering
		Knowledge	Known
		Relevance	Relevant
		Corroborated	Yes
#127	<p style="text-align: center;">Farming vs forestry</p> <p>Farmers in many countries tend to have a negative attitude towards woodland planting; Agro-forestry implies significant overall changes hampering the adoption including the permanent nature of the change, significant shift in the farming systems with legal and economic implications and uncertainty for farmers. There could be a perceived loss of autonomy of farmers once they are told where to plant trees.</p>	Factor effects	Hindering
		Knowledge	Known
		Relevance	Relevant
		Corroborated	Yes
#128	<p style="text-align: center;">Consumer habits and expectations</p> <p>Cultural barriers linked to consumer habits and expectations could impact the ways farmers approach innovation.</p>	Factor effects	It depends
		Knowledge	Known
		Relevance to CF	Very relevant
		Corroborated	Yes
#129	<p style="text-align: center;">Opposition to specific practices by professionals</p> <p>There are some practices that are not approved by particular categories of professionals as in the case of the opposition of veterinaries to Feeding ionophores/probiotics to livestock.</p>	Factor effects	Hindering
		Knowledge	Little known
		Relevance to CF	Little relevant
		Corroborated	No

Factor #124 on “Compatibility of Sustainable Agriculture Practice/Attachment to old practices” was corroborated by the reviewers. Many of them also said that it is something relevant for all land uses. From the workshops emerged indications about the value and the connected roles that farmers tend to consider as appropriate to their mission. In Dorinne, for example, when discussing the appropriate targets in terms of carbon sequestration, was questioned if the role of agriculture is reaching that type of target. This could be connected to the big divide that is felt in agriculture, between rural and urban areas. In a certain sense, it could be argued that carbon storage is perceived as an objective primarily associated with urban areas. In Madrid was suggested that farmers perceive the scope of CFPs as mainly focused on environmental issues – the provision of ecosystem services – which is far beyond their traditional responsibility of providing food (this emerged specifically when talking of cereal cropping systems but can be easily generalised). Also in Madrid, it was suggested that it is such an attitude – the focus on CF and not on production – that helps explain their low interest in VCMs.

Factor #125, according to which the “Age of farmers affects the attitude to change” was corroborated and, indeed, emerged several times also in the discussion of other factors. The idea is that older farmers are less interested in initiatives to be deployed in the longer term, unless other factors are at work, such as the succession path (see above, discussion of factor #116, sub-category 8a). In Madrid, was stressed that, in general, old farmers are less prone than younger ones (and women, see below). This was also said during the workshop in Casale.

Difficulties of cooperation (factor #126) were considered by the reviewers as possibly impacting CFPs uptake. Comments were interesting. One reviewer suggested that cooperatives are useful but require time, especially because of the need to build trust. Another one stressed that cooperation is needed since, even if CFPs are known, their adaptation to local conditions requires farmers' expertise, trials in their exploitations and peer-to-peer cooperation and exchange of knowledge. It was stressed by another reviewer that cooperation is needed for practices where neighbours are affected, such as paludiculture or –another reviewer said – which might require sharing of equipment (e.g., no-till). This resonates with what was stressed in Dorinne: in relation to the participation in certification schemes (European, National or regional), it was indicated the risk felt by farmers of losing their decision-making autonomy. In that occasion the possible limitations were those due to pressures by buyers (i.e., a type of actor to possibly cooperate with) or to market pressures. The potential benefits of cooperation between farms were also reminded in Milan.

Factor #127, on the divide “Farming vs forestry” was corroborated by the reviewers, even if some of them did not agree that it represents an issue. The problem would arise only when contrasts with alternative uses of land. The issue was at the centre of the workshop in Casale. In the discussion, issues were raised concerning a sort of “cultural conflict” between agriculture and forestry – being the two things, traditionally seen as conflicting (to the point that certain types of plants have a sort of bad reputation). Connected obstacles were the overall lack of awareness of farmers about forestry and its possible economic benefits and, lack of competencies about the issue of both farmers and the public officers.

Factor #128 on “consumer habits and expectations” was accepted by the reviewers as potentially impacting CFP adoption. The issue is how big is the appeal for consumers to buy sustainable products or products that have certain characteristics. The challenge is the price level – CF could imply rising costs, at least in the short term – in a context in which consumers are sometimes used to prefer low-cost products (the issue was also discussed in relation to factor #18). Therefore, the orientation of consumers creates expectations for producers that could be adverse to the adoption of CFPs. On the other hand, some reviewers observed, the issue of the quality of goods is becoming more and more important (attention to diets, including for religious reasons). Therefore, consumer orientation is a factor that should be taken into account and managed properly (and could represent, depending on the context, both a facilitating and a hindering factor).

Factor #129 was not corroborated by the reviewers.

B.11. Access to/Lack of basic Infrastructures and Technologies

New agricultural practices in many cases need specific infrastructures or access to dedicated technologies (including IT) as well as complementary inputs. The lack of such access or availability represents an obstacle to the adoption of CFP or to entering the VCM.

Forms of the factors of the category 11

#	Name of non-CF-related factors (initially)		
#130	<p>Lack of infrastructure and complementary inputs are necessary</p> <p>Implementing changes and adopting climate-friendly agriculture measures need, in many situations, dedicated infrastructures. The lack of such infrastructure is a barrier to the adoption of new practices.</p>	Factor effects	Hindering
		Knowledge	Known
		Relevance to CF	Very relevant
		Corroborated	Yes
#131	<p>Internet access</p> <p>Technological infrastructures such as the internet (and the access to it) can support BMP adoption.</p>	Factor effects	Facilitating
		Knowledge	Known
		Relevance to CF	Relevant
		Corroborated	Yes
#132	<p>Accessibility of necessary technology</p> <p>The existence and accessibility to the necessary technology for the adoption of new agricultural practice is a facilitating factor.</p>	Factor effects	Facilitating
		Knowledge	Known
		Relevance to CF	Very relevant
		Corroborated	Yes

These three factors were not indicated in the consulted literature as related to CF. The reviewers concluded that all of them are actually relevant to CF. The comments they provided were interesting, but we think it is better to present them altogether since the considerations done by the reviewers are relevant for the entire category 11. In general, infrastructures (factor #130) could be relevant for some specific CFPs (e.g., precision farming) and especially in light of the need to account for carbon sequestration. Similarly, an infrastructure such as the internet (factor #131) is very important, especially for many activities connected to MRV (including sensors). In general, internet access is not a problem in Europe, but there could be connectivity problems in remote areas. Access to specific technologies (factor #132) is important for CF. The problem is, as for investments in general, the capacity to invest of individual firms. Someone stressed that, in light of this, the size of farm is important since many of them have not enough economic power.

12. Gendered different behaviour

Gender could impact the adoption of new technologies in agriculture as well as the beginning of new ventures (such as entering VCM). Not many references have been found on this connection, but it could be assumed that gender is a relevant factor by generalising a connection that works in non-European regions and in domains beyond that of carbon farming.

Forms of the factors of the category 12

#	Name of non-CF-related factors (initially)		
#133	Genderised communication Genderised communication about the advantages of new practices has been found relevant for women.	Factor effects	Facilitating
		Knowledge	Little known
		Relevance to CF	Relevant
		Corroborated	No
#134	Women more likely adopt new practices Some studies found that in some countries, women more likely adopt new practices, notwithstanding – on the average – a lower level of knowledge about certain technologies.	Factor effects	Facilitating
		Knowledge	Little known
		Relevance to CF	Very relevant
		Corroborated	Yes

The factors under this category were not connected to CF. The first one “genderised communication” (#133) was not corroborated by the review. The second one, concerning the role of women in adopting new practices, including CFPs, was recognised as relevant. The issue has to do – according to a reviewer – with the role of women in the decision-making process within farms, which is rarely crucial, for cultural reasons. It emerged clearly in the Madrid workshop, where a large farmer organisation indicated that women were more open to the adoption of innovations. In this sense, the role of women is similar to that of younger farmers. In the informal exchanges had during the workshop in Casale, the comment was that women represent a growing component of the agricultural sector. It would be part of the natural renewal process of farms: as long as youngsters take over a growing percentage of the new cohort of farmers is composed by women.

Section C – Conclusions

1. Some final considerations

The validation process, whose characteristics and results have been presented in the previous chapters, allowed us to refine the initial Map of factors. The resulting list of 127 confirmed factors, organised into 12 categories, is presented in the table below. For each listed factor, the progressive number of the final map is given (first column), followed by the title of the factor and, in brackets, the reference number in the initial map (second column), and finally, the sub-category to which it belongs (third column).

Table 8 – The Final map

No.	Title	Subcat
Category 1 – Costs and benefits of Carbon Farming practices		
1	Financial constraints (due also to equipment costs of establishment (#1)	1a
2	Opportunity costs of soil carbon sequestration practices (#2)	1a
3	Learning costs (#3)	1a
4	Reduction of operational cost is an important aspect of the new practices (#5)	1a
5	Maintenance costs of new practices could impact adoption (#4)	1a
6	Agro-forestry is labour-intensive (#6)	1a
7	Government subsidies (#7)	1b
8	Financial incentives (#8)	1b
9	Profitability of new practices (#9)	1c
10	Certain carbon sequestration practices diminish yields (#10)	1c
11	Some practices Increase yields in the long term (#11)	1c
12	Combination of multiple practices (#12)	1d
13	Co-benefits of Carbon farming affect the adoption (#13)	1d
14	Uncertainty about the results of introducing Soil Carbon Management Practices (#14)	1d
15	Improving fertilisation efficiency indirectly reduces emissions of CO2 (#15)	1d
16	Farmers face competing pressures (#16)	1d
17	Unequal distribution of costs/benefits across supply chains (#17)	1d
18	Consumers' willingness to pay for sustainable products is not certain (#18)	1e
19	The organisation of industrial sectors and value chain affect adoption of climate-friendly measures (#19)	1e
20	Farmers' wealth/firm size and property impact adoption (#20)	1f
Category 2 – VCM and innovative practices		
21	Price structure impacts decision (#22)	2a
22	Possible competition between farmers in higher and lower income countries (#23)	2a
23	Averse attitude towards data publishing (#24)	2a
24	Off-farm income (#20)	2a
25	Unintended effect of incentives (crowd out effect) (#25)	2a
26	Risk of Double funding (#26)	2b
27	Potential lack of demand for Carbon credits (#27)	2b
28	Cyclicity of demand for agricultural credits disincentives CF practices (#30)	2b
29	Uncertainty about the price of carbon hinders the adoption of carbon farming practices (#31)	2b
30	Credibility of credit markets/Quality of carbon credits/Accountability of reporting (#32)	2b
31	Competition between providers of carbon credits not in agriculture (#33)	2b
32	Carbon storage reversal/ Credit reversal are a liability (#34)	2b
33	High costs for results-based schemes/MRV-Increased transaction Costs (#35)	2c

No.	Title	Subcat
34	Lack of transparency in the price discovery mechanism (#36)	2c
	Category 3 – Orientation towards the environment and drive for change	
35	Demonstration: Farmers evaluation of neighbour agricultural practices impacts on adoption (#37)	3a
36	Acceptance and support from neighbours/pressure from significant others (#38)	3a
37	Knowledge brokers are crucial for promoting innovation (#39)	3a
38	Importance of knowledge networks (#40)	3a
39	Farmers' beliefs on climate change/environmental stewardship (#41)	3b
40	Political views about the role of the state (#42)	3b
41	Increase of land aesthetic value (#43)	3b
42	Lack of skill and knowledge among farmers (#44)	3c
43	Awareness of observable phenomena of climate change/Environmental consciousness (#45)	3c
44	Awareness and understanding of Carbon Farming related policy framework do not increase related practices (#46)	3c
45	Information about the benefits of Conservation practices impacts positively adoption (#47)	3c
46	Attitudes towards Carbon Farming change according to the type of farm (#48)	3d
47	Relative advantage of sustainable practices in agriculture (#49)	3d
48	Farmers' resentment about land cost and conservation policy (#50)	3d
49	Prejudice about certain practices may hamper adoption (#51)	3d
50	Exposure to climate change impacts increases willingness to innovate for conservation (#52)	3d
51	Self-efficacy facilitates the adoption of LEAP (Low Emission Agricultural Practices) (#53)	3d
52	Positive attitude towards specific practices (#54)	3d
53	Temporal spillover (#55)	3d
54	Perception of market practices (and of the behaviour of other actors) (#56)	3d
55	Non-monetary drivers are more important than monetary motivation to join programs (#57)	3e
56	The opportunity to participate in carbon credit markets is not a relevant driver of carbon farming practices (#58)	3e
57	Irrational motivations behind the choice of innovating (#59)	3e
58	Perception of the effectiveness of the new practices (#60)	3e
59	Emotional attachment to land could hamper relocation (#61)	3e
	Category 4 – Technological and operational complexity of innovation	
60	Soil organic carbon content of Mediterranean soils changes relatively slowly (#62)	4a
61	Timing of payment (before or after sequestration) (#63)	4a
62	Slowness of technological innovation in agriculture (#64)	4a
63	Difficulty in integrating GHG impacts into national GHG inventories (#65)	4b
64	Control systems are not effective (#66)	4b
65	Permanent grassland has physical constraints (#67)	4b
66	Some practices diffuse contaminants (#68)	4b
67	R&D can reduce the uncertainty of MRV that hampers the adoption of carbon farming practices (#69)	4b
68	Carbon leakage could diminish sequestration (#70)	4b
69	Technological trade-offs could offset the positive impacts of new practices (#71)	4b
70	Technical uncertainties/Lack of verified impact of technologies (#72)	4b
71	Leakage of emissions within farms undermines additionality (#73)	4b
72	The complexity and uncertainty of Market-based schemes of carbon soil certification (#74)	4b
73	Lack of institutional capacity at the national and regional level (#75)	4b

No.	Title	Subcat
74	New agricultural practices imply more organisational complexity (#76)	4b
75	New technologies are complex (#77)	4b
76	Availability and readiness of animal manure (#78)	4b
77	Neglect of stakeholders in project design of sinking carbon (#79)	4c
78	Technologies are not fit for local farmers' needs (#80)	4c
	Category 5 – Role of advisory, information and training services, soil illiteracy	
79	Communication barriers toward consumers (#81)	5a
80	Trial of new practices is not easy (#83)	5a
81	Scarce observability of impacts (#84)	5a
82	Difficulties for technology providers in reaching customers (#85)	5a
83	Lack of knowledge of certain practices (CC, manure, etc.) (#86)	5b
84	Advisor services (and quality) help adoption (#87)	5b
85	Lack of a widely agreed definition for soil health as a novel concept (#88)	5b
86	Training needs for precision farming (#89)	5b
87	Alliances of advisors (#90)	5b
88	Knowledge gap on soil health (#92)	5b
89	Education and training favour the adoption (#93)	5c
90	Credibility of advisors (#94)	5c
91	Organisational weaknesses of public Soil Health Management advice services (#95)	5c
92	No-segmentation of information provision services (#96)	5c
93	Fragmentation of Advisory services for Agriculture (#97)	5c
	Category 6 – Policies and regulation	
94	Current rules sometimes prevent the adoption of innovation for Soil Carbon Management Practices (#98)	6a
95	Inconsistencies between different regulations (#99)	6a
96	Barriers to certification hamper markets from working well (#100)	6a
97	Effective standards promote the adoption/ Lack of a solid monitoring scheme (#101)	6b
98	Lack of data at the local level (#103)	6b
99	Uncertainty over credit ownership for regulators/administrators (#104)	6b
100	Carbon Audit tools can be manipulated (#105)	6b
101	Multiple and contradictory policy goals/unintended effects of policies (#106)	6c
102	Policy mix (#107)	6c
103	Policies should consider geographical variability (#108)	6c
104	Policies are crucial for agriculture (#109)	6c
	Category 7 – Differences in impacts across biophysical environment (geographical, temporal) and evaluation of farmers	
105	Distance of the farm from services (#1010)	7a
106	Temporal variability of reducing nitrogen application (#111)	7b
107	Certain practices are most fit for certain geographical sites (#112)	7b
108	Certain farm types are more suited to certain practices (#113)	7b
109	Attitudes changes according to agro-systems being practiced (#114)	7b
	Category 8 – Time and risk preferences	
110	Tenure security is connected to land tenure (#115)	8a
111	Succession and farm structure are relevant for decisions concerning new technologies (#116)	8a
112	Principal agent issues (#117)	8a
113	Access to credit favours adoption (#118)	8b
114	Policy Uncertainty reduces adoption (#119)	8b
115	Willingness to take risks favours adoption (#120)	8b
116	Time preference (vs short-termism) (#121)	8b
	Category 9 – Externalities and spillovers	

No.	Title	Subcat
117	Negative externalities of climate action (#122)	
118	Spatial spillover (#123)	
	Category 10 – Habits (including consumers' ones) / Resilience of existing organisational arrangements	
119	Compatibility of Sustainable Agriculture Practice/Attachment to old practices (#124)	
120	Age of farmers affects attitude to change (#125)	
121	Difficulties in cooperation (#126)	
122	Farming vs forestry (#127)	
123	Consumer habits and expectations (#128)	
	Category 11 – Access/Lack of basic Infrastructures and technologies	
124	Lack of infrastructure and complementary inputs are necessary (#130)	
125	Internet access (#131)	
126	Accessibility of necessary technology (#132)	
	Category 12 – Gendered different behaviour	
127	Women more likely adopt new practices (#134)	

As mentioned above, the forms containing all 134 initial factors, with their description and a synthesis of the information and comments provided by the 16 reviewers, are presented in Annex 1 instead.

It is worth stressing that, after the process, the distinction between CF-related factors and non-CF-related ones is not valid anymore, since all the corroborated factors should be considered relevant for the promotion of CF. This is somehow a step forward that was made possible through the validation process: some knowledge that was not connected (by the scientific community or the practitioners) to CF could be used also in this domain. In a certain sense, the capacity to act more effectively – in principle – has grown, at least a little bit.

The existing Map is a resource that can be applied to multiple applications. First of all, it is a tool that could be used for the continuation of the MRV4SOC project, particularly for devising the policy guidelines foreseen in WP5. In this framework, the Map will be useful for those who are involved in defining and promoting policies and, in general, initiatives aimed at promoting CF and establishing effective VCMs. In this sense, the Map will be useful also for local actors who could complement the information contained in the Map with those coming from their specific knowledge and experience of local agricultural systems.

The validation process has made it possible to draw some suggestions. Some of them have more the characteristics of thoughts emerged from the comprehensive reading of the comments and information provided by the reviewers or during the workshops. They could be presented in the form of some general remarks. They could be summarised in the following way.

- The first remark is that the promotion of CF and VCMs should be thought of as a deep innovation process that has **not only a technical but also a social aspect**. They should be considered simultaneously and given equal weight when designing policy interventions, or else the policies themselves will lose their effectiveness. A clear example is that the conditions to practice CF change according to the regions (there are various factors on this). Nevertheless, it should be considered that each region or locality has its own peculiar social and economic traits, which should be fully considered. This holds for many relevant factors, for example land tenure, that changes according to places, or demographic dynamics.
- The second remark stems from the first one. The innovation process connected to CF and VCM means implies a **wide array of social and economic actors**, not just farmers and technical support. The so-called Quadruple Helix approach could be of help, which states that innovation is the result of the interaction of four societal sectors: research, public administration, industry, and civil society

(to address the knowledge gap, to coordinate the changing agricultural policies with other policies, to involve industrial actors and consumers, etc.). Among other things, what is needed is sharing widely among these actors a new vision about agriculture, its role for producing diverse ecosystem services and so on.

- The third remark concerns the agricultural sector, which is called to manage an open and complex change process that takes place in the long period, whose impacts are not all clear and should be managed. Therefore, it implies learning by farmers as well as the other actors of the agricultural context, monitoring of the effects of the policies, the correction of the possible errors, considering the issue of compensation for adverse effects of the participation in VCMs on farmers, and so on. In this framework, it is crucial the promotion and management of **consensus among the various stakeholders**. This is particularly important especially because of the centrality of public policies for agriculture. In this framework, emerge as particularly important the previous experiences of the sector' actors, especially the farmers, and the ideas and perceptions they have of such policies and innovation. Finally, also in light of the long term implied, it is crucial that policies guiding this transition are kept for all the time is needed.

Apart from these general remarks, it should be stressed that **most of the suggestions** about the promotion of CF and VCMs emerged directly from the workshops themselves, where it was possible to discuss with the participants their specific points of view about how to better implement this type of policy. They are reported in the following paragraph.

2. Policy suggestions emerged from the validation process

Based on the discussion held during the workshop, it is possible to single out a list of suggestions concerning how to promote CF and VCMs. The definition of this list was informed by the results of discussions predominantly focused on the barriers and facilitating factors for CFPs and VCMs, and as such, it is shaped by the conclusions drawn from that debate.

Table 9 – List of Policy suggestions

	TYPE OF SUGGESTION	SPECIFIC SUGGESTIONS
A.	CF and VCM Mechanisms that are implementable	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Simple sequestration schemes 2. Harmonise schemes and other regulations (consistency) 3. Risk of frauds and/or greenwashing; transparency of the system
B.	Work on how CF produces beneficial effects	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Recognising the general benefits of CF on the Ecosystem 2. Promote the maintenance of sequestered carbon and not just incremental carbon sequestration 3. Land with different sequestration potentials or carbon saturation levels 4. Fair remuneration and distribution of roles of participants
C.	The promotion of CF is a complex process	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Involvement of various stakeholders in the promotion of CF 2. The adoption of CFPs should be promoted on a consensual basis
D.	Promoting research	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Knowledge should be continuously updated 2. MRV systems should be continuously improved

	TYPE OF SUGGESTION	SPECIFIC SUGGESTIONS
E.	Provision of continuing assistance to the actors involved in CF and VCM	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Training for Farmers. 2. Training for advisors. 3. Services for CF and VCM

Below is a brief description of these proposals, based on their classification.

A. CF and VCM mechanisms that are implementable

The first type of suggestions concerns the prescription of the policies for promoting CF and establishing VCMs.

A.1. Simple sequestration schemes

In almost all the workshops it was stressed that the frameworks in which such policies for CF and VCM are implemented should be simple and robust to reduce the administrative burden of the participants (farmers as well as buyers of credits). Simplicity, in particular, was stressed several times (e.g., through simple online platforms, clear pathways for accreditation). In this context, it was also suggested the opportunity and the need to develop simple MRV technologies.

A.2. Harmonise schemes and other relevant regulations (consistency)

During the workshops, comments were done on the pros and cons of possible European-wide or regional certification frameworks. In general, it emerged that if they would make the Carbon market more reliable with standardised procedures, they would increase the participation of farmers, and, eventually, consumers' trust. Of course, the risk of non-uniformity of control is there and properly trained certification bodies are needed. In this framework, it was suggested that the regulation to promote CF and various forms of reward for carbon sequestration – including VCMs – should not create discrimination among farmers in different regions and be clear and transparent at the European level. Particularly, certification frameworks should be consistent with the other policies and should not contradict other relevant regulations.

A.3. Risk of frauds and/or greenwashing: transparency of the system

In the discussions, it became clear that rewarding CFPs through MRV and VCM methodologies could be a non-completely transparent process. Furthermore, it was indicated that there is a risk of people benefiting from fraud when participating in the schemes for rewarding CFPs as well as greenwashing. Some stressed the possible conflict of interest between credit sellers and buyers. All these risks should be addressed properly.

B. Work on how CF and VCMs produce beneficial effects

CFPs and VCMs are aimed at bringing about beneficial effects for both participants and society. Nevertheless, how these benefits are produced, distributed and maintained over time cannot be taken for granted. During the workshops, some suggestions emerged on the matter.

B.1. Recognising the general benefits of CF on the Ecosystem

CFPs produce environmental benefits that go beyond solely carbon storage. In various workshops was stressed that such (further) ecosystem services should be recognised, and the related financial rewards should be given to those who adopt CFPs.

B.2. Promote the maintenance of carbon sequestered and not just incremental carbon sequestration

One central issue of carbon sequestration in agriculture concerns the distinction between the flow of newly sequestered carbon and the stock of sequestered carbon. Payments should be devoted to the activities needed to maintain over time the stock of carbon in the soil over time and, consequently, find effective ways to remunerate them (incentives for the two things could be different). In this framework, it was also stressed that funding policies should be changed so that public funding should go to launching the CFPs, while private funding – through the carbon market – should integrate the funds available for the maintenance phase.

Furthermore, it was stressed that payments to those who practice CF should be aimed also at rewarding the production of the other co-benefits of CF (someone stressed that the true economic advantage of CFPs does not come from the possible sale of carbon credits).

B.3. Land with different sequestration potentials or carbon saturation levels

Another aspect of CF is that its results change significantly according to the condition of land, climate, and, in general, regional characteristics. This implies that land has different sequestration potential. During the workshops the issue was raised and, according to some, the price of carbon should factor in the different potentials of different geographical areas.

A connected issue is that of the carbon saturation level of land. Due to the existing sequestration limits, those farmers who have already practiced CF in the past should not be left behind by new schemes. Coordination with preceding policies should be considered.

B.4. Fair remuneration and distribution of roles of participants

A general suggestion arising from the workshops was that of promoting a fair remuneration of farmers participating in VCMs, especially in light of the need to compensate for the likely decrease in market competitiveness, at least in the short term. The principle of CF policies should be that those who practice CF gain in doing so and, to this end, resources from various sources to incentivise CFPs should be made available.

In light of the production of public goods connected to CF, it was suggested that the European Carbon market scheme should be under the control of the public administration, including the registry of projects and the system for auditing the carbon flow. This would help ensure transparency and avoid greenwashing and other perverse effects. Anyhow, according to some participants, private funding should not be the only source of finance for CF (through the carbon market), but public funding should be prioritised. In this general framework, it was also stressed that VCMs represent a good opportunity to foster public-private cooperation in afforestation and regeneration initiatives in the agroforestry sector.

C. The promotion of CF and VCM is a complex process

The third type of suggestion concerns the social complexity of the process of promoting CF and VCM. In the workshops emerged clearly that it is essential how diverse actors are involved: not just farmers, but also consumers, actors in the value chains, and those operating in the contexts in which agricultural production takes place (in general, the “actors of the context”, such as producers association, technical assistants, policy makers, etc.).

C.1. Involvement of various stakeholders in the promotion of CF

In various workshops, the issue was raised that, for improving policies, different stakeholders should be involved and the interaction between the diverse bodies possibly implied in the process should be taken into account. Such involvement could be focused on different issues such as the definition of the path and speed for the diffusion of CFPs and/or the participation in VCMs, the establishment of fora for letting actors discuss technical, scientific and organisational questions connected to CF (e.g., Living labs where farmers, researchers, advisors meet), the involvement of farmer associations for promoting the adoption of CFPs and the participation in VCMs (e.g., through cost and risk sharing practices) among their associates.

C.2. The adoption of CFPs should be promoted on a consensual basis

One issue that emerged from the workshops is that the promotion of CFPs and VCM should be based on a strongly consensual base. Therefore, the good reasons for choosing CF should be singled out and presented to the potential participants and stakeholders in order to gain credibility. Awareness raising should also be done concerning the stakes behind CF-related policies. CF and VCM should also become the object of dedicated communication plans and the success stories of farmers and businesses in practicing CF should be used. The already existing forms of labelling quality could be matched with the system of carbon certificates to increase the interest for VCMs. This could increase the interest of farmers for an approach that could increase revenues through synergies between carbon and quality food markets.

D. Promoting research

Research emerged from the workshops as one of the focus areas of possible intervention. There was a generalised awareness that CFPs, VCMs, and MRV methodologies should be improved to promote their ever-growing effectiveness and sustainability. Two types of suggestions could be formulated.

D.1. Knowledge should be continuously updated

Knowledge of CFPs, especially about the conditions for their effective implementation in different geographical contexts is an issue raised several times during the workshop. In general, it was stressed that policies on CF, the related MRV methodology and VCMs should be based on the most updated knowledge and research should be implemented to fill the existing gaps and those that could arise along with policy implementation. For example, it was suggested that there should be consistency between the most advanced knowledge in agronomy and the design of the certification frameworks. The data should be made available to define possible measures to promote CF in various contexts. Experimentations should be carried out in different contexts, and the results be discussed with stakeholders, for example through Living Labs. Experiments should be also on a long-term basis and aimed at investigating the multi-dimensional benefits and trade-offs of the adoption of CFPs.

D.2. MRV systems should be continuously improved

In the workshops, although with diverse emphasis, it was stressed the need to refine the approaches to MRV and ensure compatibility with existing databases and monitoring schemes. Field analysis should be always connected to MRV approaches. Furthermore, the implementation of the defined solutions should be monitored, and corrections should be implemented quickly.

E. Provision of continuing assistance to the actors involved in CF and VCM

In all the workshops the importance of a system of support to the diffusion of CFPs was stressed. Such a system is composed of actors working in the agricultural sector with different roles and interacting

with farmers for what concerns their practices (actors of the context) as well as for performing various roles in the agricultural value chains. Suggestions emerged regarding this system are of three types.

E.1. Training for Farmers

Farmers should be trained to practice CF and enter VCMs. The enhancement of skills should be both theoretical and practical, should cover both CFPs and MRV technologies and should target not just farmers but also their associations.

E.2. Training for advisors

Advisors, technical assistants and other “actors of the context” should be trained in CF, MRV, and VCMs. Advisors and technical assistants in particular, since their role is assisting farmers in using methods and tools, should master the innovations connected to CF. In many cases, they are the actors that act as intermediate links with the research sector, industry, and the policy system. They must be able to interact with all these sectors, facilitate farmers in representing problems and issues, and embrace suggestions and directions from outside.

E.3. Services for CF and VCM

In the discussions we had in each workshop, it emerged that services for technical assistance on CF and VCM should be established. The problem is not just that of creating the individual skills and capacities for assisting and training farmers, but also that of establishing an organisation with the mandate of assisting and acting as a reference point for those interested in CF. The point is not so much establishing new bodies but creating (maybe within already existing organisations) an institutionalised mandate for the promotion of CF and VCM, and a set of people that oversees – with appropriate resources – the process of promoting such a big innovation. Implementing training and consultancy through a network of qualified consultants could be one of the activities in this framework.

3. Gender issues

Gender issues have been dealt with during the validation process. The reviewers had the possibility to express their point of view on the matter (e.g. by saying if and how each factor was related to gender). In most of the workshops, the issue was dealt with as well.

In general, specific impacts of gender on any individual factor (and also for other diversity issues) did not emerge. This does not mean that gender issues were considered irrelevant. In various instances, reviewers said that gender dimensions interact with other processes strictly connected to innovation and investments. This is the case of education, which impacts the attitude towards the adoption of new technologies. Women's literacy rate matters and when it is high (as it tends to be in Europe, even if with exceptions) this means that women tend to be more innovative. As for access to credit, during the review was stressed that women tend to have more difficulties than men. The decision-making role within farms was also raised as a possible component of the role of women in innovation.

It was also stressed that women tend to be keener to learn and implement new knowledge and, therefore, to innovate and take related risks (it emerged, especially, in the Madrid workshop). Interestingly, in various reviewers' comments, the role of women was seen as similar to that of youngsters: they tend to be more educated than older farmers and more interested in innovation. They have, too, difficulties in accessing credit and, as well as women, public subsidies. During one of the workshops, it was suggested a possible explanation for this connection: youngsters in general tend to be more innovative and the new cohorts of farmers have a larger rate of women than in the past.

In general, even if there were not strong or very clear signs that gender issues impact certain factors and how they do it; there are anyhow many hints that let us suppose that such issues are not irrelevant

to the promotion of CF. As stressed above, the implementation of CFP involves a wide innovation process that has an important social dimension and, as such, it is very likely that it is affected by important societal dynamics such as those concerning the changing role and position of women in society. This issue would be worth being further studied with a dedicated focus and research effort.

4. Further research

The Map provides an overview of the kinds of obstacles and opportunities that should be faced to promote CF and VCMs. It was, of course, anything but a conclusive work. Many issues emerged that would merit further research and analysis.

The first one is gender (see the paragraph above). Other issues could be highlighted and are related to the centrality of social actors in the innovation process (see the second remark, in the first paragraph above). One issue is the role of value chains in the promotion of CF and VCMs. It was at the centre of some factors (#17, #19, #76) and emerged during the validation process. In particular – also adopting a wider stance to innovation through approaches such as the Quadruple Helix – it would be important to study how the various types of social actors within value chains could cooperate, through which instruments and how it is possible to create shared visions about CF-related innovations and practices. This would be particularly relevant because the time needed by CFPs to bring about tangible effects could weaken the consensus of the various actors.

The value chains are not the only social-economic structure through which actors' cooperation for promoting CF could take place. Training and advisory services, territorial services to agriculture, research, NGOs, and civic associations are all sectors that could impact on good results of this innovation. How this dialogue and cooperation is carried out and implemented should be continuously monitored and validated. How to do this could be a matter of focused research, including a focus on communication and language issues inherently connected to exchanges between very diverse actors and societal sectors.

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Annexes

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Annex 1

Forms of the 134 individual factors and sources of the documentary analysis

1. Costs and benefits of Carbon Farming practices

a. Costs connected to the practice/innovation

#1	Financial constraints (due also to equipment costs of establishment)	
Description	Carbon Sequestration practices often imply upfront adoption costs, and investments in equipment. This may create financial constraints.	
Explicitly mentioned in the literature as relevant for Carbon Farming	Y	
Factor type: Hindering/facilitating	Hindering	
Type of CFP for which is relevant (according to the source)	Water and tillage management; agroforestry, cover cropping, catch cropping and residue return	
Concerned actors	Farmers	
Gender perspective is considered in the analysis of the factor	N	
Sources:	23; 30; 41; 43; 44; 58; 63; 64; 67	
<i>Some descriptive elements of the factor (based on respondents' answers)</i>		
Knowledge among interviewees	Well known	
Relevance	Very relevant	
Land use and/or landscapes most affected by the factor	All. Some interviewees mention: Croplands, peatlands, steep slopes, pasture, forestry. Two others mention the issue of equipment costs: "Landscapes under semi-arid conditions and in low-income economies were on hand there is little SOC in soils and know-how among farmers and from academia to farmers is poor"; "This factor is linked to equipment costs, so anywhere where high-cost equipment is needed"	
Geographical are this factor is most present	All	
Different impact of the factor on the actors involved	It can work differently based on the economic level of the region and the farmers, the government initiatives and the age of the farmers. In this regard, one interviewee responds "As it is associated with innovations and economic risks, young farmers are more prone to adopt them. Also new farmers and small farmers may have more difficulties in getting the funds for these investments"	
Specific CF practices affected by the factor		
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • "Agroforestry" (3) • "Establishment of perennial crops" • "Equipment for managing arable land (Croplands, Pastures, Agroforestry), Forestry" • "Cover cropping" • "Introduction of rotational grazing and improved pasture management where labour increases may occur or where it is better for the landscape to switch to a reduced number of livestock" • "Green manure, tillage" • "Introduction of no-till seeding where equipment rentals are unavailable or cost prohibitive terracing or other erosion control measures that require heavy labour" • "Zero/min-till practices, biomass crops" • "Rewetting of drained organic soils" • "For organic amendment application" 		

- “Anywhere where high-cost equipment is needed – so very broad, and hard to overcome without grants/ supported loans etc. “
- “For arable farming, as investments in adapted machinery are required”
- “Almost every practice has a financial constrain”
- “All the practices that request the adoption of new machineries or technologies not usually applied in the farm”

#2 Opportunity costs of soil carbon sequestration practices	
Description	Soil Carbon Sequestration measures can also imply opportunity costs, i.e. their implementation could require farmers to forgo revenue from other sources.
Explicitly mentioned in the literature as relevant for Carbon Farming	Y
Factor type: Hindering/facilitating	It depends on the contest (location, type of soil, farming system, other)
Type of CFP for which is relevant (according to the source)	Crop residue, soil restoration,
Concerned actors	Farmers
Gender perspective is considered in the analysis of the factor	N
Sources:	14; 30; 41
<i>Some descriptive elements of the factor (based on respondents' answers)</i>	
Knowledge among interviewees	Well known
Relevance	Very relevant
Land use and/or landscapes most affected by the factor	All, mainly croplands but also fruit orchards, grasslands, pasture, agroforestry, area with livestock farms
Geographical are this factor is most present	All. Especially “In the area where climate is the main challenge for the crop growth”
Different impact of the factor on the actors involved	Older farmers are less prone to make the investments needed to adopt CFPs as they fear they will not get their appropriate economic returns before retiring.
Specific CF practices affected by the factor	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • “All” • “All practices affecting other agricultural activities or meaning a change in farmers’ planning/traditional way of thinking” • “Cover cropping, crop residues” • “Crop residue” • “For seasonal crops” • “Carbon practices that provide the inclusion of agricultural raw wastes in the soil (straw, shells, wood chips), trees planting in fields” • “Reducing fertilizer application or reducing pesticides” • “Practices which imply a high time cost, prevent the land” 	

#3 Learning costs	
Description	Carbon farming requires new knowledge and skills that should be acquired at a cost, e.g. training, support, outreach, and practical examples (and potentially up-front payments).
Explicitly mentioned in the literature as relevant for Carbon Farming	Y
Factor type: Hindering/facilitating	Hindering

Type of CFP for which is relevant (according to the source)	All
Concerned actors	Farmers; in general it is possible to think that also advisors have to learn the new technologies.
Gender perspective is considered in the analysis of the factor	N
Sources:	49
Some descriptive elements of the factor (based on respondents' answers)	
Knowledge among interviewees	Well known
Relevance	Very relevant
Land use and/or landscapes most affected by the factor	All, specially croplands, grasslands, agroforestry or drylands/water constrained areas and intensive monocultural areas
Geographical are this factor is most present	All
Different impact of the factor on the actors involved	"In many Countries, and especially in rural areas men have easier access (possibility, time) to education", but "female farmers are keener to learn and implement new knowledge". Also "Young farmers and new comers are more open to learn from others and also share their knowledge with others"
Specific CF practices affected by the factor	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • "All" (4) • "All - mostly selection of appropriate cover/intercrops, water management, nutrient management" • "Most of them but mostly those requiring some technicalities and know-how" • "Any which represent new, novel approaches, which are a departure from established/common practice" • "When new techniques are being applied such as biological additives" • "Soil practices to increase the soil fertility" • "Zero tillage, cover cropping" • "Agroforestry; Rewetting of organic soils" • "Agroforestry" 	

#4	Maintenance costs of new practices could impact adoption		
Description	Maintaining certain technologies costs more than buying them		
Explicitly mentioned in the literature as relevant for Carbon Farming	N		
Factor type: Hindering/facilitating	It depends		
Type of CFP for which is relevant (according to the source)	General		
Concerned actors	It is a private cost that normally is sustained by an individual producer		
Gender perspective is considered in the analysis of the factor	N		
Sources:	5; 43		
Knowledge (based on respondents' answers)			
Knowledge among interviewees	Known	Relevance	Relevant

#5		Reduction of operational cost is an important aspect of the new practices	
Description	Some Carbon Farming practices reduce operational costs, especially because require less input (fuel, fertilizer, etc.)		
Explicitly mentioned in the literature as relevant for Carbon Farming	N		
Factor type: Hindering/facilitating	Facilitating		
Type of CFP for which is relevant (according to the source)	Minimum/zero tillage; clover; nitrification and urease inhibitors		
Concerned actors	Farmers		
Gender perspective is considered in the analysis of the factor			
Sources:	23; 43; 64		
<i>Knowledge (based on respondents' answers)</i>			
Knowledge among interviewees	Well Known	Relevance	Very Relevant

#6		Agro-forestry is labour-intensive	
Description	Agro-forestry requires an extra effort for tending new trees		
Explicitly mentioned in the literature as relevant for Carbon Farming	N		
Factor type: Hindering/facilitating	Hindering		
Type of CFP for which is relevant (according to the source)	Agro-forestry		
Concerned actors	Farmers		
Gender perspective is considered in the analysis of the factor	N		
Sources:	23		
<i>Knowledge (based on respondents' answers)</i>			
Knowledge among interviewees	Known	Relevance	Relevant

b. Policy on subsidies and incentives

#7		Government subsidies	
Description	Government subsidies (in the form of credit or loans or direct payment) favor the adoption		
Explicitly mentioned in the literature as relevant for Carbon Farming	Y		
Factor type: Hindering/facilitating	Facilitating		
Type of CFP for which is relevant (according to the source)	Paludiculture and agroforestry		
Concerned actors	Farmers; policy makers		
Gender perspective is considered in the analysis of the factor	N		
Sources:	43; 49		
<i>Some descriptive elements of the factor (based on respondents' answers)</i>			
Knowledge among interviewees	Well known		

Relevance	Very relevant
Land use and/or landscapes most affected by the factor	All, in particular croplands, pastures, peatlands and grasslands
Geographical are this factor is most present	All
Different impact of the factor on the actors involved	"Young people approaching agriculture may need different subsidies than established businesses. The same for the women"
Specific CF practices affected by the factor	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • "All" (3) • "Almost all" • "For practices that may require the purchase of specific equipment or initial production reduction" • "For practices that may require the purchase of specific equipment or initial production reduction" • "For agri-environmental measures that are related to CAP policies, either as constraints or as supplementary actions" • "For rewetting, public funding is concentrated on pilot and demonstration sites" • "Existing subsidies in many countries favor conventional practices" • Introduction of subsidies for perennial biomass cropping in 2000 in UK increased adoption – relevant for BECCS. Relevant to all practices as provision of subsidies provides signal to farmers that government supports the practice" 	

#8	Financial incentives	
Description	Financial incentives favour the adoption; poorer farmers tend to be more sensitive.	
Explicitly mentioned in the literature as relevant for Carbon Farming	Y	
Factor type: Hindering/facilitating	Facilitating	
Type of CFP for which is relevant (according to the source)	All (quoted agroforestry)	
Concerned actors	Farmers; policy makers and regulators	
Gender perspective is considered in the analysis of the factor	N	
Sources:	5; 23; 43; 52; 63	
<i>Some descriptive elements of the factor (based on respondents' answers)</i>		
Knowledge among interviewees	Well known	
Relevance	Very relevant	
Land use and/or landscapes most affected by the factor	All, especially croplands, peatlands and agroforestry	
Geographical are this factor is most present	All	
Different impact of the factor on the actors involved	"Overall level of financial resilience/ success, potentially linked to educational level etc."	
Specific CF practices affected by the factor		
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • "All" (2) • "Any for which a farmer is incentivized, any practice which requires additional cost" 		

- “All practices representing significant changes for farmers”
- “For all kind of CFPs, especially those that require more initial investments (e.g., direct seeding) or may reduce yields”
- “Zero/min tillage, perennial biomass crops, agroforestry
- “Especially for rewetting or restoring peatland or in reforestation activities”
- “More relevant for practices with higher costs (financial, disruption etc)”

c. Effects on profitability and yields

#9 Profitability of new practices	
Description	Increased profits brought about by new practices favor adoption/new practices must be perceived as bringing positive effects on profits for being adopted
Explicitly mentioned in the literature as relevant for Carbon Farming	Y
Factor type: Hindering/facilitating	Facilitating
Type of CFP for which is relevant (according to the source)	All
Concerned actors	Farmers; it is also suggested that advisory services have to focus on how practices can maximise profits
Gender perspective is considered in the analysis of the factor	N
Sources:	22; 30; 43; 44;52; 55; 64
Some descriptive elements of the factor (based on respondents' answers)	
Knowledge among interviewees	Well known
Relevance	Very relevant
Land use and/or landscapes most affected by the factor	All, in particular for croplands
Geographical area this factor is most present	All
Different impact of the factor on the actors involved	
Specific CF practices affected by the factor	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • “All” (3) • “All affecting crop yields potentially” • “For all, but especially for those contributing to a significant reduction of inputs, which would be translated in increased revenues when analysing farm budgets” • “Cover crops, no-till” • “Legume adoption, reduction of fertilizer, cover cropping or intercropping with high value crops” • “Cover cropping” • “Application of soil amendments” 	

#10 Certain carbon sequestration practices diminish yields	
Description	Certain carbon sequestration practices diminish yields in the short run. Possible positive effects occur over longer time
Explicitly mentioned in the literature as relevant for Carbon Farming	Y

Factor type: Hindering/facilitating		Hindering
Type of CFP for which is relevant (according to the source)		Livestock; No tillage, Green Manure, Compost
Concerned actors	Farmers	
Gender perspective is considered in the analysis of the factor		N
Sources:	14; 23; 49;	
<i>Some descriptive elements of the factor (based on respondents' answers)</i>		
Knowledge among interviewees	Well known	
Relevance	Very relevant	
Land use and/or landscapes most affected by the factor	All especially croplands	
Geographical are this factor is most present	All	
Different impact of the factor on the actors involved	No	
Specific CF practices affected by the factor		
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • “Rewetting of organic soils; Agroforestry; (Reduced-till or no-till systems)” • “Zero/min tillage, crop residues” • “No tillage, Agroforestry” • “For those already indicated plus organic farming” • “Reduction of fertilizer” • “All practices involving substitution of synthetic inputs by organic ones (e.g. in organic systems or agroecological ones)” • “For those already indicated plus organic farming” • “Especially for small farmers, that they see their short-term productivity reduced” 		

#11	Some practices Increase yields in the long term	
Description	Practices of C sequestration such as crop rotation, cover cropping and other bring about reduction of fertilizer, pesticide and herbicide needs, and possible crop yield and soil quality improvements in the long term, added to the low investment and operational costs to implement the practice, may encourage farmers to establish crop rotation	
Explicitly mentioned in the literature as relevant for Carbon Farming	Y	
Factor type: Hindering/facilitating	Facilitating	
Type of CFP for which is relevant (according to the source)	Crop rotation, Cover cropping; Precision farming, manure management	
Concerned actors	Farmers	
Gender perspective is considered in the analysis of the factor		N
Sources:	23; 43; 64	
<i>Some descriptive elements of the factor (based on respondents' answers)</i>		
Knowledge among interviewees	Well known	
Relevance	Very relevant	

Land use and/or landscapes most affected by the factor	Mainly croplands, but all landscapes
Geographical are this factor is most present	All
Different impact of the factor on the actors involved	"It is more relevant for small farmers"
Specific CF practices affected by the factor	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • "All" (3) • "All practices involving substitution of synthetic inputs by organic ones (e.g. in organic systems or agroecological ones)" • "Crop rotation, manure management" • "Management of croplands that improves soil quality e.g. cover crops, conservation tillage, residue management" • "Crop rotation and cover cropping" • "Cover cropping, intercropping, integrated pest management, crop livestock integration" • "Crop rotations and cover cropping with leguminous crops" • "Crop rotation, green manure, tillage, manure application" 	

d. Farming systems interactions

#12	Combination of multiple practices	
Description	Combining multiple practices may improve ecosystem services	
Explicitly mentioned in the literature as relevant for Carbon Farming	Y	
Factor type: Hindering/facilitating	Facilitating	
Type of CFP for which is relevant (according to the source)	Soil organic amendments and vegetation covers;	
Concerned actors	No tillage, Green Manure, Compost	
Gender perspective is considered in the analysis of the factor	Farmers; it could be assumed that advisory and training services could be relevant for activating this factor	
Sources:	14	
Some descriptive elements of the factor (based on respondents' answers)		
Knowledge among interviewees	Well known	
Relevance	Very relevant	
Land use and/or landscapes most affected by the factor	All landscapes, in particular those under extreme climatic conditions and intensive monocultural area. Some interviewees mention also croplands	
Geographical are this factor is most present	All	
Different impact of the factor on the actors involved	No	
Specific CF practices affected by the factor		
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • "All" (3) • "All practices that reduce the impact of agriculture on the environment" • "Agroecological ones, e.g. agroforestry" 		

- “Agroforestry, cover crop”
- “Crop rotation + green manure + crop residues”
- “Soil organic amendments, biochar”
- “Rewetting and restoring peatlands and also conservation tillage techniques, etc”
- “Practices that increase biodiversity (live fences, intercropping), erosion control measures (shelter belts, hedgerows)”

#13 Co-benefits of Carbon farming affect the adoption	
Description	Co-benefits of Carbon farming affect adoption. The reason is that it has positive impacts on soil quality and indirectly on yields
Explicitly mentioned in the literature as relevant for Carbon Farming	Y
Factor type: Hindering/facilitating	Facilitating
Type of CFP for which is relevant (according to the source)	Retention of stubble after crop harvest, rotational grazing, no-till cropping,
Concerned actors	Farmers; it could be assumed that advisory and training services could be relevant for activating this factor
Gender perspective is considered in the analysis of the factor	N
Sources:	16; 23; 40; 43
<i>Some descriptive elements of the factor (based on respondents' answers)</i>	
Knowledge among interviewees	Well known
Relevance	Very relevant
Land use and/or landscapes most affected by the factor	All
Geographical are this factor is most present	All
Different impact of the factor on the actors involved	No
Specific CF practices affected by the factor	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • “All” • “Crop rotation, crop residues, tillage” • “No till cropping” • “Most important for intensive cropland farming, where the potential for soil restoration is highest. Although livestock breeding has even higher impacts on the environment, current C farming practices are mostly targeting croplands” • “Specially for restoring or reforestation for biodiversity and sustainable forest management” • “Practices that increase biodiversity, erosion control measures” 	

#14 Uncertainty about the results of introducing Soil Carbon Management Practices	
Description	Farmers, particularly those who are risk adverse, are looking for more assurances about the income potential of these Soil Carbon Management and other conservation practices.
Explicitly mentioned in the literature as relevant for Carbon Farming	Y
Factor type: Hindering/facilitating	Hindering

Type of CFP for which is relevant (according to the source)	All
Concerned actors	Farmers
Gender perspective is considered in the analysis of the factor	N
Sources:	5; 22; 44; 52
<i>Some descriptive elements of the factor (based on respondents' answers)</i>	
Knowledge among interviewees	Well known
Relevance	Very relevant
Land use and/or landscapes most affected by the factor	All landscapes, with a specific mention for "Intensive monocultural areas"
Geographical are this factor is most present	All
Different impact of the factor on the actors involved	The small farmers are more reluctant to take risk, while young people and women seem more interested in developing conservative practices regardless of the impact on income
Specific CF practices affected by the factor	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • "All" (6) • "All, particularly those related to livestock" • "All in general but those related to the efficient use of fertilizers or pesticides which may have an impact on the final crop production could more relevant" • "Newer, more innovative/less common approaches where there is less of evidence base from which to draw inferences about performance" 	

#15	Improving fertilisation efficiency indirectly reduces emissions of CO2	
Description	Improving fertilisation efficiency may induce savings in other chains, but implies also some investment costs	
Explicitly mentioned in the literature as relevant for Carbon Farming	Y	
Factor type: Hindering/facilitating	It depends on the contest (location, type of soil, farming system, other)	
Type of CFP for which is relevant (according to the source)	All	
Concerned actors	Farmers; producers of fertilizers	
Gender perspective is considered in the analysis of the factor	N	
Sources:	49	
<i>Some descriptive elements of the factor (based on respondents' answers)</i>		
Knowledge among interviewees	Well known	
Relevance	Very relevant	
Land use and/or landscapes most affected by the factor	Mainly croplands. The interviewees mention also: mixed livestock and crop systems; agroforestry, intensive monocultural areas	
Geographical are this factor is most present	All except the local level (not mentioned)	
Different impact of the factor on the actors involved	No	

Specific CF practices affected by the factor
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • “All” • “All carbon farming practices can reduce energy and materials consumption and, therefore, reduce the environmental footprint of agriculture” • “For all but especially those relying of manure management” • “All based on N application” • “Fertilizer reduction through increase of legumes, integration of crops and livestock” • “Fertilization reduction, cover crops” • “Croplands as grasslands are much less fertilized and for grasslands FYM is generally abundant.” • “Especially in agroforestry or mixed farming and also in the cover crops or conservation tillage” • “Introduction of leguminous crops or trees”

#16	Farmers face competing pressures		
Description	Farmers are business managers and as such must deal holistically with a range of financial and time requirements		
Explicitly mentioned in the literature as relevant for Carbon Farming	N		
Factor type: Hindering/facilitating	Hindering		
Type of CFP for which is relevant (according to the source)	General		
Concerned actors	Farmers		
Gender perspective is considered in the analysis of the factor	N		
Sources:	58; 67		
<i>Knowledge (based on respondents' answers)</i>			
Knowledge among interviewees	Well Known	Relevance	Very Relevant

#17	Unequal distribution of costs/benefits across supply chains		
Description	The unequal distribution of costs and benefits across agro-food supply chains reduces the motivation of farmers to adopt CSA technologies.		
Explicitly mentioned in the literature as relevant for Carbon Farming	N		
Factor type: Hindering/facilitating	Hindering		
Type of CFP for which is relevant (according to the source)	General		
Concerned actors	Farmers; actors within the supply chains (the costs are borne by farmers and the benefits are borne elsewhere)		
Gender perspective is considered in the analysis of the factor	N		
Sources:	44		
<i>Knowledge (based on respondents' answers)</i>			
Knowledge among interviewees	Known	Relevance	Very Relevant

e. Market and sector dynamics (demand and supply sides)

#18	Consumers' willingness to pay for sustainable products is not certain		
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Description	Consumers' willingness to pay for sustainable products sometimes is assumed as relevant by farmers, but sometimes it turns out that it is not the case		
Explicitly mentioned in the literature as relevant for Carbon Farming	N		
Factor type: Hindering/facilitating	It depends on the contest (location, type of soil, farming system, other)		
Type of CFP for which is relevant (according to the source)	General		
Concerned actors	Farmers; consumers; those who helps farmers investigating consumers orientation.		
Gender perspective is considered in the analysis of the factor	N		
Sources:	22; 44		
Knowledge (based on respondents' answers)			
Knowledge among interviewees	Well Known	Relevance	Very Relevant

#19	The organisation of industrial sectors and value chain affect adoption of climate-friendly measures		
Description	The existing contracts within the value chains may induce farmers to not practices climate friendly measures (e.g. the related costs cannot be sustained).		
Explicitly mentioned in the literature as relevant for Carbon Farming	N		
Factor type: Hindering/facilitating	It depends on the contest (location, type of soil, farming system, other)		
Type of CFP for which is relevant (according to the source)	General		
Concerned actors	Famers; actors within the value chains; policy makers who can help farmers to do certain choices		
Gender perspective is considered in the analysis of the factor	N		
Sources:	67		
Knowledge (based on respondents' answers)			
Knowledge among interviewees	Little Known	Relevance	Very Relevant

f. Access to resources (human and social capital)

#20	Farmers' wealth/firm size and property impact adoption		
Description	Literacy level, wealth, and firm income favour the uptake of practices. In general, these aspects increase availability to those resources that favour the uptake of new technologies		
Explicitly mentioned in the literature as relevant for Carbon Farming	Y		
Factor type: Hindering/facilitating	Facilitating		
Type of CFP for which is relevant (according to the source)	All		
Concerned actors	Farmers		

Gender perspective is considered in the analysis of the factor		N	
Sources:		5; 25; 40; 43	
<i>Some descriptive elements of the factor (based on respondents' answers)</i>			
Knowledge among interviewees	Well known		
Relevance	Relevant		
Land use and/or landscapes most affected by the factor	All, especially on marginal lands and likely where larger, more industrial type farms operate		
Geographical are this factor is most present	All		
Different impact of the factor on the actors involved	Young farmers may be more open to implement innovations, especially in some regions where there is still a different level of literacy between young and old or between men and women.		
Specific CF practices affected by the factor			
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • “All” (29) • “For most of them, especially those that need more initial investments such as appropriate machinery” • “CF measures with high investment costs, such as agroforestry” • “Higher cost/ higher tech options” • “Fertilizer reduction/optimization, other inputs optimization as water input” 			

#21	Access to labour		
Description	The possibility to access labour improve possibility to practice. Family size is relevant for this reason		
Explicitly mentioned in the literature as relevant for Carbon Farming	N		
Factor type: Hindering/facilitating	Facilitating		
Type of CFP for which is relevant (according to the source)	General		
Concerned actors	Farmers		
Gender perspective is considered in the analysis of the factor	N		
Sources:	25; 43		
<i>Knowledge (based on respondents' answers)</i>			
Knowledge among interviewees	Known	Relevance	Little relevant

2. VCM and innovative practices

a. Farming system interaction with VCM

#22		Market leakage – Unintended effect	
Description	“Market leakage occurs when many farmers reduce output as a result of the carbon farming scheme, which leads to increased market prices for output that induce additional farming activities to occur elsewhere”		
Explicitly mentioned in the literature as relevant for Carbon Farming	Y		
Factor type: Hindering/facilitating	Hindering		
Type of CFP for which is relevant (according to the source)	The example is connected to livestock		
Concerned actors	Regulators		
Gender perspective is considered in the analysis of the factor	N		
Sources:	18		
<i>Some descriptive elements of the factor (based on respondents' answers)</i>			
Knowledge among interviewees	Known		
Relevance	Little relevant		
Land use and/or landscapes most affected by the factor	All, mostly Cropland		
Geographical are this factor is most present	Mostly International		
Different impact of the factor on the actors involved	No		
Specific CF practices affected by the factor			
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> “Cover cropping, intercropping, reduction of fertilizer” 			

#23		Price structure impacts decision	
Description	Changes in certain prices induced by policy choices can have effects on adoption. In general, carbon gains and profits depend on the overall market conditions.		
Explicitly mentioned in the literature as relevant for Carbon Farming	Y		
Factor type: Hindering/facilitating	It depends on the contest (location, type of soil, farming system, other)		
Type of CFP for which is relevant (according to the source)	ALL		
Concerned actors	Farmers		
Gender perspective is considered in the analysis of the factor	N		
Sources:	23; 41		
<i>Some descriptive elements of the factor (based on respondents' answers)</i>			

Knowledge among interviewees	Known
Relevance	Very Relevant
Land use and/or landscapes most affected by the factor	All, in particular Cropland, pasture and peatland
Geographical are this factor is most present	All
Different impact of the factor on the actors involved	No
Specific CF practices affected by the factor	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • “All” (3) • “All in general because some policies may provide some incentives for specific products under specific conditions” • “All which are subsidized through VCM” • “Change in crop rotations and crops” • “Low prices, low interest. So price level matters in the choice of CF scheme” 	

#24	Possible competition between farmers in higher and lower income countries	
Description	The advantages of selling carbon credits could be greater for farmers in developing countries, (if the price is unique).	
Explicitly mentioned in the literature as relevant for Carbon Farming	Y	
Factor type: Hindering/facilitating	Hindering	
Type of CFP for which is relevant (according to the source)	General	
Concerned actors	The effect is indirect. It depends on the representation of market dynamics that farmers and other actors have, as well as on specific information.	
Gender perspective is considered in the analysis of the factor	N	
Sources:	66	
<i>Some descriptive elements of the factor (based on respondents' answers)</i>		
Knowledge among interviewees	Known	
Relevance	Relevant	
Land use and/or landscapes most affected by the factor	All	
Geographical are this factor is most present	All	
Different impact of the factor on the actors involved	In developing countries it can perform differently. Otherwise, No.	
Specific CF practices affected by the factor		
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • “All” (2) • “Any financed by VCM” • “All in general but more regulation is needed to make a secure market” 		

#25 Averse attitude towards data publishing	
Description	The need to publish data needed for the practice of carbon schemes can create adversity among farmers
Explicitly mentioned in the literature as relevant for Carbon Farming	N
Factor type: Hindering/facilitating	Hindering
Type of CFP for which is relevant (according to the source)	ALL
Concerned actors	Farmers
Gender perspective is considered in the analysis of the factor	N
Sources:	18
<i>Knowledge (based on respondents' answers)</i>	
Knowledge among interviewees	Well Known
Relevance	Relevant

#26 Off-farm income	
Description	Off-farm income may also influence the adoption of SAP (Sustainable Agricultural Practices). An additional income, external to farmland, may provide additional resources for adoption or decrease the priority of agricultural work
Explicitly mentioned in the literature as relevant for Carbon Farming	N
Factor type: Hindering/facilitating	Facilitating
Type of CFP for which is relevant (according to the source)	General
Concerned actors	Farmers
Gender perspective is considered in the analysis of the factor	N
Sources:	25
<i>Knowledge (based on respondents' answers)</i>	
Knowledge among interviewees	Well Known
Relevance	Very Relevant

#27 Unintended effect of incentives (crowd out effect)	
Description	Studies demonstrate that specific incentives could crowd out investment-related investments. It depends on the context.
Explicitly mentioned in the literature as relevant for Carbon Farming	N
Factor type: Hindering/facilitating	It depends on the context (location, type of soil, farming system, other)
Type of CFP for which is relevant (according to the source)	Cover crops, conservation tillage and others
Concerned actors	Farmers
Gender perspective is considered in the analysis of the factor	N
Sources:	43
<i>Knowledge (based on respondents' answers)</i>	
Knowledge among interviewees	Little Known
Relevance	Very Relevant

b. VCM uncertainty

#28		Risk of Double funding	
Description		Double funding occurs when farmers are paid twice from different policies/schemes for the same action. It undermines market functioning and the objective of decarbonization. This should be avoided by regulators but is difficult to achieve and requires complex controls.	
Explicitly mentioned in the literature as relevant for Carbon Farming		Y	
Factor type: Hindering/facilitating		Hindering	
Type of CFP for which is relevant (according to the source)		All	
Concerned actors	Regulators and, only indirectly, farmers		
Gender perspective is considered in the analysis of the factor		N	
Sources:	18		
<i>Some descriptive elements of the factor (based on respondents' answers)</i>			
Knowledge among interviewees	Well known		
Relevance	R#69elevant		
Land use and/or landscapes most affected by the factor	All, in particular Cropland		
Geographical are this factor is most present	All, but not local		
Different impact of the factor on the actors involved	No		
Specific CF practices affected by the factor			
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • “All” (2) • “All CF practices for which public subsidies are available” • “Those related CAP payments” • “Practices related to cover crops that are already required by the CAP compliance. Other examples include the SOC/clay ratio as an indicator for soil health. These measures are at risk for double counting changes in SOC stocks” 			

#29		Potential lack of demand for Carbon credits	
Description		It is not clear if the demand for credit will be sufficient to make the carbon credit market an opportunity for farmers.	
Explicitly mentioned in the literature as relevant for Carbon Farming		Y	
Factor type: Hindering/facilitating		Hindering	
Type of CFP for which is relevant (according to the source)		All	
Concerned actors	Farmers that could be concerned for the uncertainty of demand; regulators, who knows this problem and should find a way to cope with it		
Gender perspective is considered in the analysis of the factor		N	
Sources:	18		

<i>Some descriptive elements of the factor (based on respondents' answers)</i>	
Knowledge among interviewees	Known
Relevance	Relevant
Land use and/or landscapes most affected by the factor	All, mainly arable lands with traditional intensive cultivation (like North Italy)
Geographical are this factor is most present	International, European
Different impact of the factor on the actors involved	No
Specific CF practices affected by the factor	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • “All” • “In particular for the most innovative practices, little known or expensive to apply and not already used by the most sustainable farms” 	

#30	Cyclicity of demand for agricultural credits disincentives CF practices	
Description	Cyclicity of demand and multiyear process of production of agricultural credits disincentives continuous CF practices. Investments tend to be higher in the first period after the launching of policies and then diminishes. Overall, this phenomenon could jeopardize the correct functioning of carbon credit market	
Explicitly mentioned in the literature as relevant for Carbon Farming	Y	
Factor type: Hindering/facilitating	Hindering	
Type of CFP for which is relevant (according to the source)	ALL	
Concerned actors	Farmers and credit buyers; farmers could suffer of the uncertainty that is probably perceived by actors in the finance industry	
Gender perspective is considered in the analysis of the factor	N	
Sources:	66	
<i>Some descriptive elements of the factor (based on respondents' answers)</i>		
Knowledge among interviewees	Known	
Relevance	Relevant	
Land use and/or landscapes most affected by the factor	All, in particular Cropland and areas that already have high levels of C sink or that already regularly apply CF practices and which therefore could start from a baseline that is already very high and difficult to improve	
Geographical are this factor is most present	European	
Different impact of the factor on the actors involved	No	
Specific CF practices affected by the factor		
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • “All” • “I'm thinking of practices that allow you to quickly reach high levels of C sink and that are difficult to improve” 		

#31	Uncertainty about the price of carbon hinders the adoption of carbon farming practices (operational aspect)	
Description	The price of carbon credits is not stable. This uncertainty represents a barrier: the prospect of financial gains is not seen as a benefit able to offset to costs of adopting the new farming practices required to trade the credits	
Explicitly mentioned in the literature as relevant for Carbon Farming	Y	
Factor type: Hindering/facilitating	Hindering	
Type of CFP for which is relevant (according to the source)	ALL	
Concerned actors	Farmers (probably also for other actors in the carbon credit industry)	
Gender perspective is considered in the analysis of the factor	N	
Sources:	16; 18; 43	
<i>Some descriptive elements of the factor (based on respondents' answers)</i>		
Knowledge among interviewees	Known	
Relevance	Very Relevant	
Land use and/or landscapes most affected by the factor	All, in particular Arable lands with intensive cultivation, Forestry and Agroforestry	
Geographical are this factor is most present	International, in particular European	
Different impact of the factor on the actors involved	No	
Specific CF practices affected by the factor		
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • "All" • "All and in particular the most expensive ones such as the application of the agroforestry model" • "Rewetting and restoring peatlands and wetlands, trees' integration or shrubs in mixed farming, and/or conservation tillage" 		

#32	Credibility of credit markets/Quality of carbon credits/Accountability of reporting	
Description	The low level of credibility of credit markets (connected to issues such as permanence and non-additionality) is a barrier to participate in trading; Changing farm management to increase SOC-sequestration will only be eligible for offset payments if activities represent permanent abatement.	
Explicitly mentioned in the literature as relevant for Carbon Farming	Y	
Factor type: Hindering/facilitating	Hindering	
Type of CFP for which is relevant (according to the source)	ALL	
Concerned actors	Actors in the financial industry; This factor is relevant both for farmers and for regulators. It is not immediately evident (therefore it arises when schemes are being proposed).	
Gender perspective is considered in the analysis of the factor	N	
Sources:	41; 49; 66	
<i>Some descriptive elements of the factor (based on respondents' answers)</i>		

Knowledge among interviewees	Known
Relevance	Very Relevant
Land use and/or landscapes most affected by the factor	All, in particular Croplands
Geographical are this factor is most present	International
Different impact of the factor on the actors involved	No
Specific CF practices affected by the factor	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • “All” • “All financed by VCM” • “All measures aiming to increase the SOC stocks. Changes are slow against a background of large stocks. The spatial variability does not help either” • “Practices that can easily be stopped. Not such much practices such as establishment of hedges, agroforestry, or rewetting of organic soils” • “Soil carbon voluntary markets” 	

#33	Competition between providers of carbon credits not in agriculture	
Description	Uncertainty in the conversion of agricultural practices into carbon credits, suppliers of agricultural carbon credits will face competition from other suppliers of carbon credits.	
Explicitly mentioned in the literature as relevant for Carbon Farming	Y	
Factor type: Hindering/facilitating	Hindering	
Type of CFP for which is relevant (according to the source)	ALL	
Concerned actors	This factor probably undermines all the carbon farming industry. It probably doesn't have a direct effect on the farmers (who, otherwise, could perceive the overall weakness of the market)	
Gender perspective is considered in the analysis of the factor	N	
Sources:	66	
<i>Some descriptive elements of the factor (based on respondents' answers)</i>		
Knowledge among interviewees	Known	
Relevance	Relevant	
Land use and/or landscapes most affected by the factor	All, in particular Arable lands	
Geographical are this factor is most present	All, mainly International and European	
Different impact of the factor on the actors involved	No	
Specific CF practices affected by the factor		
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • “All” (2) 		

#34	Carbon storage reversal/ Credit reversal are a liability	
Description	This is a problem for carbon credit schemes, as participants may have incentives to reverse carbon storage or lack incentives to reduce this risk, which would undermine the integrity of these schemes and undo the carbon gains. No insurance is present for carbon credit reversal	
Explicitly mentioned in the literature as relevant for Carbon Farming	Y	
Factor type: Hindering/facilitating	Hindering	
Type of CFP for which is relevant (according to the source)	ALL	
Concerned actors	Farmers and credit buyers; farmers could suffer of the uncertainty that is probably perceived by actors in the finance industry	
Gender perspective is considered in the analysis of the factor	N	
Sources:	18; 49; 66	
<i>Some descriptive elements of the factor (based on respondents' answers)</i>		
Knowledge among interviewees	Well known	
Relevance	Very relevant	
Land use and/or landscapes most affected by the factor	Croplands, but also managed peatlands and those where C reversals are more likely (in Europe, Mediterranean areas are more prone to experience this type of reversal due to meteorological processes influencing soil erosion, soil losses and desertification processes)	
Geographical are this factor is most present	All except local	
Different impact of the factor on the actors involved	No	
Specific CF practices affected by the factor		
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • “All” • “For all practices that aim increasing the soil carbon. When these measures are not maintained the stocks will again decrease” • “Practices that can easily be stopped. Not such much practices such as establishment of hedges, agroforestry, or rewetting of organic soils” • “No tillage” 		

c. VCM implementation costs

#35	High costs for results-based schemes/MRV-Increased transaction Costs	
Description	Participation in VCM implies higher costs, particularly the result-based schemes. Indeed, there are transaction costs of verification for carbon farming; High certification costs; need to define the pace of calculation. The application of the procedure implies also hidden costs	
Explicitly mentioned in the literature as relevant for Carbon Farming	Y	
Factor type: Hindering/facilitating	Hindering	
Type of CFP for which is relevant (according to the source)	ALL	

Concerned actors	In general, the practice is costly for regulators, who could be unwilling to promote and practice VCM. Each transaction for farmers may not be worth the cost.
Gender perspective is considered in the analysis of the factor	N
Sources:	4; 18; 30; 49; 67
<i>Some descriptive elements of the factor (based on respondents' answers)</i>	
Knowledge among interviewees	Well known
Relevance	Very relevant
Land use and/or landscapes most affected by the factor	All, in particular Croplands and those where C stocking potential is the lowest (and thus associated payments to farmers would be initially smaller. This reduced additional income would become shorter once the costs of MRV are considered).
Geographical are this factor is most present	All. (Mediterranean areas in Europe are more vulnerable in this regard. Not only their soils have a lower C accumulation potential; also MRV efforts and costs must be more intensive due to greater heterogeneity of conditions in the exploitations and potential interannual and intra-annual C losses)
Different impact of the factor on the actors involved	No
Specific CF practices affected by the factor	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • "All" (2) • "Certifications for soil amendments" • "Conservation tillage, catch crops, cover crops and/or fertiliser and pesticide' reduction" 	

#36	Lack of transparency in the price discovery mechanism	
Description	Some participants of marketplaces for credits see credit price information as sensitive, and do not want to make this public. This could be a problem for schemes, as generally, clear information on prices supports efficient operation of markets	
Explicitly mentioned in the literature as relevant for Carbon Farming	Y	
Factor type: Hindering/facilitating	Hindering	
Type of CFP for which is relevant (according to the source)	ALL	
Concerned actors	Farmers and, in general, potential participants in the market-based schemes could be unwilling to enter	
Gender perspective is considered in the analysis of the factor	N	
Sources:	18; 66	
<i>Some descriptive elements of the factor (based on respondents' answers)</i>		
Knowledge among interviewees	Known	
Relevance	Very Relevant	
Land use and/or landscapes most affected by the factor	All	
Geographical are this factor is most present	International	

Different impact of the factor on the actors involved	No
Specific CF practices affected by the factor	
<ul style="list-style-type: none">• “All” (3)	

3. Orientation towards the environment and drive for change

a. Social pressure (from peers, local communities, etc.)

#37	Demonstration: Farmers evaluation of neighbour agricultural practices impacts on adoption	
Description	Farmers make their opinions based on what they see in neighbouring properties. Demonstration occurs by observing what happens in neighbouring properties.	
Explicitly mentioned in the literature as relevant for Carbon Farming	Y	
Factor type: Hindering/facilitating	It depends	
Type of CFP for which is relevant (according to the source)	All (example are no tillage, planting trees, stubble retention)	
Concerned actors	Farmers; somehow local communities are relevant	
Gender perspective is considered in the analysis of the factor	N	
Sources:	16	
<i>Some descriptive elements of the factor (based on respondents' answers)</i>		
Knowledge among interviewees	Well known	
Relevance	Very relevant	
Land use and/or landscapes most affected by the factor	All, especially Croplands	
Geographical are this factor is most present	All	
Different impact of the factor on the actors involved	No	
Specific CF practices affected by the factor		
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • "All" (7) • "In particular for practices that are not yet widely adopted, such as agroforestry or paludiculture" • "Practices that are visible, such as no-till, tree planting, cover crops, stubble retention" • "All related reduce use of fertilizers and pesticides and also conservation tillage and cover crops" 		

#38	Acceptance and support from neighbors/pressure from significant others	
Description	Social capital is important for the adoption of new agricultural practices (there could be a role for social media in this)	
Explicitly mentioned in the literature as relevant for Carbon Farming	Y	
Factor type: Hindering/facilitating	Hindering	
Type of CFP for which is relevant (according to the source)	All	
Concerned actors	Farmers; local communities and network	
Gender perspective is considered in the analysis of the factor	N	
Sources:	15; 22; 25; 40; 43; 44; 51; 57; 62; 64	
<i>Some descriptive elements of the factor (based on respondents' answers)</i>		

Knowledge among interviewees	Well known
Relevance	Relevant
Land use and/or landscapes most affected by the factor	All, in particular Croplands, orgic soil. Where farms operate in proximity to each other (community element)
Geographical are this factor is most present	All
Different impact of the factor on the actors involved	Age of the farmer could play a role, with older farmers more deeply rooted within their communities
Specific CF practices affected by the factor	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • “All” (5) • “Rewetting of organic soils” • “Soil Capital mainly works for cropland farmers” 	

#39	Knowledge brokers are crucial for promoting innovation		
Description	The opinion of key stakeholders, advisors and other gatekeepers are crucial for the adoption of innovation		
Explicitly mentioned in the literature as relevant for Carbon Farming	N		
Factor type: Hindering/facilitating	Facilitating		
Type of CFP for which is relevant (according to the source)	General		
Concerned actors	Advisors, gatekeepers and other actors in the local contexts		
Gender perspective is considered in the analysis of the factor	N		
Sources:	43		
<i>Knowledge (based on respondents' answers)</i>			
Knowledge among interviewees	Well Known	Relevance	Relevant

#40	Importance of knowledge networks		
Description	Social networks sometimes have specific knowledge on soils (it's a form of social capital). Users' network are effective tools for promoting innovation		
Explicitly mentioned in the literature as relevant for Carbon Farming	N		
Factor type: Hindering/facilitating	Facilitating		
Type of CFP for which is relevant (according to the source)	General		
Concerned actors	Knowledge networks (informal social structures)		
Gender perspective is considered in the analysis of the factor	N		
Sources:	33; 67		
<i>Knowledge (based on respondents' answers)</i>			
Knowledge among interviewees	Known	Relevance	Very Relevant

b. Pro-environment sentiment

#41 Farmers' beliefs on climate change/environmental stewardship	
Description	Attention to the environment, feeling responsible for it, is a relevant factor. If farmers feel they are doing enough are reluctant to further engaging. Beliefs on climate change influence positively the adoption of SAP (anyhow, the issue is sometimes contested since this is not sufficient)
Explicitly mentioned in the literature as relevant for Carbon Farming	Y
Factor type: Hindering/facilitating	Facilitating
Type of CFP for which is relevant (according to the source)	All, but mention was to agroforestry.
Concerned actors	Farmers
Gender perspective is considered in the analysis of the factor	N
Sources:	16; 22; 25; 43; 51; 63; 67
<i>Some descriptive elements of the factor (based on respondents' answers)</i>	
Knowledge among interviewees	Well known
Relevance	Very relevant
Land use and/or landscapes most affected by the factor	All, especially Croplands (and marginal agricultural areas)
Geographical are this factor is most present	All
Different impact of the factor on the actors involved	Yes. Women are more sensitive to their surroundings, environmental responses and the well-being of living things so they may be more inclined to adopt sustainable and innovative practices.
Specific CF practices affected by the factor	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • “All” (3) • “Tree planting, agroforestry” • “Cover crops, use of fertilizers and pesticides” • “It may be more relevant for lesser-known practices or for those whose effect on the environment is little known (e.g. reduction of fertilization, sometimes farmers do not know the environmental footprint of chemical fertilization)” 	

#42 Political views about the role of the state	
Description	The states with a population more opposed to public environmental spending are more likely to have higher EQIP (Environmental Quality Incentive Program) application rates
Explicitly mentioned in the literature as relevant for Carbon Farming	N
Factor type: Hindering/facilitating	It depends
Type of CFP for which is relevant (according to the source)	General
Concerned actors	Farmers
Gender perspective is considered in the analysis of the factor	N
Sources:	43

<i>Knowledge (based on respondents' answers)</i>			
Knowledge among interviewees	Little Known	Relevance	Very Relevant

#43		Increase of land aesthetic value	
Description	Some farmers engage in agricultural practices that increases the aesthetic value of land (e.g. by maintaining certain landscapes)		
Explicitly mentioned in the literature as relevant for Carbon Farming	N		
Factor type: Hindering/facilitating	Facilitating		
Type of CFP for which is relevant (according to the source)	General		
Concerned actors	Farmers		
Gender perspective is considered in the analysis of the factor	N		
Sources:	23; 43		
<i>Knowledge (based on respondents' answers)</i>			
Knowledge among interviewees	Known	Relevance	Relevant

c. Information/knowledge

#44		Lack of skill and knowledge among farmers	
Description	Farmers felt that they lacked the necessary skills and knowledge to implement the practices and integrate them into their existing management systems and regulatory requirements. It could include several practices, for example peatland restoration		
Explicitly mentioned in the literature as relevant for Carbon Farming	Y		
Factor type: Hindering/facilitating	Hindering		
Type of CFP for which is relevant (according to the source)	All		
Concerned actors	Farmers (it implies, anyhow, the need of training therefore of dedicated agencies)		
Gender perspective is considered in the analysis of the factor	N		
Sources:	23; 52; 58		
<i>Some descriptive elements of the factor (based on respondents' answers)</i>			
Knowledge among interviewees	Well known		
Relevance	Very relevant		
Land use and/or landscapes most affected by the factor	All. Croplands, organic soils, pasture, grassland, wetland, forestry and agroforestry are specified by the interviewees		
Geographical are this factor is most present	All		
Different impact of the factor on the actors involved	Generally not, but according to one interviewee it is likely to operate especially where there is a perception that skills/knowledge among farmers are problematic, i.e. with a lower level of education, etc.		

Specific CF practices affected by the factor
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • “All” (3) • “Paludiculture, agroforestry” • “Selection of crops, water management” • “Ecosystem restoration” • “Higher tech/ higher complexity approaches” • “Soil carbon and peat management, novel practices like agroforestry, biomass and tree crops”

#45	Awareness of observable phenomena of climate change/Environmental consciousness	
Description	Farmers who are aware of the connection between certain practices and the environment are more likely to adopt those practices	
Explicitly mentioned in the literature as relevant for Carbon Farming	Y	
Factor type: Hindering/facilitating	Facilitating	
Type of CFP for which is relevant (according to the source)	All	
Concerned actors	Farmers	
Gender perspective is considered in the analysis of the factor	N	
Sources:	23; 33; 40; 42; 43	
<i>Some descriptive elements of the factor (based on respondents' answers)</i>		
Knowledge among interviewees	Well known	
Relevance	Relevant	
Land use and/or landscapes most affected by the factor	All, especially in the most sensitive and reactive environments to climate change. Mountains, coastal areas, areas with high hydrogeological risk	
Geographical are this factor is most present	All	
Different impact of the factor on the actors involved	No	
Specific CF practices affected by the factor	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • “All” (3) • “Erosion control measures – erosion is very visible and alarming” • “Conservation tillage, cover crops” • “Tillage” 	

#46	Awareness and understanding of Carbon Farming related policy framework do not increase related practices	
Description	Attitude to Carbon Farming in not only a matter of knowledge of the relevant practices. It depends on other assessment, connected to policies. Studies found that knowing that there is a policy for Carbon sequestration does not facilitate adoption	
Explicitly mentioned in the literature as relevant for Carbon Farming	Y	
Factor type: Hindering/facilitating	Hindering	
Type of CFP for which is relevant (according to the source)	ALL (particularly mulch and plant trees belt)	

Concerned actors	Farmers
Gender perspective is considered in the analysis of the factor	N
Sources:	16
<i>Some descriptive elements of the factor (based on respondents' answers)</i>	
Knowledge among interviewees	Little known
Relevance	Very relevant
Land use and/or landscapes most affected by the factor	All
Geographical are this factor is most present	Mostly International and European
Different impact of the factor on the actors involved	No
Specific CF practices affected by the factor	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • "All" (2) 	

#47	Information about the benefits of Conservation practices impacts positively adoption		
Description	Information is crucial for adopting Conservation practices (including Soil Carbon Sequestration). Nevertheless, relevant information is context specific (not all measures work in the same way in all the places)		
Explicitly mentioned in the literature as relevant for Carbon Farming	N		
Factor type: Hindering/facilitating	It depends on the contexts		
Type of CFP for which is relevant (according to the source)	General (including CS)		
Concerned actors	Farmers; (it implies extension services and other advisory agencies)		
Gender perspective is considered in the analysis of the factor	N		
Sources:	5; 22; 43; 67		
<i>Knowledge (based on respondents' answers)</i>			
Knowledge among interviewees	Well Known	Relevance	Very Relevant

d. Orientation/ability to change

#48	Attitudes towards Carbon Farming change according to the type of farm		
Description	Farmers can be divided in different groups that differ considerably in terms of their level of concern about climate change, environmental values, time orientation, place attachment, and efficacy beliefs associated with LEAP (low emission agricultural practices), indicating that different engagement strategies are needed for each group		
Explicitly mentioned in the literature as relevant for Carbon Farming	Y		
Factor type: Hindering/facilitating	It depends		

Type of CFP for which is relevant (according to the source)	All
Concerned actors	Farmers
Gender perspective is considered in the analysis of the factor	N
Sources:	55
<i>Some descriptive elements of the factor (based on respondents' answers)</i>	
Knowledge among interviewees	Known
Relevance	Relevant
Land use and/or landscapes most affected by the factor	All. Horticulture, viticulture and arable lands were highlighted by the interviewees
Geographical are this factor is most present	All
Different impact of the factor on the actors involved	Women and men may have different motivations for applying carbon farming practices. Even between young and less young people there could be differences linked to different sensitivities/needs or even technical possibilities.
Specific CF practices affected by the factor	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • “All” (2) • “All, but especially those requiring larger initial and maintenance investments” 	

#49	Relative advantage of sustainable practices in agriculture	
Description	It means the degree to which an innovation is perceived as being better than the idea it supersedes” (e.g., economic profitability or social prestige). Favourable attitudes toward relative advantage might influence positively the adoption of sustainable practices in agriculture	
Explicitly mentioned in the literature as relevant for Carbon Farming	Y	
Factor type: Hindering/facilitating	Facilitating	
Type of CFP for which is relevant (according to the source)	General	
Concerned actors	Farmers	
Gender perspective is considered in the analysis of the factor	N	
Sources:	25; 30	
<i>Some descriptive elements of the factor (based on respondents' answers)</i>		
Knowledge among interviewees	Known	
Relevance	Very relevant	
Land use and/or landscapes most affected by the factor	All, but (according to an interviewee) especially those regions which products have a great prestige and value, like those dominated by vineyards in areas with Designation of Origin.	
Geographical are this factor is most present	All	
Different impact of the factor on the actors involved	No	
Specific CF practices affected by the factor		
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • “All” (4) 		

#50 Farmers' resentment about land cost and conservation policy	
Description	Resentment concerning policies on conservation is a predictor of engagement of farmers in conservation policies
Explicitly mentioned in the literature as relevant for Carbon Farming	N
Factor type: Hindering/facilitating	Hindering
Type of CFP for which is relevant (according to the source)	General
Concerned actors	Farmers
Gender perspective is considered in the analysis of the factor	N
Sources:	43
<i>Knowledge (based on respondents' answers)</i>	
Knowledge among interviewees	Known
Relevance	Very Relevant

#51 Prejudice about certain practices may hamper adoption	
Description	Prejudice against certain practices is a relevant factor that explain adoption. It was observed in relation to biological fixation with clover
Explicitly mentioned in the literature as relevant for Carbon Farming	N
Factor type: Hindering/facilitating	Hindering
Type of CFP for which is relevant (according to the source)	Clover biological fixation
Concerned actors	Farmers
Gender perspective is considered in the analysis of the factor	N
Sources:	23
<i>Knowledge (based on respondents' answers)</i>	
Knowledge among interviewees	Known
Relevance	Very Relevant

#52 Exposure to climate change impacts increases willingness to innovate for conservation	
Description	Farmers who are exposed to climate change impacts tend to be more willing to undertake conservation practices
Explicitly mentioned in the literature as relevant for Carbon Farming	N
Factor type: Hindering/facilitating	Facilitating
Type of CFP for which is relevant (according to the source)	General
Concerned actors	Farmers
Gender perspective is considered in the analysis of the factor	N
Sources:	25
<i>Knowledge (based on respondents' answers)</i>	
Knowledge among interviewees	Well Known
Relevance	Very Relevant

#53	Self-efficacy facilitates the adoption of LEAP (Low Emission Agricultural Practices)		
Description	An individual's perceived ability to engage in a specific behaviour		
Explicitly mentioned in the literature as relevant for Carbon Farming	N		
Factor type: Hindering/facilitating	Facilitating		
Type of CFP for which is relevant (according to the source)	General		
Concerned actors	Farmers		
Gender perspective is considered in the analysis of the factor	N		
Sources:	51; 55		
<i>Knowledge (based on respondents' answers)</i>			
Knowledge among interviewees	Little Known	Relevance	Very Relevant

#54	Positive attitude towards specific practices		
Description	Adoption is also based on the familiarity with certain practices and habits.		
Explicitly mentioned in the literature as relevant for Carbon Farming	N		
Factor type: Hindering/facilitating	Facilitating		
Type of CFP for which is relevant (according to the source)	Biological fixation with Clover; feeding ionophores/probiotics to livestock; using animal manure		
Concerned actors	Farmers		
Gender perspective is considered in the analysis of the factor	N		
Sources:	23		
<i>Knowledge (based on respondents' answers)</i>			
Knowledge among interviewees	Known	Relevance	Very Relevant

#55	Temporal spillover		
Description	Attitude to innovation tends to persist. Certain practices tend to favour the adoption of other practices later on.		
Explicitly mentioned in the literature as relevant for Carbon Farming	N		
Factor type: Hindering/facilitating	Facilitating		
Type of CFP for which is relevant (according to the source)	General		
Concerned actors	Farmers		
Gender perspective is considered in the analysis of the factor	N		
Sources:	43		
<i>Knowledge (based on respondents' answers)</i>			
Knowledge among interviewees	Known	Relevance	Very Relevant

#56	Perception of market practices (and of the behavior of other actors)		
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Description	How market practices are perceived is relevant for certain actors' behavior. (e.g. in a research, interviewees thought that supermarket specifications were connected to food losses).		
Explicitly mentioned in the literature as relevant for Carbon Farming	N		
Factor type: Hindering/facilitating	Facilitating		
Type of CFP for which is relevant (according to the source)	General		
Concerned actors	Farmers		
Gender perspective is considered in the analysis of the factor	N		
Sources:	22		
Knowledge (based on respondents' answers)			
Knowledge among interviewees	Little Known	Relevance	Very Relevant

e. Utilitarian vs Non-utilitarian orientation

#57	Non-monetary drivers are more important than monetary motivation to join programs		
Description	Economic motivations are not the unique drivers of adoption of new technologies. Farmers decide also to optimise social and intrinsic goals. Lifestyle farming is relevant for explaining adoption		
Explicitly mentioned in the literature as relevant for Carbon Farming	Y		
Factor type: Hindering/facilitating	Facilitating		
Type of CFP for which is relevant (according to the source)	General		
Concerned actors	Farmers		
Gender perspective is considered in the analysis of the factor			
Sources:	40; 43; 51		
Some descriptive elements of the factor (based on respondents' answers)			
Knowledge among interviewees	Well known		
Relevance	Relevant		
Land use and/or landscapes most affected by the factor	All (in particular, agricultural and agroforestry lands)		
Geographical are this factor is most present	All		
Different impact of the factor on the actors involved	No		
Specific CF practices affected by the factor			
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • "All" (4) • "Relevant for farming systems, i.e. 'regenerative'" • "Cover crops or tree plantation" 			

#58	The opportunity to participate in carbon credit markets is not a relevant driver of carbon farming practices		
Description	Carbon farming practices could depend on incentives that are not necessarily economic.		
Explicitly mentioned in the literature as relevant for Carbon Farming	Y		
Factor type: Hindering/facilitating	Facilitating		
Type of CFP for which is relevant (according to the source)	ALL		
Concerned actors	Farmers		
Gender perspective is considered in the analysis of the factor	N		
Sources:	16		
<i>Some descriptive elements of the factor (based on respondents' answers)</i>			
Knowledge among interviewees	Known		
Relevance	Very relevant		
Land use and/or landscapes most affected by the factor	All, but again (according to an interviewee) Mediterranean areas with rainfed cereal crops under semi-arid conditions are probably the most affected. This is due to their low soil C stocking potential (lower payments) and the associated uncertainty of getting unwilling C losses due to pedoclimatic conditions (potential liability problems or reduced expectations of incomes).		
Geographical are this factor is most present	All but none mention the local level		
Different impact of the factor on the actors involved	No		
Specific CF practices affected by the factor			
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • "All" (4) 			

#59	Irrational motivations behind the choice of innovating		
Description	Studies from psychology and sociology found that individuals seemingly acted irrationally, for example: over discounting the future, suffering from overly positive illusions and enacting presumed associations		
Explicitly mentioned in the literature as relevant for Carbon Farming	N		
Factor type: Hindering/facilitating	It depends		
Type of CFP for which is relevant (according to the source)	General		
Concerned actors	Farmers		
Gender perspective is considered in the analysis of the factor	N		
Sources:	44		
<i>Knowledge (based on respondents' answers)</i>			
Knowledge among interviewees	Little Known	Relevance	Very Relevant

#60 Perception of the effectiveness of the new practices	
Description	New practices should be perceived as effective from a productive point of view. This has not to do on actual impacts on yields
Explicitly mentioned in the literature as relevant for Carbon Farming	N
Factor type: Hindering/facilitating	It depends
Type of CFP for which is relevant (according to the source)	General
Concerned actors	Farmers
Gender perspective is considered in the analysis of the factor	N
Sources:	19; 43; 67
<i>Knowledge (based on respondents' answers)</i>	
Knowledge among interviewees	Known
Relevance	Very Relevant

#61 Emotional attachment to land could hamper relocation	
Description	Emotional or cultural attachments to land or activity can act both as an enhancer and barrier to adaptation (including relocation).
Explicitly mentioned in the literature as relevant for Carbon Farming	N
Factor type: Hindering/facilitating	It depends
Type of CFP for which is relevant (according to the source)	General
Concerned actors	Farmers
Gender perspective is considered in the analysis of the factor	N
Sources:	67
<i>Knowledge (based on respondents' answers)</i>	
Knowledge among interviewees	Known
Relevance	Very Relevant

4. Technological and operational complexity of innovation

a. Time required for change

#62	Soil organic carbon content of Mediterranean soils changes relatively slowly → In the Netherlands I wouldn't speak of Mediterranean soils	
Description	The relative slowness of Soil organic carbon content of Mediterranean soils makes payments for sequestration less attractive	
Explicitly mentioned in the literature as relevant for Carbon Farming	Y	
Factor type: Hindering/facilitating	Hindering	
Type of CFP for which is relevant (according to the source)	General	
Concerned actors	Farmers	
Gender perspective is considered in the analysis of the factor	N	
Sources:	14	
<i>Some descriptive elements of the factor (based on respondents' answers)</i>		
Knowledge among interviewees	Known	
Relevance	Very relevant	
Land use and/or landscapes most affected by the factor	All agricultural and agroforestry	
Geographical are this factor is most present	All, especially regional level (Mediterranean)	
Different impact of the factor on the actors involved	No	
Specific CF practices affected by the factor		
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • "All" (4) • "Cover crops and reduce tillage; tree plantation in mixed farming will depend" 		

#63	Timing of payment (before or after sequestration)	
Description	If payments are done before sequestration based on expected climate impacts, it increases uncertainty about actual impacts and decrease permanence incentives; if payments are done ex-post, this represents a risk for farmers	
Explicitly mentioned in the literature as relevant for Carbon Farming	Y	
Factor type: Hindering/facilitating	Hindering	
Type of CFP for which is relevant (according to the source)	General	
Concerned actors	Farmers, regulators	
Gender perspective is considered in the analysis of the factor	N	
Sources:	18	
<i>Some descriptive elements of the factor (based on respondents' answers)</i>		

Knowledge among interviewees	Well known
Relevance	Very relevant
Land use and/or landscapes most affected by the factor	All
Geographical are this factor is most present	All, particularly European level
Different impact of the factor on the actors involved	No
Specific CF practices affected by the factor	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • “All” (4) • “Restoring peatlands and wetlands, or reforestation strategies or implementing conservation tillage” • “Application of organic amendments” 	

#64	Slowness of technological innovation in agriculture		
Description	Studies demonstrate that initial adoption rates of adoption of Climate Smart agricultural practices is slow		
Explicitly mentioned in the literature as relevant for Carbon Farming	N		
Factor type: Hindering/facilitating	Hindering		
Type of CFP for which is relevant (according to the source)	General		
Concerned actors	Farmers and other actors involved in promoting innovation		
Gender perspective is considered in the analysis of the factor	N		
Sources:	44		
Knowledge (based on respondents' answers)			
Knowledge among interviewees	Known	Relevance	Very Relevant

b. Complexity of the technologies and the control system

#65	Difficulty in integrating GHG impacts into national GHG inventories		
Description	Difficulty in integrating GHG impacts into national GHG inventories. This fact can undermine the integrity of schemes, including demands for credits		
Explicitly mentioned in the literature as relevant for Carbon Farming	Y		
Factor type: Hindering/facilitating	Hindering		
Type of CFP for which is relevant (according to the source)	General		
Concerned actors	Regulators, credit buyers		
Gender perspective is considered in the analysis of the factor	N		
Sources:	18		
Some descriptive elements of the factor (based on respondents' answers)			

Knowledge among interviewees	Known
Relevance	Very Relevant
Land use and/or landscapes most affected by the factor	All
Geographical are this factor is most present	All
Different impact of the factor on the actors involved	No
Specific CF practices affected by the factor	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • "All" (4) 	

#66	Control system are not effective	
Description	Absence of a system of control for the fulfilment of legal regulation	
Explicitly mentioned in the literature as relevant for Carbon Farming	Y	
Factor type: Hindering/facilitating	Hindering	
Type of CFP for which is relevant (according to the source)	General	
Concerned actors	Regulators	
Gender perspective is considered in the analysis of the factor	N	
Sources:	5	
<i>Some descriptive elements of the factor (based on respondents' answers)</i>		
Knowledge among interviewees	Known	
Relevance	Very relevant	
Land use and/or landscapes most affected by the factor	All, especially cropland	
Geographical are this factor is most present	All	
Different impact of the factor on the actors involved	No	
Specific CF practices affected by the factor		
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • "All" (4) • "Cover crops" 		

#67	Permanent grassland has physical constraints	
Description	There are physical-environmental constraints in practicing permanent grassland, since after a certain time lapse the quality of grass begins to diminish	
Explicitly mentioned in the literature as relevant for Carbon Farming	Y	
Factor type: Hindering/facilitating	Hindering	
Type of CFP for which is relevant (according to the source)	Permanent grassland	
Concerned actors	Farmers	

Gender perspective is considered in the analysis of the factor	N
Sources:	23
<i>Some descriptive elements of the factor (based on respondents' answers)</i>	
Knowledge among interviewees	Known
Relevance	Relevant
Land use and/or landscapes most affected by the factor	Mainly grassland and for an interviewee wetland
Geographical are this factor is most present	Mostly Regional (tropical)
Different impact of the factor on the actors involved	No
Specific CF practices affected by the factor	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • “Permanent grassland” (2) • “Wetland and grassland applications” • “Grassland management. There are policies on maintaining permanent grassland (> 5 years in Belgium)” 	

#68	Some practices diffuse contaminants	
Description	The use of slurry may increase the accumulation of metals in the soil. Biochar or municipal compost have similar risks.	
Explicitly mentioned in the literature as relevant for Carbon Farming	Y	
Factor type: Hindering/facilitating	Hindering	
Type of CFP for which is relevant (according to the source)	Biochar; slurry	
Concerned actors	Farmers; local authorities; health authorities	
Gender perspective is considered in the analysis of the factor	N	
Sources:	49; 64	
<i>Some descriptive elements of the factor (based on respondents' answers)</i>		
Knowledge among interviewees	Well known	
Relevance	Very relevant	
Land use and/or landscapes most affected by the factor	All, but especially cultivated land and pastures (mainly sewage)	
Geographical are this factor is most present	All	
Different impact of the factor on the actors involved	No	
Specific CF practices affected by the factor		
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • “Relevant for all practices based on relocating biomass to the target areas” • “Organic amendments” • “Addition of organic amendments” • “Organic amendments. There is a discussion on the question if organic amendments sequester atmospheric carbon or merely increase carbon storage” 		

- “Wastewater sludge, biochar applications”
- “Manure and biochar application”
- “For those considering the use of manure/slurries and the circularity between livestock and cropping systems. It is not only heavy metals, also pharmaceuticals, and also trade-offs like increased GHG or airborne pollutant emissions”
- “Cover crops and conservation tillage”

#69	R&D can reduce the uncertainty of MRV that hampers the adoption of carbon farming practices	
Description	R&D can reduce uncertainty of MRV that hampers the adoption of carbon farming practices. The current level of uncertainty hinders market-based carbon farming schemes. Investments in research are needed and should be complemented by continuing practical experience to identify further barriers and new solutions.	
Explicitly mentioned in the literature as relevant for Carbon Farming	Y	
Factor type: Hindering/facilitating	Facilitating	
Type of CFP for which is relevant (according to the source)	All	
Concerned actors	Farmers, regulators, advisors	
Gender perspective is considered in the analysis of the factor	N	
Sources:	49	
<i>Some descriptive elements of the factor (based on respondents' answers)</i>		
Knowledge among interviewees	Well known	
Relevance	Very relevant	
Land use and/or landscapes most affected by the factor	All	
Geographical are this factor is most present	All	
Different impact of the factor on the actors involved	No	
Specific CF practices affected by the factor		
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • “All” (6) • “Mainly focused on the monitoring in specific seasons of practices (cover crops and conservation tillage)” 		

#70	Carbon leakage could diminish sequestration	
Description	The emissions reduced by one country through stricter environmental controls or greater voluntary adoption of mitigating measures by actors, are increased in another country with weaker environmental protection.	
Explicitly mentioned in the literature as relevant for Carbon Farming	Y	
Factor type: Hindering/facilitating	Hindering	
Type of CFP for which is relevant (according to the source)	All	
Concerned actors	Regulators, policy makers	

Gender perspective is considered in the analysis of the factor		N
Sources:	67	
<i>Some descriptive elements of the factor (based on respondents' answers)</i>		
Knowledge among interviewees	Well known	
Relevance	Very relevant	
Land use and/or landscapes most affected by the factor	All, mainly cropland but also pasture and forest	
Geographical are this factor is most present	All, especially international	
Different impact of the factor on the actors involved	No	
Specific CF practices affected by the factor		
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • “All” (5) • “Any which may initially reduce yields or change amount of certain crop produced (fertilizer reduction, intercropping)” • “Applies mainly to forestry and provision of wood products” 		

#71	Technological trade-offs could offset the positive impacts of new practices	
Description	Certain practices could imply adverse effects that could offset other positive impacts. Examples are the risk of fire caused by crop residue in Mediterranean areas; or the need to increase herbicides. Effects are not necessarily negative.	
Explicitly mentioned in the literature as relevant for Carbon Farming	Y	
Factor type: Hindering/facilitating	It depends on the specific location	
Type of CFP for which is relevant (according to the source)	All (even if the examples are no-tillage,	
Concerned actors	Farmers; advisors at the local level could be concerned by this factor.	
Gender perspective is considered in the analysis of the factor	N	
Sources:	41; 43; 49; 64	
<i>Some descriptive elements of the factor (based on respondents' answers)</i>		
Knowledge among interviewees	Well known	
Relevance	Very relevant	
Land use and/or landscapes most affected by the factor	All, mainly cropland with a specific citation of Mediterranean landscape	
Geographical are this factor is most present	All	
Different impact of the factor on the actors involved	No (One interviewee answers yes, but does not specify the different impact)	
Specific CF practices affected by the factor		
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • “All” (3) • “Green manure incorporation” • “No-till (increased need for herbicide)” • “Conservation tillage and cover crops” • “forestation” 		

#72		Technical uncertainties/Lack of verified impact of technologies	
Description		Technical uncertainties concerning the implementation of certain practices (e.g., use of agricultural inputs), the results that will be produced, the interaction with other practices	
Explicitly mentioned in the literature as relevant for Carbon Farming		Y	
Factor type: Hindering/facilitating		Hindering	
Type of CFP for which is relevant (according to the source)		General	
Concerned actors	Farmers		
Gender perspective is considered in the analysis of the factor		N	
Sources:	16; 22; 23; 44		
<i>Some descriptive elements of the factor (based on respondents' answers)</i>			
Knowledge among interviewees	Known		
Relevance	Very relevant		
Land use and/or landscapes most affected by the factor	All, especially cropland and grassland		
Geographical are this factor is most present	All		
Different impact of the factor on the actors involved	No		
Specific CF practices affected by the factor			
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • “All” (4) • “Application of biochar, biological inoculation” • “Crop and livestock integration, cover cropping, any introduction of new crop or practice” • “Those focused on the restoration or in the efficient use of fertilisers” 			

#73		Leakage of emissions within farms undermines additionality	
Description		This phenomenon can occur when certain schemes are implemented in one part of a farm. In the others, the positive effects could be offset. This undermines additionality	
Explicitly mentioned in the literature as relevant for Carbon Farming		Y	
Factor type: Hindering/facilitating		Hindering	
Type of CFP for which is relevant (according to the source)		Livestock	
Concerned actors	Farmers, regulators		
Gender perspective is considered in the analysis of the factor		N	
Sources:	18		
<i>Some descriptive elements of the factor (based on respondents' answers)</i>			
Knowledge among interviewees	Known		
Relevance	Very relevant		

Land use and/or landscapes most affected by the factor	All, in particular cropland, grassland, pasture and peatlands
Geographical are this factor is most present	All
Different impact of the factor on the actors involved	No
Specific CF practices affected by the factor	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • “All” (3) • “Application of organic fertilizers” 	

#74	The complexity and uncertainty of Market-based schemes of carbon soil certification	
Description	There are many requirements for farmers to interact with carbon markets and the related actors and this creates additional costs – transaction costs. Extra activities are required for validation of the credit claimed and validation of reporting. The farmers bear the costs of climate actions while being highly uncertain about the possible rewards of such actions. Such uncertainty depends also on the possible occurrence of events that are completely out of farmers’ control (e.g. wildfires). Another source of uncertainty is the fluctuation of the carbon market price.	
Explicitly mentioned in the literature as relevant for Carbon Farming	Y	
Factor type: Hindering/facilitating	Hindering	
Type of CFP for which is relevant (according to the source)	All	
Concerned actors	Farmers, regulators, carbon market participants.	
Gender perspective is considered in the analysis of the factor	N	
Sources:	18; 53	
<i>Some descriptive elements of the factor (based on respondents' answers)</i>		
Knowledge among interviewees	Known	
Relevance	Very relevant	
Land use and/or landscapes most affected by the factor	All, in particular cropland and pastures	
Geographical are this factor is most present	All	
Different impact of the factor on the actors involved	No	
Specific CF practices affected by the factor		
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • “All” (3) • “Peatland’ restoration, catch crops, cover crops and conservation tillage” 		

#75	Lack of institutional capacity at the national and regional level	
Description	The ability of regulators (at the national and regional level) to establish effective carbon markets is scarce. Difficulties regard all the phases of the market process, including setting up, implementing, and monitoring schemes. This problem is exacerbated once multiple jurisdictions are considered	

Explicitly mentioned in the literature as relevant for Carbon Farming		Y
Factor type: Hindering/facilitating		Hindering
Type of CFP for which is relevant (according to the source)		All
Concerned actors	Regulators	
Gender perspective is considered in the analysis of the factor		N
Sources:	18; 49	
<i>Some descriptive elements of the factor (based on respondents' answers)</i>		
Knowledge among interviewees	Known	
Relevance	Very relevant	
Land use and/or landscapes most affected by the factor	All, in particular cropland and pastures	
Geographical are this factor is most present	All, mainly national and regional	
Different impact of the factor on the actors involved	No	
Specific CF practices affected by the factor		
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • "All" (5) 		

#76	New agricultural practices imply more organisational complexity	
Description	Crop rotation implies management constraints that are not present for monocultures. Furthermore, paperwork is relevant since participation in carbon market programs implies reading long contracts, apply additionality requirements and so on.	
Explicitly mentioned in the literature as relevant for Carbon Farming		Y
Factor type: Hindering/facilitating		Hindering
Type of CFP for which is relevant (according to the source)		All (crop rotation is mentioned)
Concerned actors	Farmers; Policy makers	
Gender perspective is considered in the analysis of the factor		N
Sources:	40; 63; 64	
<i>Some descriptive elements of the factor (based on respondents' answers)</i>		
Knowledge among interviewees	Known	
Relevance	Relevant	
Land use and/or landscapes most affected by the factor	All, mainly cropland	
Geographical are this factor is most present	All. Some interviewees mentioned European and local level	
Different impact of the factor on the actors involved	No	
Specific CF practices affected by the factor		

- “All” (3)
- “Crop rotations, cover cropping, rotational grazing”
- “Cover crops and conservation tillage”

#77 New technologies are complex			
Description	complexity refers to the degree to which an innovation is perceived as difficult to understand. Greater complexity of SAP should be negatively related to adoption		
Explicitly mentioned in the literature as relevant for Carbon Farming	N		
Factor type: Hindering/facilitating	Hindering		
Type of CFP for which is relevant (according to the source)	General		
Concerned actors	Farmers		
Gender perspective is considered in the analysis of the factor	N		
Sources:	25		
<i>Knowledge (based on respondents' answers)</i>			
Knowledge among interviewees	Well Known	Relevance	Very Relevant

#78 Availability and readiness of animal manure			
Description	Ready availability of animal manure could be a problem for those farmers who do not practice both crop cultivation and livestock farming or do not have neighbours who do this.		
Explicitly mentioned in the literature as relevant for Carbon Farming	N		
Factor type: Hindering/facilitating	Hindering		
Type of CFP for which is relevant (according to the source)	Use of animal manure		
Concerned actors	Farmers		
Gender perspective is considered in the analysis of the factor	N		
Sources:	63		
<i>Knowledge (based on respondents' answers)</i>			
Knowledge among interviewees	Well Known	Relevance	Relevant

c. Role of actors in the implementation

#79 Neglect of stakeholders in project design of sinking carbon	
Description	Stakeholders needs and behaviours are not included in the design process of project design of sinking carbon
Explicitly mentioned in the literature as relevant for Carbon Farming	Y
Factor type: Hindering/facilitating	Hindering
Type of CFP for which is relevant (according to the source)	General
Concerned actors	Project stakeholders

Gender perspective is considered in the analysis of the factor		N	
Sources:	53		
<i>Some descriptive elements of the factor (based on respondents' answers)</i>			
Knowledge among interviewees	Known		
Relevance	Relevant		
Land use and/or landscapes most affected by the factor	All with a citation for forestry, agroforestry and cropland		
Geographical are this factor is most present	All		
Different impact of the factor on the actors involved	No		
Specific CF practices affected by the factor			
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • "All" (4) • "Reforestation" 			

#80	Technologies are not fit for local farmers' needs		
Description	Technologies neglects many 'day-to-day' realities faced by farmers. They are carried out by professionals who don't know the actual problems of farmers and needs.		
Explicitly mentioned in the literature as relevant for Carbon Farming	N		
Factor type: Hindering/facilitating	Hindering		
Type of CFP for which is relevant (according to the source)			
Concerned actors	Farmers, researchers		
Gender perspective is considered in the analysis of the factor	N		
Sources:	44		
<i>Knowledge (based on respondents' answers)</i>			
Knowledge among interviewees	Known	Relevance	Very Relevant

5. Role of advisory, information and training services, soil illiteracy

a. Advisory needs for CF technologies and VCM procedures

#81 Communication barriers toward consumers	
Description	Difficulties to communicate to consumers the additional (social) value of output produced in carbon farming schemes.
Explicitly mentioned in the literature as relevant for Carbon Farming	Y
Factor type: Hindering/facilitating	Hindering
Type of CFP for which is relevant (according to the source)	General
Concerned actors	Policy Makers
Gender perspective is considered in the analysis of the factor	
Sources:	18
<i>Some descriptive elements of the factor (based on respondents' answers)</i>	
Knowledge among interviewees	Known
Relevance	Very relevant
Land use and/or landscapes most affected by the factor	Cropland, pasture, horticulture. "More related to farming systems and supply chains". "Especially those connecting urban-rural areas".
Geographical are this factor is most present	European, National
Different impact of the factor on the actors involved	No
Specific CF practices affected by the factor	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • "All" (2) • Those relating to consumer goods" • "Those related to value chain" 	

#82 Farmers are hard to reach and train	
Description	Some potential users of the Climate Smart Agriculture (CSA) technological innovations (and technology providers) are based several supply chain stages away from the farm
Explicitly mentioned in the literature as relevant for Carbon Farming	N
Factor type: Hindering/facilitating	Hindering
Type of CFP for which is relevant (according to the source)	General
Concerned actors	Trainer, policy makers, advisory services
Gender perspective is considered in the analysis of the factor	N
Sources:	44
<i>Knowledge (based on respondents' answers)</i>	

Knowledge among interviewees	Little Known	Relevance	Little Relevant
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#83	Trial of new practices is not easy		
Description	Uptake of new practices depends on the difficulties to make trials		
Explicitly mentioned in the literature as relevant for Carbon Farming	N		
Factor type: Hindering/facilitating	Hindering		
Type of CFP for which is relevant (according to the source)	All		
Concerned actors	Farmers, advisory services		
Gender perspective is considered in the analysis of the factor	N		
Sources:	40		
<i>Knowledge (based on respondents' answers)</i>			
Knowledge among interviewees	Known	Relevance	Relevant

#84	Scarce observability of impacts		
Description	Difficulty in proving value and demonstrating impact of Climate Smart Agriculture innovations		
Explicitly mentioned in the literature as relevant for Carbon Farming	N		
Factor type: Hindering/facilitating	Hindering		
Type of CFP for which is relevant (according to the source)	All		
Concerned actors	Technology provider		
Gender perspective is considered in the analysis of the factor	N		
Sources:	43; 44		
<i>Knowledge (based on respondents' answers)</i>			
Knowledge among interviewees	Well Known	Relevance	Very Relevant

#85	Difficulties for technology providers in reaching customers		
Description	Difficulties for technology providers is both identifying and reach specific costumers segments		
Explicitly mentioned in the literature as relevant for Carbon Farming	N		
Factor type: Hindering/facilitating	Hindering		
Type of CFP for which is relevant (according to the source)	All		
Concerned actors	Technology providers		
Gender perspective is considered in the analysis of the factor	N		
Sources:	44		
<i>Knowledge (based on respondents' answers)</i>			
Knowledge among interviewees	Known	Relevance	Relevant

b. Advisory agencies' skills and capacities

#86		Lack of knowledge of certain practice (CC, manure, etc.)	
Description	Lack of knowledge of certain practices by the implementers. This concerns both basic aspects and arrangement to optimize the impacts of given technologies.		
Explicitly mentioned in the literature as relevant for Carbon Farming	Y		
Factor type: Hindering/facilitating	Hindering		
Type of CFP for which is relevant (according to the source)	General (cover cropping, use of animal manure)		
Concerned actors	Farmers; it is implied that advisory services are relevant actors.		
Gender perspective is considered in the analysis of the factor	N		
Sources:	63; 64		
<i>Some descriptive elements of the factor (based on respondents' answers)</i>			
Knowledge among interviewees	Well known		
Relevance	Relevant		
Land use and/or landscapes most affected by the factor	All		
Geographical are this factor is most present	All		
Different impact of the factor on the actors involved	No		
Specific CF practices affected by the factor			
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • “All” (4) • “Novel practices, such as paludiculture or agroforestry” • “Cover crops and conservation tillage; also efficient use of fertilisers” • “Relevant only for some CFP such as Agroforestry” 			

#87		Advisor services (and quality) help adoption	
Description	Advisor services and their quality help adoption. There is a need for more cooperation among the various services, more attention to the actual needs and to the specific regional and local conditions (soil, climate, current practices, etc.). Attention to the needs could also include giving feed-back to farmers). Capacity of using local social capital is relevant.		
Explicitly mentioned in the literature as relevant for Carbon Farming	Y		
Factor type: Hindering/facilitating	It depends		
Type of CFP for which is relevant (according to the source)	All		
Concerned actors	Advisory services, individual advisors, policy makers		
Gender perspective is considered in the analysis of the factor	N		
Sources:	5; 25; 33; 43; 51; 52; 63; 67		
<i>Some descriptive elements of the factor (based on respondents' answers)</i>			

Knowledge among interviewees	Well known
Relevance	Very relevant
Land use and/or landscapes most affected by the factor	All with specific mention for Arable land, Pastures and Peatland
Geographical are this factor is most present	European, local
Different impact of the factor on the actors involved	No
Specific CF practices affected by the factor	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • “All” (6) • “Efficient use of pesticides and fertilisers” 	

#88	Lack of a widely agreed definition for soil health as a novel concept		
Description	There is not an agreed definition of the nature of healthy soil and of indicators (and the related thresholds) relevant for each type of soils, land use and climate context.		
Explicitly mentioned in the literature as relevant for Carbon Farming	N		
Factor type: Hindering/facilitating	Hindering		
Type of CFP for which is relevant (according to the source)	General		
Concerned actors	Scientists, policy makers		
Gender perspective is considered in the analysis of the factor	N		
Sources:	17		
<i>Knowledge (based on respondents' answers)</i>			
Knowledge among interviewees	Well Known	Relevance	Very Relevant

#89	Training needs for precision farming		
Description	Precision farming there is need for training the farmers as complex software are installed in the machinery (PW).		
Explicitly mentioned in the literature as relevant for Carbon Farming	N		
Factor type: Hindering/facilitating	It depends		
Type of CFP for which is relevant (according to the source)	Precision farming		
Concerned actors	Farmers, Advisory agencies (especially extension services)		
Gender perspective is considered in the analysis of the factor	N		
Sources:	23		
<i>Knowledge (based on respondents' answers)</i>			
Knowledge among interviewees	Known	Relevance	Relevant

#90	Alliances of advisors
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Description	Alliances of advisors could help in the promotion of the adoption of advanced practices for soil health		
Explicitly mentioned in the literature as relevant for Carbon Farming	N		
Factor type: Hindering/facilitating	It depends		
Type of CFP for which is relevant (according to the source)	General		
Concerned actors	Advisory agencies		
Gender perspective is considered in the analysis of the factor	N		
Sources:	33		
Knowledge (based on respondents' answers)			
Knowledge among interviewees	Known	Relevance	Very Relevant

#91	Low awareness of Climate Smart Agriculture CSA/inaccessible language		
Description	Climate change and sustainability initiatives (including CSA) were associated with 'jargon', which non-experts found hard to understand and offputting.		
Explicitly mentioned in the literature as relevant for Carbon Farming	N		
Factor type: Hindering/facilitating	Hindering		
Type of CFP for which is relevant (according to the source)	General		
Concerned actors	Technology users, farmers, Advisory services, Policy makers		
Gender perspective is considered in the analysis of the factor	N		
Sources:	44		
Knowledge (based on respondents' answers)			
Knowledge among interviewees	Known	Relevance	Little Relevant

#92	Knowledge gap on soil health		
Description	Knowledge gap concerns not just the final adopters of new practices, but is also widespread among advisors. It is due to various reasons including that knowledge is often specialized according to disciplinary boundaries or the lack of meaningful guidance for the advisors		
Explicitly mentioned in the literature as relevant for Carbon Farming	N		
Factor type: Hindering/facilitating	Hindering		
Type of CFP for which is relevant (according to the source)	General		
Concerned actors	Advisers, Advisers agencies		
Gender perspective is considered in the analysis of the factor	N		
Sources:	17; 33		
Knowledge (based on respondents' answers)			
Knowledge among interviewees	Well Known	Relevance	Very Relevant

c. General weaknesses of advisory agencies

#93		Education and training favour the adoption	
Description	Education and training favour adoption, and interpersonal relations are important		
Explicitly mentioned in the literature as relevant for Carbon Farming	Y		
Factor type: Hindering/facilitating	Facilitating		
Type of CFP for which is relevant (according to the source)	All		
Concerned actors	Advisers, Advisory services agencies		
Gender perspective is considered in the analysis of the factor	N		
Sources:	5; 33; 43; 44; 49; 52; 63; 64		
<i>Some descriptive elements of the factor (based on respondents' answers)</i>			
Knowledge among interviewees	Well known		
Relevance	Very relevant		
Land use and/or landscapes most affected by the factor	All. Especially rural landscape. Arable land, Pastures and Peatland		
Geographical are this factor is most present	Mainly local and regional		
Different impact of the factor on the actors involved	No		
Specific CF practices affected by the factor			
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • "All" (5) • "ALL in general because you want convince them to implement a new practice" 			

#94		Credibility of advisors	
Description	Credibility of advisors is crucial since behavioural changes, albeit difficult, can be achieved if those who promote them are recognized as authority and trustful		
Explicitly mentioned in the literature as relevant for Carbon Farming	Y		
Factor type: Hindering/facilitating	Facilitating		
Type of CFP for which is relevant (according to the source)	General		
Concerned actors	Advisers, Advisory services agencies, policy makers		
Gender perspective is considered in the analysis of the factor	N		
Sources:	18; 40; 44; 49; 51		
<i>Some descriptive elements of the factor (based on respondents' answers)</i>			
Knowledge among interviewees	Well known		
Relevance	Very relevant		
Land use and/or landscapes most affected by the factor	All, mainly rural productive land. Arable land, pasture, peatland		
Geographical are this factor is most present	Mainly Regional and Local level		

Different impact of the factor on the actors involved	No
Specific CF practices affected by the factor	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • “All” (5) • “Efficient use of fertilisers and pesticides and cover crops or conservation tillage” 	

#95	Organisational weaknesses of public Soil Health Management advice services		
Description	Organisational weaknesses limit the delivery of services. Such weaknesses consist of lack of adequate investment in staff capacity, little continuity in the provision of funds, little staff retention, competition with private services		
Explicitly mentioned in the literature as relevant for Carbon Farming	N		
Factor type: Hindering/facilitating	Hindering		
Type of CFP for which is relevant (according to the source)	General		
Concerned actors	Advisory services		
Gender perspective is considered in the analysis of the factor	N		
Sources:	33		
<i>Knowledge (based on respondents' answers)</i>			
Knowledge among interviewees	Known	Relevance	Very Relevant

#96	No-segmentation of information provision services		
Description	The approach to extension with farmers should be segmented and targeted. It should not just provide information but also be more helpful and appeal to people's values.		
Explicitly mentioned in the literature as relevant for Carbon Farming	N		
Factor type: Hindering/facilitating	Hindering		
Type of CFP for which is relevant (according to the source)	General		
Concerned actors	Advisory services providers		
Gender perspective is considered in the analysis of the factor	N		
Sources:	67		
<i>Knowledge (based on respondents' answers)</i>			
Knowledge among interviewees	Known	Relevance	Very Relevant

#97	Fragmentation of Advisory services for Agriculture		
Description	Various providers of advisory services compete for clients and project funding. This brings about that soil advice for farmers is characterized by duplication, conflicting deliveries and other malfunctioning		
Explicitly mentioned in the literature as relevant for Carbon Farming	N		
Factor type: Hindering/facilitating	Hindering		

Type of CFP for which is relevant (according to the source)		General	
Concerned actors	Advisory services providers		
Gender perspective is considered in the analysis of the factor		N	
Sources:	33		
<i>Knowledge (based on respondents' answers)</i>			
Knowledge among interviewees	Little Known	Relevance	Very Relevant

6. Policies and regulation

a. Rules impeding CF adoption

#98	Current rules sometimes prevent the adoption of innovation for Soil Carbon Management Practices	
Description	Some Carbon Management Practices cannot be practiced in specific national contexts because current legislations actually forbid them or hinder them.	
Explicitly mentioned in the literature as relevant for Carbon Farming	Y	
Factor type: Hindering/facilitating	Hindering	
Type of CFP for which is relevant (according to the source)	Legumes into crop rotation in Denmark; Manure application in Italy	
Concerned actors	National regulators	
Gender perspective is considered in the analysis of the factor	N	
Sources:	52	
<i>Some descriptive elements of the factor (based on respondents' answers)</i>		
Knowledge among interviewees	Well known	
Relevance	Very relevant	
Land use and/or landscapes most affected by the factor	All with specific mention for Arable land, pasture and peatland	
Geographical are this factor is most present	All except local level (not mentioned)	
Different impact of the factor on the actors involved	No	
Specific CF practices affected by the factor		
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • “All” • “All, but especially those related to manure management (at least in Spain)” • “Manure and biochar application and management” • “Organic manure application in the Netherlands” • “Restoration, agroforestry and conservation tillage” • “Agroforestry, paludiculture” 		

#99	Inconsistencies between different regulations	
Description	Inconsistencies between different regulations concerning different aspect of certain practices could create legal restrictions. Different regulations pursue different objectives that could be conflicting (e.g. European, National, local, etc)	
Explicitly mentioned in the literature as relevant for Carbon Farming	Y	
Factor type: Hindering/facilitating	Hindering	
Type of CFP for which is relevant (according to the source)	All (particularly use of manure or sludge)	
Concerned actors	Regulators, Policy makers, technology users	
Gender perspective is considered in the analysis of the factor	N	

Sources:	44; 64
<i>Some descriptive elements of the factor (based on respondents' answers)</i>	
Knowledge among interviewees	Known
Relevance	Very relevant
Land use and/or landscapes most affected by the factor	All especially pasture and organic soils
Geographical area this factor is most present	All, mainly national
Different impact of the factor on the actors involved	No
Specific CF practices affected by the factor	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • “All” (3) • “Paludiculture: conflicting with GAP payments for farming drained organic soils, for support payments, regulations for maintaining permanent grasslands, or protection of biotopes/species that have established themselves on drained organic soils” • “Reforestation and use of cover crops or conservation tillage” 	

#100	Barriers to certification hamper markets from working well	
Description	Carbon credit markets involve trading a credence good (those whose quality consumers cannot directly verify and for which experts' evaluation is needed), and any barriers to certification hinder their proper functioning.	
Explicitly mentioned in the literature as relevant for Carbon Farming	Y	
Factor type: Hindering/facilitating	Hindering	
Type of CFP for which is relevant (according to the source)	ALL	
Concerned actors	All the actors are hampered in participating in a market with this characteristic. Difficulties in certification are magnified	
Gender perspective is considered in the analysis of the factor	N	
Sources:	66	
<i>Some descriptive elements of the factor (based on respondents' answers)</i>		
Knowledge among interviewees	Known	
Relevance	Relevant	
Land use and/or landscapes most affected by the factor	All	
Geographical area this factor is most present	Mainly European level	
Different impact of the factor on the actors involved	No	
Specific CF practices affected by the factor		
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • “All” (3) • “Cover crops and conservation tillage; Rewetting and restoring peatlands and wetlands” 		

b. Effective regulation

#101	Effective standards promote the adoption/ Lack of a solid monitoring scheme	
Description	The existence of effective standards promotes the adoption of new practices (notwithstanding costs of compliance). Due to uncertainties in the MRV of net SCS and concerns about double accounting, activities that enhance net SCS have not been eligible	
Explicitly mentioned in the literature as relevant for Carbon Farming	Y	
Factor type: Hindering/facilitating	Hindering	
Type of CFP for which is relevant (according to the source)	All	
Concerned actors	Regulators, Policy Makers, Farmers and other Actors in the Carbon markets	
Gender perspective is considered in the analysis of the factor	N	
Sources:	17; 18; 22; 43; 66	
<i>Some descriptive elements of the factor (based on respondents' answers)</i>		
Knowledge among interviewees	Well known	
Relevance	Very relevant	
Land use and/or landscapes most affected by the factor	All	
Geographical are this factor is most present	All	
Different impact of the factor on the actors involved	No	
Specific CF practices affected by the factor		
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • "All" (5) • "Conservation tillage and cover crops, also restoration" 		

#102	Uniform Subsidies are not effective	
Description	Due to different operational conditions uniform subsidies are not effective	
Explicitly mentioned in the literature as relevant for Carbon Farming	Y	
Factor type: Hindering/facilitating	Hindering	
Type of CFP for which is relevant (according to the source)	All (particularly No-tillage, crop rotation)	
Concerned actors	Farmers, policy makers	
Gender perspective is considered in the analysis of the factor	N	
Sources:	66	
<i>Some descriptive elements of the factor (based on respondents' answers)</i>		
Knowledge among interviewees	Known	
Relevance	Little relevant	

Land use and/or landscapes most affected by the factor	All
Geographical are this factor is most present	All except for local level (not mentioned)
Different impact of the factor on the actors involved	No
Specific CF practices affected by the factor	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • "All" (4) 	

#103	Lack of data at the local level	
Description	Data on current/past GHG emissions/sequestration data or sufficient data for accurate GHG estimation needed for regulating the market	
Explicitly mentioned in the literature as relevant for Carbon Farming	Y	
Factor type: Hindering/facilitating	Hindering	
Type of CFP for which is relevant (according to the source)	All	
Concerned actors	Regulators	
Gender perspective is considered in the analysis of the factor	N	
Sources:	18	
<i>Some descriptive elements of the factor (based on respondents' answers)</i>		
Knowledge among interviewees	Well known	
Relevance	Very relevant	
Land use and/or landscapes most affected by the factor	All in particular agricultural land, cropland, pasture, grasslands, peatlands	
Geographical are this factor is most present	All	
Different impact of the factor on the actors involved	No	
Specific CF practices affected by the factor		
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • "All" (5) • "Impact of restoration on C seq" 		

#104	Uncertainty over credit ownership for regulators/administrators	
Description	The lack of reliable and robust registry of carbon credit can make the demand decrease	
Explicitly mentioned in the literature as relevant for Carbon Farming	Y	
Factor type: Hindering/facilitating	Hindering	
Type of CFP for which is relevant (according to the source)	All	
Concerned actors	Regulators	
Gender perspective is considered in the analysis of the factor	N	

Sources:	18
<i>Some descriptive elements of the factor (based on respondents' answers)</i>	
Knowledge among interviewees	Well known
Relevance	Relevant
Land use and/or landscapes most affected by the factor	All
Geographical are this factor is most present	All
Different impact of the factor on the actors involved	No
Specific CF practices affected by the factor	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • “All” (5) • “Conservation tillage and cover crops; efficient use of fertilisers and pesticides” 	

#105	Carbon Audit tools can be manipulated	
Description	Farmers, in principle, can “play” with carbon credit tools, e.g. changing inputs to maximise expected reductions in unrealistic ways. This undermines the functioning of the Carbon market	
Explicitly mentioned in the literature as relevant for Carbon Farming	Y	
Factor type: Hindering/facilitating	Hindering	
Type of CFP for which is relevant (according to the source)	All	
Concerned actors	Regulators, Farmers	
Gender perspective is considered in the analysis of the factor	N	
Sources:	18	
<i>Some descriptive elements of the factor (based on respondents' answers)</i>		
Knowledge among interviewees	Known	
Relevance	Very relevant	
Land use and/or landscapes most affected by the factor	All, in particular croplands and grasslands	
Geographical are this factor is most present	All except local level (not mentioned)	
Different impact of the factor on the actors involved	No	
Specific CF practices affected by the factor		
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • “All” (3) • “All of them because if finally is very unrealistic, it will not be implemented” 		

c. Diverse contexts and conditions of policies' implementation

#106 Multiple and contradictory policy goals/unintended effects of policies	
Description	Multiple and contradictory policy goals may be a barrier to a successful increase of carbon avoided and sequestered.
Explicitly mentioned in the literature as relevant for Carbon Farming	Y
Factor type: Hindering/facilitating	Hindering
Type of CFP for which is relevant (according to the source)	All
Concerned actors	Policymakers, farmers
Gender perspective is considered in the analysis of the factor	N
Sources:	18; 44; 67
<i>Some descriptive elements of the factor (based on respondents' answers)</i>	
Knowledge among interviewees	Well known
Relevance	Very relevant
Land use and/or landscapes most affected by the factor	All with specific mention for forestry, peatlands and organic soils
Geographical are this factor is most present	European and regional
Different impact of the factor on the actors involved	No
Specific CF practices affected by the factor	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • “All” (3) • “Paludiculture” • “Conservation tillage and agroforestry implementation” 	

#107 Policy mix	
Description	Different actions within policies favour adoption (e.g., favouring combinations of different practices)
Explicitly mentioned in the literature as relevant for Carbon Farming	Y
Factor type: Hindering/facilitating	Facilitating
Type of CFP for which is relevant (according to the source)	All, particularly No-till farming, residue retention and the use of cover crop
Concerned actors	Policymakers, research, advisory agencies, farm industry
Gender perspective is considered in the analysis of the factor	N
Sources:	30
<i>Some descriptive elements of the factor (based on respondents' answers)</i>	
Knowledge among interviewees	Well known
Relevance	Very relevant
Land use and/or landscapes most affected by the factor	All agriculture and agroforestry landscape

Geographical are this factor is most present	All, especially European and regional
Different impact of the factor on the actors involved	No
Specific CF practices affected by the factor	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • “All” (2) • “Reforestation or restoration and implementation of cover crops or conservation tillage” 	

#108	Policies should consider geographical variability	
Description	Biophysical environment diversity changes the conditions in which carbon farming is most effective. Policies should be based on this assumption and defining different payment schemes.	
Explicitly mentioned in the literature as relevant for Carbon Farming	Y	
Factor type: Hindering/facilitating	It depends	
Type of CFP for which is relevant (according to the source)	All	
Concerned actors	Policymakers (EU, members states)	
Gender perspective is considered in the analysis of the factor		
Sources:	49	
<i>Some descriptive elements of the factor (based on respondents' answers)</i>		
Knowledge among interviewees	Well known	
Relevance	Very relevant	
Land use and/or landscapes most affected by the factor	All (An interviewee adds “All, but especially those having a low C stockage potential such as Mediterranean rainfed cropping systems”)	
Geographical are this factor is most present	All	
Different impact of the factor on the actors involved	No	
Specific CF practices affected by the factor		
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • “All” (4) • “Agroforestry” • “Soil carbon management practices” • “More expensive or more effective CFP” 		

#109	Policies are crucial for agriculture	
Description	Policies are already dominant factors in agricultural management. Oftentimes farmers are already compliant with policies related provisions	
Explicitly mentioned in the literature as relevant for Carbon Farming	N	
Factor type: Hindering/facilitating	It depends	
Type of CFP for which is relevant (according to the source)	General	
Concerned actors	Policymakers	

Gender perspective is considered in the analysis of the factor		N	
Sources:	22		
<i>Knowledge (based on respondents' answers)</i>			
Knowledge among interviewees	Well Known	Relevance	Very Relevant

7. Differences in impacts across biophysical environment (geographical, temporal) and evaluation of farmers

a. Proximity to agricultural services

#110 Distance of the farm from services	
Description	Accessibility of extension services impacts on the adoption of new farming practices It is an aspect of geographical dimension of diffusion of technology.
Explicitly mentioned in the literature as relevant for Carbon Farming	N
Factor type: Hindering/facilitating	Hindering
Type of CFP for which is relevant (according to the source)	General
Concerned actors	Advisory services, policy makers
Gender perspective is considered in the analysis of the factor	N
Sources:	25
Knowledge (based on respondents' answers)	
Knowledge among interviewees	Known
Relevance	Very Relevant

b. Agricultural practices are affected by the characteristics of location and the farming systems

#111 Temporal variability of reducing nitrogen application	
Description	The effectiveness of the reduction of the application of nitrogen changes according to the climate condition of each year
Explicitly mentioned in the literature as relevant for Carbon Farming	Y
Factor type: Hindering/facilitating	Hindering
Type of CFP for which is relevant (according to the source)	Nitrogen application
Concerned actors	Farmers; advisory services
Gender perspective is considered in the analysis of the factor	N
Sources:	23
Some descriptive elements of the factor (based on respondents' answers)	
Knowledge among interviewees	Known
Relevance	Very relevant
Land use and/or landscapes most affected by the factor	All forestry and agroforestry. An interviewee states: "For those experiencing dramatic interannual and intra-annual changes in meteorological conditions. Again, the Mediterranean area is especially sensitive in this regard."

Geographical are this factor is most present	All
Different impact of the factor on the actors involved	No
Specific CF practices affected by the factor	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • “All” (2) • “Introduction of leguminous crops” • “Rewetting and restoring peatlands” • “Manure application” 	

#112	Certain practices are most fit for certain geographical sites	
Description	Certain practices are more suited to specific geographical sites (e.g. some very fertile land could be removed from production; sandy land are not fit for certain practices). Certain practices are valuable only with certain temperatures. The systems of incentives and the promotion should change accordingly	
Explicitly mentioned in the literature as relevant for Carbon Farming	Y	
Factor type: Hindering/facilitating	It depends	
Type of CFP for which is relevant (according to the source)	Use of straw or manure; growing legumes	
Concerned actors	Farmers; Advisory services are implied	
Gender perspective is considered in the analysis of the factor	N	
Sources:	23; 25; 43; 52	
Questions about CF-related factors		
Some descriptive elements of the factor (based on respondents' answers)		
Knowledge among interviewees	Well known	
Relevance	Very relevant	
Land use and/or landscapes most affected by the factor	All. Croplands, pastures and agroforestry were specified	
Geographical are this factor is most present	All	
Different impact of the factor on the actors involved	No	
Specific CF practices affected by the factor		
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • “All” (4) • “Diversified crop rotations, agroforestry” • “Efficient use of fertilisers or integrating trees or shrubs in mixed farming and cover crops” • “This applies to most soil or climate related measures” • “Depends on particular locations” 		

#113	Certain farm types are more suited to certain practices	
Description	Farm types are relevant for favouring certain conservation activities (e.g. livestock practicing farm vs cropping)	
Explicitly mentioned in the literature as relevant for Carbon Farming	N	
Factor type: Hindering/facilitating	It depends	

Type of CFP for which is relevant (according to the source)		General	
Concerned actors	Farmers		
Gender perspective is considered in the analysis of the factor		N	
Sources:	40		
<i>Knowledge (based on respondents' answers)</i>			
Knowledge among interviewees	Well Known	Relevance	Very Relevant

#114	Attitudes changes according to agro-systems being practiced		
Description	In different locations and with different agricultural practices and mixes of practices, the orientation to adopting conservation practices change		
Explicitly mentioned in the literature as relevant for Carbon Farming	N		
Factor type: Hindering/facilitating	It depends		
Type of CFP for which is relevant (according to the source)	General		
Concerned actors	Farmers; advisory services		
Gender perspective is considered in the analysis of the factor		N	
Sources:	43		
<i>Knowledge (based on respondents' answers)</i>			
Knowledge among interviewees	Known	Relevance	Very Relevant

8. Time and risk preferences

a. Land Tenure and succession

#115	Tenure security is connected to land tenure	
Description	Tenure security is considered a factor facilitating Tech Change. Farmers having security for a long term in their land are more willing to invest in practices that have long lifetime such as planting tree, peatland restoration,	
Explicitly mentioned in the literature as relevant for Carbon Farming	Y	
Factor type: Hindering/facilitating	Facilitating	
Type of CFP for which is relevant (according to the source)	Peatland restoration, flood management, agro-forestry and tree planting	
Concerned actors	Farmers	
Gender perspective is considered in the analysis of the factor	N	
Sources:	25; 30; 43; 67	
<i>Some descriptive elements of the factor (based on respondents' answers)</i>		
Knowledge among interviewees	Well known	
Relevance	Very relevant	
Land use and/or landscapes most affected by the factor	All	
Geographical are this factor is most present	All except international level	
Different impact of the factor on the actors involved	No	
Specific CF practices affected by the factor		
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • “All” (4) • “All, but especially those that cause significant changes in land use, such as agroforestry or paludiculture” • “Rewetting and restoring peatlands and wetlands and reforestation to increase biodiversity” 		

#116	Succession and farm structure are relevant for decisions concerning new technologies	
Description	Succession and farm structure impact land tenure, including fragmentation of properties, dimension of farms, time-horizon of property. They are factors that impact on decisions concerning the introduction of new practices	
Explicitly mentioned in the literature as relevant for Carbon Farming	N	
Factor type: Hindering/facilitating	It depends	
Type of CFP for which is relevant (according to the source)	General	
Concerned actors	Farmers	
Gender perspective is considered in the analysis of the factor	N	

Sources:	67		
Knowledge (based on respondents' answers)			
Knowledge among interviewees	Known	Relevance	Very Relevant

#117	Principal agent issues		
Description	Principal-agent issues such as landowners refusing efficient technologies for tenant farmers can also be identified		
Explicitly mentioned in the literature as relevant for Carbon Farming	N		
Factor type: Hindering/facilitating	Hindering		
Type of CFP for which is relevant (according to the source)	General		
Concerned actors	Farmers and landowners		
Gender perspective is considered in the analysis of the factor	N		
Sources:	44; 58		
Knowledge (based on respondents' answers)			
Knowledge among interviewees	Known	Relevance	Relevant

b. Risks and uncertainty

#118	Access to credit favors adoption		
Description	The adoption of climate-friendly measures that imply investments depends on the availability of credit and, in general, of cash.		
Explicitly mentioned in the literature as relevant for Carbon Farming	Y		
Factor type: Hindering/facilitating	Facilitating		
Type of CFP for which is relevant (according to the source)	All		
Concerned actors	Farmers		
Gender perspective is considered in the analysis of the factor	N		
Sources:	25; 30; 43; 44; 67		
Some descriptive elements of the factor (based on respondents' answers)			
Knowledge among interviewees	Well known		
Relevance	Very relevant		
Land use and/or landscapes most affected by the factor	All		
Geographical areas where this factor is most present	All		
Different impact of the factor on the actors involved	No		
Specific CF practices affected by the factor			
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • "All" (3) 			

- “Practices with high investment costs, such as agroforestry or paludiculture”
- “Reforestation and restoration, as well as efficient use of fertilisers and pesticides may require investment in sensors”
- “More expensive measures”

#119 Policy Uncertainty reduces adoption	
Description	The risk that policy toward Carbon Sequestration changes reduces adoption. This risk is relevant for non-market schemes, that are based on rewards for farming but could be generalized to any regulatory scheme related to carbon farming
Explicitly mentioned in the literature as relevant for Carbon Farming	Y
Factor type: Hindering/facilitating	Hindering
Type of CFP for which is relevant (according to the source)	
Concerned actors	Farmers, Regulators, administrators
Gender perspective is considered in the analysis of the factor	N
Sources:	16; 18; 40; 43; 52
<i>Some descriptive elements of the factor (based on respondents' answers)</i>	
Knowledge among interviewees	Well known
Relevance	Relevant
Land use and/or landscapes most affected by the factor	All
Geographical are this factor is most present	All except international level
Different impact of the factor on the actors involved	No
Specific CF practices affected by the factor	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • “All” (4) • “Cover crops or conservation tillage” 	

#120 Willingness to take risks favors adoption	
Description	Willingness to take on the risks associated with the investment in new agricultural practices is a crucial factor (vs risk aversion)
Explicitly mentioned in the literature as relevant for Carbon Farming	N
Factor type: Hindering/facilitating	Facilitating
Type of CFP for which is relevant (according to the source)	General
Concerned actors	Farmers
Gender perspective is considered in the analysis of the factor	N
Sources:	43; 67
<i>Knowledge (based on respondents' answers)</i>	
Knowledge among interviewees	Well Known
Relevance	Very Relevant

#121	Time preference (vs short-termism)		
Description	Farmers (and investors in general) are not positive toward waiting for the results of the new practices		
Explicitly mentioned in the literature as relevant for Carbon Farming	N		
Factor type: Hindering/facilitating	Hindering		
Type of CFP for which is relevant (according to the source)	General		
Concerned actors	Farmers, investors		
Gender perspective is considered in the analysis of the factor	N		
Sources:	43; 44; 52		
<i>Knowledge (based on respondents' answers)</i>			
Knowledge among interviewees	Well Known	Relevance	Very Relevant

9. Externalities and spillovers

#122		Negative externalities of climate action	
Description	If carbon farming schemes and climate actions are compartmentalized and other impacts are not considered, negative externalities could emerge (e.g. loss of biodiversity or loss of jobs at the local level) bringing about an overall decrease of social benefits and even impacts on climate.		
Explicitly mentioned in the literature as relevant for Carbon Farming	Y		
Factor type: Hindering/facilitating	Hindering		
Type of CFP for which is relevant (according to the source)	All		
Concerned actors	Policy makers		
Gender perspective is considered in the analysis of the factor	N		
Sources:	18; 41		
<i>Some descriptive elements of the factor (based on respondents' answers)</i>			
Knowledge among interviewees	Well known		
Relevance	Very relevant		
Land use and/or landscapes most affected by the factor	All, with a mention for agroforestry and agriculture		
Geographical area this factor is most present	All		
Different impact of the factor on the actors involved	No		
Specific CF practices affected by the factor			
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • "All" (4) • "Introduction of new trees or reduction on use of pesticides" 			

#123		Spatial spillover	
Description	Positive impacts of practices extend beyond the individual plot to neighbouring ones		
Explicitly mentioned in the literature as relevant for Carbon Farming	N		
Factor type: Hindering/facilitating	Facilitating		
Type of CFP for which is relevant (according to the source)	General		
Concerned actors	Policy Makers		
Gender perspective is considered in the analysis of the factor	N		
Sources:	43		
<i>Knowledge (based on respondents' answers)</i>			
Knowledge among interviewees	Well Known	Relevance	Relevant

10. Habits (including consumers' ones) / Resilience or existing organisational arrangements

#124	Compatibility of Sustainable Agriculture Practice/Attachment to old practices	
Description	The degree to which an innovation is perceived as consistent with the existing values, past experiences, and needs of the potential adopters. Favourable attitudes toward compatibility might influence positively the adoption of SAP. (also, the use of slurries)	
Explicitly mentioned in the literature as relevant for Carbon Farming	Y	
Factor type: Hindering/facilitating	Hindering	
Type of CFP for which is relevant (according to the source)	ALL	
Concerned actors	Farmers	
Gender perspective is considered in the analysis of the factor	N	
Sources:	5; 23; 25; 30; 43; 44; 52; 64; 67	
<i>Some descriptive elements of the factor (based on respondents' answers)</i>		
Knowledge among interviewees	Well known	
Relevance	Relevant	
Land use and/or landscapes most affected by the factor	All especially croplands	
Geographical are this factor is most present	All	
Different impact of the factor on the actors involved	This is an issue related to farmers' age. Regarding gender influence one large agricultural organisation also pointed out that women are more prone to adopt innovations.	
Specific CF practices affected by the factor		
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • "All" (4) • "Diversified crop rotations, cover crops" • "Cover crops, conservation tillage and efficient use of fertilisers and pesticides" 		

#125	Age of farmers affects attitude to change	
Description	Age of farmers could affect the level of information about new technologies and implies planning horizon and different working experience. All these aspects of age could impact differently the orientation to change. There is no unambiguous evidence on the matter	
Explicitly mentioned in the literature as relevant for Carbon Farming	Y	
Factor type: Hindering/facilitating	Hindering	
Type of CFP for which is relevant (according to the source)	All	
Concerned actors	Farmers	
Gender perspective is considered in the analysis of the factor	N	

Sources:	25; 43; 44; 63
<i>Some descriptive elements of the factor (based on respondents' answers)</i>	
Knowledge among interviewees	Well known
Relevance	Relevant
Land use and/or landscapes most affected by the factor	All
Geographical are this factor is most present	All
Different impact of the factor on the actors involved	This is an issue related to farmers' age. Regarding gender influence one large agricultural organisation also pointed out that women are more prone to adopt innovations.
Specific CF practices affected by the factor	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • "All" (3) • "Efficient use of fertilizers and pesticides, cover crops and conservation tillage" 	

#126	Difficulties in cooperation	
Description	Cooperation between farmers is difficult to achieve, even if it helps in implementing the investments needed to promote adoption	
Explicitly mentioned in the literature as relevant for Carbon Farming	Y	
Factor type: Hindering/facilitating	Hindering	
Type of CFP for which is relevant (according to the source)	Reduced/zero tillage	
Concerned actors	Farmers; farmers organisations	
Gender perspective is considered in the analysis of the factor	N	
Sources:	52	
<i>Some descriptive elements of the factor (based on respondents' answers)</i>		
Knowledge among interviewees	Known	
Relevance	Relevant	
Land use and/or landscapes most affected by the factor	All	
Geographical are this factor is most present	All, but not specific mention for international level	
Different impact of the factor on the actors involved		
Specific CF practices affected by the factor		
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • "All" (2) • "All. Even if CFPs are known, their adaptation to local conditions requires farmers' expertise, trials in their exploitations and peer-to-peer cooperation and exchange of knowledge" • "Practices which might require sharing of equipment e.g., no-till" • "Relevant foe practices where cooperation is needed or neighbours are affected, such as paludiculture" 		

#127 Farming vs forestry	
Description	Farmers in many countries tend to have a negative attitude towards woodland planting; Agro-forestry implies significant overall changes hampering the adoption including the permanent nature of the change, significant shift in the farming systems with legal and economic implications and uncertainty for farmers. There could be a perceived loss of autonomy of farmers once they are told where to plant trees
Explicitly mentioned in the literature as relevant for Carbon Farming	Y
Factor type: Hindering/facilitating	Hindering
Type of CFP for which is relevant (according to the source)	Agroforestry
Concerned actors	Famers
Gender perspective is considered in the analysis of the factor	N
Sources:	23; 49; 67
<i>Some descriptive elements of the factor (based on respondents' answers)</i>	
Knowledge among interviewees	Known
Relevance	Relevant
Land use and/or landscapes most affected by the factor	All especially croplands and grasslands
Geographical are this factor is most present	All
Different impact of the factor on the actors involved	No
Specific CF practices affected by the factor	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • “Relevant only for measures including tree-planting” • “Tree planting, agroforestry” • “Afforestation” • “Agroforestry” • “The whole farming” 	

#128 Consumer habits and expectations	
Description	Cultural barriers linked to consumer habits and expectations could impact the ways farmers approach innovation.
Explicitly mentioned in the literature as relevant for Carbon Farming	N
Factor type: Hindering/facilitating	It depends
Type of CFP for which is relevant (according to the source)	General
Concerned actors	Farmers
Gender perspective is considered in the analysis of the factor	N
Sources:	44
<i>Knowledge (based on respondents' answers)</i>	

Knowledge among interviewees	Known	Relevance	Very Relevant
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#129	Opposition to specific practices by professionals		
Description	There are some practices that are not approved by particular categories of professionals as in the case of the opposition of veterinaries to Feeding ionophores/probiotics to livestock		
Explicitly mentioned in the literature as relevant for Carbon Farming	N		
Factor type: Hindering/facilitating	Hindering		
Type of CFP for which is relevant (according to the source)	Feeding ionophores/probiotics to livestock		
Concerned actors	Professionals of the agricultural sector		
Gender perspective is considered in the analysis of the factor	N		
Sources:	23		
<i>Knowledge (based on respondents' answers)</i>			
Knowledge among interviewees	Little Known	Relevance	Little Relevant

11. Access/Lack of basic Infrastructures and technologies

#130 Lack of infrastructure and complementary inputs are necessary	
Description	Implementing changes and adopting climate-friendly agriculture measures needs, in many situations, dedicated infrastructures. Lack of such infrastructure is a barrier to the adoption of new practices.
Explicitly mentioned in the literature as relevant for Carbon Farming	N
Factor type: Hindering/facilitating	Hindering
Type of CFP for which is relevant (according to the source)	General
Concerned actors	Famers, local authorities, policymakers
Gender perspective is considered in the analysis of the factor	N
Sources:	67
<i>Knowledge (based on respondents' answers)</i>	
Knowledge among interviewees	Known
Relevance	Very Relevant

#131 Internet access	
Description	Technological infrastructures such as internet (and the access to it) can support BMP adoption
Explicitly mentioned in the literature as relevant for Carbon Farming	N
Factor type: Hindering/facilitating	Facilitating
Type of CFP for which is relevant (according to the source)	General
Concerned actors	Farmers, technology providers, policy makers
Gender perspective is considered in the analysis of the factor	N
Sources:	43
<i>Knowledge (based on respondents' answers)</i>	
Knowledge among interviewees	Known
Relevance	Relevant

#132 Accessibility of necessary technology	
Description	The existence and accessibility to the necessary technology for the adoption of new agricultural practice is a facilitating factor
Explicitly mentioned in the literature as relevant for Carbon Farming	N
Factor type: Hindering/facilitating	Facilitating
Type of CFP for which is relevant (according to the source)	General
Concerned actors	Farmers, technology providers, policy makers
Gender perspective is considered in the analysis of the factor	N
Sources:	5

<i>Knowledge (based on respondents' answers)</i>			
Knowledge among interviewees	Known	Relevance	Very Relevant

12. Gendered different behaviour

#133	Genderized communication		
Description	Genderized communication about the advantages of new practices has been found relevant for women		
Explicitly mentioned in the literature as relevant for Carbon Farming	N		
Factor type: Hindering/facilitating	Facilitating		
Type of CFP for which is relevant (according to the source)	General		
Concerned actors	Women farmers		
Gender perspective is considered in the analysis of the factor	Y		
Sources:	43		
<i>Knowledge (based on respondents' answers)</i>			
Knowledge among interviewees	Little Known	Relevance	Relevant

#134	Women more likely adopt new practices		
Description	Some studies found that in some countries, women more likely adopt new practices, notwithstanding – on the average – a lower level of knowledge about certain technologies.		
Explicitly mentioned in the literature as relevant for Carbon Farming	N		
Factor type: Hindering/facilitating	Facilitating		
Type of CFP for which is relevant (according to the source)	General		
Concerned actors	Women farmers		
Gender perspective is considered in the analysis of the factor	Y		
Sources:	43		
<i>Knowledge (based on respondents' answers)</i>			
Knowledge among interviewees	Little Known	Relevance	Very Relevant

Sources of the documentary analysis

Below are reported the references of the main texts that have been consulted for drafting the Map. Among these texts, those that contributed to the definition of the factors are reported in each form with the related number under the heading 'source'.

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Annex 2

Questions for the workshops

Casale Monferrato

Round 1	What are the most important benefits that might be achieved through the adoption of CFPs/management practices?
Round 1	What are the CFPs that you consider most important to be adopted because associated with productivity and environmental co-benefits (win-win approach), which are the most suitable in this Region?
Round 1	What are the possible factors, measures, and solutions that might help to support farmers in the adoption of CFPs, in general and in particular in this Region?
Round 2	What are the main barriers, concerns, obstacles, problems, hindering factors to the adoption of CFPs by farmers in your country and, particularly, in your region with reference to agroforestry
Round 2	What are the main needs that should be addressed for supporting an effective and feasible adoption of CFPs in cropland plots in this region?
Round 2	What are, among the existing CF management practices, those that you consider less effective and not feasible to put in practice, and why? What are the main challenges for the implementation of these new management practices by farmers in this Region?
Round 3	What are the main strengths of Europe-wide or regional certification frameworks/schemes? à
Round 3	What are the critical aspects or limitations of these certification schemes at local/national level and at EU level?
Round 3	What are your suggestions and recommendations for policy improvement in the sector of CF, at local, regional, national and EU level?

Dorinne

Round 1	What are the most important benefits that might be achieved through the adoption of CFPs/management practices?
Round 1	What are the CFPs that you consider most important to be adopted because associated with productivity and environmental co-benefits (win-win approach), which are the most suitable in the context of Wallonia?
Round 2	What are the main barriers, concerns, obstacles, problems, hindering factors to the adoption of CFPs by farmers in your country and, particularly, in the Namur region/Wallonia with reference to cropland or grasslands land use/plots systems ?
Round 2	How gender and other farmers characteristics, or farms features, is related to the adoption of different kind of CFPs? Are there specific barriers/obstacles/needs of support affecting male or female farmers differently? How do farmers' gender matter (or other diversity) matter for the positive or negative orientation to the adoption of Carbon Farming Practices? Can you report, if any, concrete examples for further discussion?
Round 3	What are the main strengths of Europe-wide or regional certification frameworks/schemes? à
Round 3	What are the critical aspects or limitations of these certification schemes at local/national level and at EU level?
Round 3	What are your suggestions and recommendations for policy improvement in the sector of CF, at local, regional, national and EU level?

Amalie

Round 1	What are the most important benefits that might be achieved through the adoption of CFPs/management practices?
Round 1	What are the CFPs that you consider most important to be adopted because associated with productivity and environmental co-benefits (win-win approach), which are the most suitable in the context of Czech Republic?
Round 1	What are the possible factors, measures, and solutions that might help to support farmers in the adoption of CFPs, in general and in particular in this region?
Round 2	What are the main needs that should be addressed for supporting an effective and feasible adoption of CFPs in cropland or grasslands plots in this region (and for farmers in particular: in your farm or other farm with whom you collaborate)?
Round 2	What are, among the existing CF management practices, those that you consider less effective and not feasible to put in practice, and why? What are the main challenges for the implementation of these new management practices by farmers in this region?
Round 2	What are the main barriers, concerns, obstacles, problems, hindering factors to the adoption of CFPs by farmers in your country and, particularly, in your region with reference to croplands
Round 2	How gender and other farmers characteristics, or farms features, is related to the adoption of different kind of CFPs? Are there specific barriers/obstacles/needs of support affecting male or female farmers differently? How do farmers' gender matter (or other diversity) matter for the positive or negative orientation to the adoption of Carbon Farming Practices? Can you report, if any, concrete examples for further discussion?
Round 3	What are the main strengths of Europe-wide or regional certification frameworks/schemes?
Round 3	What are the critical aspects or limitations of these certification schemes at local/national level and at EU level?
Round 3	What are your suggestions and recommendations for policy improvement in the sector of CF, at local, regional, national and EU level?

Milan

Round 1	What are the most important benefits that might be achieved through the adoption of CFPs/management practices?
Round 1	What are the CFPs that you consider most important to be adopted because associated with productivity and environmental co-benefits (win-win approach), which are the most suitable in your context?
Round 1	What are the possible factors, measures, and solutions that might help to support farmers in the adoption of CFPs, in general and in particular in this region?
Round 2	What are the main needs to be met to support a real and feasible adoption of Carbon Farming practices on farmland in our region and in particular in your company and in the companies with which you collaborate?
Round 2	Which carbon farming practices do you consider less feasible or more difficult to implement and why? What are the main challenges to make these practices feasible in our environmental and cultural context?

Round 2	What are the main factors that hinder or create problems for the adoption of Carbon Farming practices in our country and in particular in our region with particular reference to land dedicated to agricultural crops?
Round 3	What are the possible strengths of a European or Regional Carbon Farming certification scheme?
Round 3	What are the critical aspects and limitations of these certification schemes designed at local or European level?
Round 3	What are your suggestions and recommendations for policy improvement in the sector of CF, at local, regional, national and EU level?

Madrid

The Madrid workshop was focused on two different land uses. People were distributed in two groups, one for each land use, and then in sub-groups of 5-6 and carried out two sessions.

Barriers and opportunities were respectively identified in the first and second sessions at each table, by using flipcharts, sticky notes, and facilitation by moderators, and focusing the identification of Carbon Farming Practices (CFPs) suited for the two types of land-uses and those barriers related to their implementation, along with MRV and VCM constraints associated with them. The second session was devoted to the identification of solutions to overcome the barriers found in the previous session.

